

**CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES (SEZ) AND
RURAL DEVELOPMENT IN MAHARASHTRA STATE
WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO KONKAN AND MARATHWADA REGION
[2006-2013]**

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the thesis entitled “**Critical Analysis of Special Economic Zones (SEZs) and Rural Development in Maharashtra State - with special reference to Konkan and Marathwada regions (2006-2013)**”, has been presented by **Mr. Dhoke Satish Manikrao** Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad for the award the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) in Commerce has been carried out under my supervision and guidance. This is the original research work done by him. No part of this thesis is published elsewhere to the best of my knowledge. The matter presented in the thesis has not been submitted earlier for the award of the Ph.D. Degree or any other similar degree of the Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad or any other University.

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Abstract

The present study tries to examine the critical analysis of Special Economic Zone (SEZs) and Rural Development in Maharashtra State with special reference to Konkan and Marathwada Regions. The Special Economic Zones (SEZs) and socio-economic development in the selected regions in Konkan and Marathwada for overall social, cultural, political, economic, and regional development, infrastructure development, technological development, overall development of stakeholders in project affected areas in Konkan and Marathwada regions in the state of Maharashtra and their socio-economic development through implementation of SEZs. The main objective of the Socio-economic development of selected regions is to prepare demographic and growth profiles of all the villages under the focused areas; to assess socio-economic characteristics of the people; to assess the nature of existing resources and means of livelihood; to examine possible impact of the project on local population due to their displacement, loss of land, and other means of livelihood etc.; and an last but not the least, to evolve preliminary suggestion and guidelines for an effective R&R of the 'project affected persons (PASs).

The Government of India introduced a Special Economic Zone (SEZ) Policy. The aim of the SEZ policy is to promote export oriented industrial and economic development. Through SEZs it is expected that it should act as engines of high economic growth. But policymakers forget other side of the story and the tragic story is that the common people in the affected areas are being alienated from land on which their traditional habitats have been located and on which their traditional livelihoods depends. It is often not realized and recognized that while land ownership in rural areas is limited to a few families the fact is that the lives of several more families depend upon that same land although they may not own it.

The study focuses on the SEZs and Socio-Economic development in selected regions of Maharashtra within the framework of rural development and address social justice to the marginalized sections of the society. This study is an account of the people's struggle for their livelihood rights especially land, water, and forest and employment rights. It also describes the opposition of the affected people to the concept of Special Economic Zone, which is, from the point of view of general public anti-poor, anti-labour, anti-farmers, and anti-people in general, and various issues. Hence, the situation has challenged the establishment of SEZs in Maharashtra and across the country.

In recent years, the debate over government land acquisition for industrial projects and development through Special Economic Zones (SEZ) has grown increasingly controversial. Throughout India, people have been resisting the forceful land acquisition for development projects and related issues of displacement, loss of livelihood, employment insecurity, disrespect for local self-governance, and exclusion of marginalized communities. Opposition to SEZs by affected communities has primarily taken two forms: whilst some have used violent methods to express resistance and others have employed non-violent tactics of political activism to express their needs.

The development of SEZs and change in land use will have a catalytic and transformative impact on socio-economic, political, and cultural life of people /farmers the regions as a whole. The land use pattern will undergo a dramatic changes affecting peoples in the above mention aspect. Therefore, it becomes a prerequisite to gauge the possible impact on the socio-economic status of the inhabitant of the area. It will help to address the issue of rehabilitation and resettlement (R & R) systematically. Moreover, it will equip the development agent with pre-request skill, information and knowledge required for the rehabilitation of the projected affect persons (PAPs), and development aspects of SEZs project..

Statement of the Problem

The “Critical Analysis of Special Economic Zones (SEZ) and Rural Development in Maharashtra State” With Special Reference to Konkan and Marathwada Region”, aim’s study the socio-Economic aspects of Marathwada and Konkan region. The study is mainly focused on the various types of SEZs that are developed in the said regions. This study highlights on the problems during the development of SEZ and land acquisition process, compensation process. It gives suitable suggestions to improve the performance.

The researcher studied Sustainable Operation of Special Economic Zones in Maharashtra: *Critical analysis of Study of Marathwada and Konkan regions*. In 2005, the Government of India (GoI) introduced the Special Economic Zone (SEZ) Act, which changed the way India attracted foreign investors who wanted to utilize the country’s natural and human capital.

Significance of the Study

The State has adopted the Special Economic Zone (SEZ) Policy with effect from 10th February, 2006. Up to November 2009, in all 225 SEZ proposals were received in the State, of which the Central Government (108 formal and 36 in-principle approvals)

approved 144 and 58 proposals were notified. Out of 144 approved SEZs, 59 are information technology/information technology enabled services, 57 are single-product, 16 are multi-product and 12 are multi services. The area wise proposals approved, land requirement, investments therein and likely employment generation through these SEZs.

The SEZ units highlights on the Maharashtra particularly in no. of units i.e. Konkan- 69, Western Maharashtra-50, Marathwada-15, Vidarbha-10, overall total no of units at present are 144. With the above information for total Area acquired (Hec.) 45,392 and proposed total investment & employment (lack) show the area wise Investment Rs. (crore) 1, 89,148. A total Employment of SEZs units in Maharashtra is 65.25 and in Marathwada region is 1.53 (lack).

Objectives of the Study

- (1) To study the Special economic zones (SEZs) and its impact on Socio-economic Development of Rural peoples in Konkan and Marathwada region.
- (2) To know the policy of Govt. behind the Special Economic Zones (SEZs) and its effective implementation.
- (3) To analyse the Performance of Special economic zones (SEZ) in general and Konkan and Marathwada region in particular.
- (4) To study the SEZs and Its impact on rural development. i.e. employment, entrepreneurship, Social, Economic, and overall industrial development.
- (5) To know the Problems and prospects of Special economic zones (SEZs) and its impact on Konkan and Marathwada region Industrial area.

The Government of India passed Special Economic Zone Policy Act in the year 2005. As proposed, the Act is aimed at promoting export oriented industrial economic development in India. As of now, 1064 SEZs have received approval for setting up industrial zones across the country to carry out the objectives laid out in the Act. These SEZs are, on the one side, meant for promoting economic growth, and on the other hand, they have attracted pervasive discontent amongst farmers, workers and common people. Due to enactment of SEZs policy, many of the affected people in and around SEZ area have to relocate their homes, loose land assets and thus lead a completely disturbed life. Indeed, the SEZ Policy has raised subsidiary fundamental questions confronted by general public. Hence it is need of the hour to address the socio-economic impact on the general public in Marathwada and Konkan regions.

The present study deals with the data analysis and interpretation of responses collected during the field survey based on the scheduled questionnaire. The data acquired primarily focusses on livelihood patterns of affected people who lost their land assets and employment resources. This study uncovers the impact of the SEZ Act in Marathwada and Konkan Region of Maharashtra. The analysis and interpretation is based on field survey undertaken in SEZs units in study area. For the purpose, over 200 respondents, 100 from each of the regions, including male and female workers, farmers, landowners, were selected who are directly and indirectly affected in SEZ units operational in the regions. It has been observed that majority of the farmers and general public in Navi Mumbai, Raigad, Ratnagiri of **Konkan region and Nanded, Latur, and Aurangabad** in Marathwada region staged protest against SEZ projects in the respective regions.

The present study deals with important aspects of Special Economic Zone (SEZs) and Rural Development. The government of India (GoI) introduced a Special Economic Zone (SEZ) Policy. The aim of the Policy is to promote export oriented industrial and economic development for the proponents of rapid development of India. SEZs are considered as engines of high economic growth. Agriculture and allied activities are largest sectors in Indian economy and employing about 60 % of the total population. It contributes about 25 % GDP and provides forward and backward linkage to industry and service sectors. The main objectives of SEZs policy is to create employment opportunities for introducing better facility, to improve lifestyle of rural area and develop industrial corridor of manufacturers and service sector, provide sustainable rural development in agriculture most particularly to farmers, poor people and landless people, to get employment opportunities, to increase income sources directly and indirectly. Overall attitude towards the SEZs project is to develop import-export services thereby attract foreign investors. The government provide such types of infrastructural facility for Special Economic Zone (SEZs) projects in order to start manufacturing units, to develop industrial sector and increase foreign direct investment for sustainable economic development to the backward region and rural area and thereby provide better facility through road, transportation, water, electricity, communication facility, health facility, education, and generation of employment opportunities.

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DECLARATION

I, hereby declares that the said research work of this thesis entitled, **“Critical Analysis of Special Economic Zones (SEZ) and Rural Development in Maharashtra State with special reference to Konkan and Marathwada Regions (2006-2013)”** is carried out under the guidance of **Dr. Kishor L. Salve, Principal & Research Guide, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar College of Art’s & Commerce, Nagsenvana Aurangabad.** The work is original and has not been submitted in part or in full to any other University or institute for award of any research degree. The extent of information derived from the existing literature has been indicated in the body of the thesis at appropriate places giving the references.

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ABBREVIATION

ASIDE	- Assistance to State for Developing Export
BOA	- Board of Approval
CST	- Central Sales Tax
DC	- Department of Commerce
DC	- Development Commissioner
DIC	- District Industries Centre
DTA	- Domestic Tariff Area
EOU	- Export Oriented Unites
EPZ	- Export Processing Zone
FA	- Formal Approvals
FDI	- Foreign Direct Investment
FII's	- Foreign Institutional Investors
FTZ	- Free Trade Zone
GDP	- Gross Domestic Product
GOI	- Government of India
GSDP	Gross State Domestic Product
ICFTU	- International Confederation of Free Trades Union
ILO	International Labour Office
IMF	- International Monetary Funds
IP	- Principles Approvals
MES	- Maharashtra Economic Survey
MIDC	- Maharashtra Industrial Development Corporation
MMSEZ	- Maha Mumbai Special Economi Zones
MNC	- Multi-National Corporation
NPA	- Non-Processing Area
PAS	- Project Affected Persons
R & D	- Research & Development
R & R	- Resettlement & Rehabilitation
RBI	- Reserve Bank of India
SEEPZ	- Santacruz Electronic Export Processing Zone
SEZ	- Special Economic Zone
STP	- Software Technology Park
VAT	- Value Added Tax
WB	- World Bank
WEPZA	- World Export Processing Zone Association
WTO	- World Trade Organization
ZACB	- Zonal Approval Committee Board

CHAPTER - I

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Introduction

This section introduces the concept of SEZ. It highlights on need and importance of SEZ, industrial sites, relevance of the study, objectives, the research methodology adopted by the researcher, tools and techniques used for the data analysis and area presentation of the study. A Special Economic Zone, abbreviated as SEZ, is a geographically bound zone where the economic laws in matters related to export and import are more broadminded and liberal as compared to rest of the parts of the country. SEZs are projected as duty free area for the purpose of trade, operations, duty and tariffs. Such industrial units are self-contained and integrated having their own infrastructure and support services. Within SEZs, industrial unit may be established undertake manufacturing activities including processing, assembling, trading, repairing, reconditioning, unearthing precious metals like gold, silver, platinum jewellery etc. Generally, SEZs are constructed by utilizing an array of institutional compositions varying from complete government-owned organizations to privately-owned firms.

In some cases, the government-owned organizations perform as quasigovernment groups in which they follow a pseudo-corporate organization composition and have total control over their budget construction. SEZs are also constructed under the tie-up of private and government organizations where the government sector offer's assistance by introducing provisions on infrastructure, investment, issue of bonds & debentures, etc. This enables the private industry to attain a considerable rate of return on the venture. Hence, Special Economic Zones (SEZs) are specifically delineated duty-free enclaves treated as foreign territory for the purpose of trade operations, duties and tariffs. They offer total exemption from most of the duties and taxes.

1.2. HISTORY OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONE

Prior to the Second World War during 1930s the world experienced a recession period that contributed to the global changing scenario. In this period each and every country tried to improve and develop its economic condition. One of the part of the plan was, since 1929, to increase import and setup Special Economic Zones after air land. **In the year 1956 it was gradually termed as** Import Process Zones. After the process of Hong Kong, Taiwan, Malaysia, Singapore, development of import–export planning became substitute structure and the involved stakeholder countries felt the need to be develop the zones.

World's first Free Zone concept started in Puerto Rico in 1947 with the aim of attracting firms from USA. In accordance in the year 1951 it passed the Tax Exemption law. The concept of Free Zone greatly affected economy as can be seen from following points:

- Per Capita GNP grew over 45 times in 40 years
- Employment grew by 9% per annum
- Higher education went up from 2% to 60% in 40 years

India recognized the effectiveness of Export Processing Zone (EPZ) in mid-sixties and came up with Asia's first structured EPZ at Kandla in 1965 followed by seven other such zones which were later set up in Mumbai, Chennai, Surat, Falta, Kochi, Noida and Vizag. The spread of SEZ in initial years was very slow and the concept gained popularity only after the success of Chinese SEZs.

The concept of SEZ can also be traced back to Ireland where the first Export Processing Zone was set up in 1960. However, it was in China that the SEZ model became successful on large scale. Starting in 1980s, China today has more than 1500 open zones, under various names. According to World Bank estimates, there are about 3000 running place in SEZs in 120 countries.

1.2.1. EMERGENCE OF SEZs IN INDIA

Special Economic Zones in India were established in an attempt to accelerate foreign investment and encourage exports from India. They recognized the need of a global platform to expose and explore the domestic firms and producers to the competitive world market.

For a country like us, faster economic growth, industrialization and development of infrastructure are two primary needs of the hours. This naturally required a amount of capital outlay which could not be met by domestic investors and thus emerged the need for vast amounts of foreign capital (FDI). To attract Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) several measures were taken including attractive fiscal packages, both at the Central and State government level, with minimum possible regulations (single window clearance). The intention of the policy maker is to make SEZs an engine for economic growth.

1.2.2. History of SEZs in India

The seeds of the Special Economic Zone (SEZ) were sown in the mid-sixties. Present day basic model of Indian Special Economic Zone was structured with the establishment of the first Export Processing Zone (EPZ) at Kandla in the year 1965. Several other Export Processing Zones were set up in various parts of India in the subsequent years. But The lack of good economic policy and inefficient management hampered the success of these Export Processing Zones. Thus, the performance of these Export Processing Zones of India fell short of expectations.

The modern day Special Economic Zone came into existence because the economic reforms incorporated in the early 1990s did not result in the overall growth of the Indian economy. The SEZ policy of India was devised to act as a catalyst to achieve the economic growth of the early 1990s. The economic reforms formulated during the 1990s did not produce the desired results. The Indian manufacturing sector witnessed a sudden dip in the overall growth of the industry, during the second-half of 1990s. Red tape, lengthy

administrative procedures, rigid labour laws and poor physical infrastructural facilities were the main cause of decline in Foreign Direct Investments (FDI) inflow into India. Further, the Indian markets were not mature enough to facilitate easy entry of Foreign Institutional Investors (FIIs) into the Indian economic system. Also, the legal framework of Indian economy was not strong enough to prevent misuse of Indian markets by the foreign investors. Thus, the lack of investor friendly environment in India prevented growth of Indian industry, in spite of implementation of liberal economic policy by the central government. This led to in the formation of a much larger and more efficient form with world-class infrastructural facility.

The present day Special Economic Zone policies of India was well complemented by the provisions of the Acts and Rules of Special Economic Zone. A number of meetings were held across India for the formulation of - 'The Special Economic Zones Act, 2005', which was subsequently passed by Parliament in May 2005.

The SEZ Act, 2005 and SEZ Rules became effective on and from 10th February 2006. The SEZ Act 2005 defines the key role for the State Governments in Export Promotion and creation of infrastructural facilities. A Single Window SEZ approval mechanism has been facilitated through a 19 member inter-ministerial SEZ Board of Approval or BOA; and the decision of the SEZ Board of Approval was made binding and final.

1.2.3. Indian Perspective

India pursued restrictive import substitution policies in terms of Government's announcement in Lok Sabha in April 1960 to establish the first Free Trade Zones (FTZ) at Kandla (KAFTZ) in Gujarat. The zone becomes operational in the year 1966-67. India, thus acquired the distinction of establishing the First FTZ in Asia and Second amongst the developing countries next only to Puerto Rico. Then Export Processing Zone were setup at Bombay and four more EPZs in 1980s at Calcutta, Cochin, Madras and NOIDA followed by yet another at Vishakhapatnam. The EPZs in India were

developed, owned and managed by the Central Government; and the zone units were permitted of processing or manufacturing with project specific value addition for strict compliance. In absence of conducive macroeconomic policy framework, inadequate infrastructure, lack of promotional strategy, the performance was not significant in terms of contribution exports, foreign exchange earnings, foreign direct investment and GDP. The prevailing scenario was appropriately described as, ‘if the EPZ are ‘grafted’ in isolation on an inward looking economy, their performance will not be optimal as is borne out by the Indian experience.’

Chinese development strategy of export-led growth, developing Special Economic Zones as the vanguard in its opening up drives has been, by all account, highly successful. It has been instrumental for country’s rapid economic development. With annual rates of growth in economic output and foreign trade that averaged nearly 10 percent respectively during 1978-2000, China’s performance has, in many ways, become the envy of the world countries: developed and developing alike.

Now, India has embarked upon an ambitious plan to emulate the Chinese model of Special Economic Zones to boost exports, attract FDIs and thereby accelerating economic progress. The new Export & Import Policy effective from April 01, 2000 was introduced for setting up of Special Economic Zones in the country with a view to provide an internationally complete, re-engineering and service activities. Eminent economist, **Meghnad Desai** is of the view that:

“Specific manufacturing growth strategy would be required for a growth rate in manufacturing at 12 to 15 percent with an aim of doubling the manufacturing labour force from the present of around 40 million to 80 million over 20 years. China achieved such a rate between 1980 and 2000. There is no reason why Indian cannot do the same.”

India was one of the first country in Asia to recognize the effectiveness of the Export Processing Zone (EPZ) model in promoting exports, with Asia's

first EPZ set up in Kandla in 1965. With a view to overcome the shortcomings experienced on account of the multiplicity of controls and clearances; absence of world-class infrastructure, and an unstable fiscal regime and with a view to attract larger foreign investments in India, the Special Economic Zones (SEZs) Policy was announced in April 2000.

In India, at present , current fact sheet on Special Economic Zones are following: No. of Formal approvals -574 and Number of notified SEZs (As on 26th February, 2010) – 350 (out of 573) + (7 Central Govt. + 12 State/Pvt. SEZs); Number of valid In-Principle Approvals 151; Operational SEZs (As on 31st December, 2009) - 105 (Out of this 15 are multi product SEZs, remaining are IT/ITES; Engineering, electronic hardware, textiles, Biotechnology, Gem& Jewellery SEZs and other sector specific SEZs); Units approved in SEZs (As on 31st December, 2009)- 2,761.

Land allocated for SEZs: - Notified SEZs-42,888Ha; Formal Approvals (FA) incl. notified SEZs-74,883 Ha; Valid In-Principles approvals (IP)- 1,26,963 Ha; Total area for proposed SEZs (FA+IP)- 2,01,845 Ha; Total area for the notified SEZs would not be more than 0.014% of the total land area of India. Land is a state subject. Land for SEZs is procured as per the policy and procedures of the respective State Govts.

Investment - As on 31th December, 2009 SEZs notified under the Act Incremental Investment Rs. 1,15,603.78/- Crore; **State/Pvt. SEZs set up before 2006;** Incremental Investment Rs. 5,043.39 crore and Rs 6,799.70 crore, **Central Government SEZs** - Incremental Investment Rs. 3,707.76/- crore; Rs. 5,986.96/- crore; **Total** Incremental Investment Rs. 1,24,354.93/- crore, Rs. 1,28,390.44/- crore.

Employment - As on 31st December, 2009 SEZs Notified under the Act Incremental Employment- 2,27,669 persons; Total Employment-2,27,669 persons; State/Pvt. SEZs set up before 2006: Incremental Employment 48,787 persons; Total Employment- 61,255 persons; Central Government SEZs: Incremental Employment-78,671 persons; Total Employment-2,00,907

persons. **Total:-** Incremental Employment-2,27,946 persons; Total Employment-3,62,650 persons;

Exports in 2008-09: Rs. 99,689 crore (Growth of 50% over 2007-08)
Overall growth of exports of 620% in five years (2004-2009);

Exports in 2009-10 (As on 31st December,2009) Rs. 1,52,092.685 crore
(Growth of 127% over the corresponding period of Financial Year 2008-09).

1.3. SALIENT FEATURES OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES

- ✚ Indian SEZs are developed by government, private and joint sector, unlike its international counterparts where zones are chiefly maintained by their respective governments. This provides equal prospects to both Indian and global players.
- ✚ Government has allocated a least favorable area of 1,000 hectares for green-field SEZs. There is however, no limitation in the context of favorable area in constructing sector specific SEZs.
- ✚ 100% of Foreign Direct Investment is allowed for all endowments in Special Economic Zones, apart from activities cataloged under the unconstructive record.
- ✚ SEZ divisions are obligatory to encourage net foreign exchange yielders and are not entitled to any least amount of value addition guidelines or export responsibilities.
- ✚ Commodity surge from Domestic Tariff Area (DTA) into a SEZ is recognized as exports and commodity surge into DTA from SEZ are recognized as imports.

1.4. BENEFITS OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES

- ✚ Income tax exemption.
- ✚ Manufacturing industry is allowed FDI influx of 100% via automatic channels excluding a few industries.
- ✚ Services can establish off-shore banking divisions in SEZs.
- ✚ Service Tax and Central Sales Tax exemption.

- ✚ External commercial lending of up to US\$500 million is allowed for SEZ divisions in a year sans any maturity limitations via certified banking networks.
- ✚ No import authorization obligations.
- ✚ SEZ franchisees are allowed 100% FDI in offering customary telephone facilities in the areas.
- ✚ No limitation of foreign endowments for small scale industry reticent products.
- ✚ Tax relief from sectoral authorization obligations for goods reticent for SSI industry.
- ✚ Tax relief from custom tariff on import of merchandize, raw products, spare parts etc.
- ✚ Tax relief from Central Excise tariff on acquirement of merchandize, raw products, spare parts etc from the local market.
- ✚ No regular assessments by Customs for export and import freight.
- ✚ Capacity to comprehend and repatriate export advances within a year.
- ✚ Revenues permitted to be repatriated sans any dividend assessment needs.

1.5. CONCEPT OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES (SEZS):

A Special Economic Zone in short SEZ is a geographically bound zone where the economic laws in matters related to export and import are more broadminded and liberal as compared to rest parts of the country. SEZs are projected as duty free area for the purpose of trade, operations, duty and tariffs. SEZ units are self-contained and integrated having their own infrastructure and support services.

1.5.1. Meaning of SEZ Act

In this Act, unless there is something repugnant in the subject context “Act”, means the State SEZ Act 2002. “**Special Economic Zones (SEZ)**”, means a geographical area is declared and notified as Special Economic Zones by Government of India (GOI). “**Unit**”, means a unit / enterprises in whole or

part which occupies space within zones for carrying out its approved business. “Zones”, means Special Economic Zones constituted from and /or developed within the specified area under provision of this Act.

What are special economic Zones?

Special Economic Zones means a geographical area declared and notified as Special Economic Zones by government of India was announced since dated 31 August, 2004 through policy announced from 2004-2009.

1.5.2. Definition of special Economic Zone:

“SEZ is a specifically delineated duty free enclave and shall be deemed to be foreign territory for purposes of trade operations and duties and tariffs”.

As per law, SEZ units are deemed to be outside the customs territory of India. Goods and services coming into SEZs from the domestic tariff area or DTA are treated as exports from India and goods and services rendered from the SEZ to the DTA are treated as imports into India.

The proposed legislation on SEZs to be enacted in the near future would cover the concepts of the developer and co- developer, fiscal concessions under the Income Tax and Customs Act provide for Offshore Banking Units (OBUs) etc. A brief on the facilities available under the SEZ scheme is given as under:

Scheme - This may be called the Special Economic Zones Scheme.

For the purposes of Special Economic Zone scheme, unless the context otherwise requires, the following words and expressions shall have the meanings attached to them as given in the Policy.

1.5.3. Status of SEZs

- 1) Special Economic Zone (SEZ) is a specifically delineated duty free enclave and shall be deemed to be foreign territory for the purposes of trade operations and duties and tariffs.
- 2) Goods and services going into the SEZ area from DTA shall be treated as exports and goods and services coming from the SEZ area into DTA shall be treated as if these are being imported.

- 3) The Special Economic Zones may have areas, demarcated as,-
 - a) Processing areas for setting up of units for production of goods and rendering of services; and
 - b) Non-processing areas, if any.

1.5.4. Identification of Special Economic Zones

- A) The State government may identify any areas or areas to be a Special Economic Zones and may invite or accept proposals for the development of such area as Special Economic Zones, in such manner as may be prescribed.
- B) The proposal for establishing a Special Economic Zones shall be forwarded by the State Government to the Central Government for its approval.
- C) Without prejudice to the provisions of sub-section: (1) and sub-section (2) any area identified as a Special Economic Zones prior to the coming into force of this Act, shall be deemed to have been duly identified as a Special Economic Zone under this section.

1.6. ESTABLISHMENT OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONE

1.6.1. Procedure for making proposal to establish Special Economic Zone

- 1) A Special Economic Zone may be established under this Act, either jointly or severally by the Central Government, State Government, or any person for manufacture of goods or rendering services or for both or as a Free Trade and Warehousing Zone.
- 2) Any person, who intends to set up a Special Economic Zone, may, after identifying the area, make a proposal to the State Government concerned for the purpose of setting up the Special Economic Zone.
- 3) Notwithstanding anything contained in sub-section (2), any person, who intends to set up a Special Economic Zone, may, after identifying the area, at his option, make a proposal directly to the Board for the purpose of setting up the Special Economic Zone. Provided that where such a

proposal has been received directly from a person under sub-section, the Board may grant approval and after receipt of such approval, the person concerned shall obtain the concurrence of the State Government within the period, as may be prescribed.

- 4) In case a State Government intends to set up a Special Economic Zone, it may after identify the area, forward the proposal directly to the Board for the purpose of setting up the Special Economic Zone Provided that the Central Government may: a) after consulting the State Government concerned, b) Without referring the proposal for setting up the Special Economic Zone to the Board, c) after identifying the area; set up and notify the Special Economic Zone.
- 5) Every proposal under sub-sections (2) to (4) shall be made in such form and manner containing such particulars as may be prescribed.
- 6) The State Government may, on receipt of the proposal made under sub-section (2), forward the same together with its recommendations to the Board within such period as may be prescribed.
- 7) Without prejudice to the provisions contained in subsection (8), the Board may, after receipt of the proposal under sub-section (2) to (4), approve the proposal subject to such terms and conditions as it may deem fit to impose, or modify or reject the proposal.
- 8) The Central Government may prescribe the following requirement for establishment of a Special Economic Zone, namely: a) The minimum area of land and other terms and conditions subject to which the Board shall approve, modify or reject any proposal received by it under sub-section (2) to (4); b) The terms and conditions, subject to which the Developer shall undertake the authorized operations and his obligations and entitlements.
- 9) Provided that different minimum area of land and other terms and conditions referred to in clause (a) may be prescribed by the Central Government for a class or classes of Special Economic Zones.

- 10)** If the Board- (a) approves without any modification, the proposal received under sub-section (2) to (4), it shall communicate the same to the Central Government; (b) approves with modifications the proposal received under sub-section (2) to (4), it shall, communicate such modifications to the person or the State Government concerned and if such modifications have been accepted by such person or the State Government, the Board shall communicate the approval to the Central Government; (c) rejects the proposal, received under sub-section (2) to (4), it shall record the reasons therefore and communicate the rejection to the Central Government which shall intimate to the State Government or the person concerned. The Central Government shall, on receipt of communication under clause (a) or clause (b) of sub-section.
- 11)** Grant, within such time as may be prescribed, a letter of approval on such terms and conditions and obligations and entitlements as may be approved by the Board, to the Developer, being the person or the State Government concerned: Provided that the Central Government may, on the basis of approval of the Board, approve more than one Developer in a Special Economic Zone in cases where one Developer does not have in his possession the minimum area of contiguous land, as may be prescribed, for setting up a Special Economic Zone and in such cases, each Developer shall be considered as a Developer in respect of the land in his possession.
- 12)** Any person who, or a State Government which, intends to provide any infrastructure facilities in the identified area referred to in sub-section (2) to (4), or undertake any authorized operation may, after entering into an agreement with the Developer referred to in sub-section (10), make a proposal for the same to the Board for its approval and the provisions of sub-section (5) and sub-sections (7) to (10) shall, as far as may be, apply to the said proposal made by such person or State Government.
- 13)** Every person or a State Government referred to in subsection (11), whose proposal has been approved by the Board and who, or which, has been

granted letter of approval by the Central Government, shall be considered as a Co-Developer of the Special Economic Zone.

- 14) Subject to the provisions of this section and the letter of approval granted to a Developer, the Developer may allocate space or built up area or provide infrastructure services to the approved units in accordance with the agreement entered into by him with the entrepreneurs of such Units.

1.6.2. Establishment of Special Economic Zone and approval for authorization to operate through a developer

1. The Developer shall, after the grant of letter of approval under sub-section (10) of section 3, submit the exact particulars of the identified area referred to in sub-section (2) to (4) of that section, to the Central Government and thereupon that Government may, after satisfying that the requirements, under sub-section (8) of section 3 and other requirements, as may be prescribed, are fulfilled, notify the specifically identified area in the State as a Special.
2. Economic Zone - Provided that an existing Special Economic Zone shall be deemed to have been notified and established in accordance with the provisions of this Act and the provisions of this Act shall, as far as may be, apply to such Zone accordingly. Provided, further the Central Government may, after notifying the Special Economic Zone, if it considers appropriate, notify subsequently any additional area to be included as a part of that Special Economic Zone.
3. After the appointed day, the Board may, authorized the Developer to undertake in a Special Economic Zone, such operations which the Central Government may authorize.

1.6.3. Processing and Non-Processing areas

The areas falling within the Special Economic Zones may be demarcated by the Central Government or any authority specified by it as:

- a) The processing area for setting up Units for activities, being manufacture of goods, or rendering services;

- b) The area exclusively for trading or warehousing purposes; or (c) The non-processing areas for activities other than those specified under clause (a) or clause (b)

1.6.4. Exemption from taxes, duties or Cess

Any goods or services exported out of, or imported into, or procured from the Domestic Tariff Area by-

- (i) A Unit in a Special Economic Zone; or
- (ii) A Developer, subject to such terms, conditions and limitations, as may be prescribed, is exempted from the payment of Taxes, Duties or Cess under all enactments specified in the First Schedule.

1.7. SEZs AND LAND ACQUISITION

SEZs and Land Acquisition are interconnected for in the setting up of SEZs for which huge area of land is required. Land Acquisition and SEZs have picked up speed in India since the Indian government has encouraged the setting up of SEZs in the country. Assessing its role in the growth of Indian economy, country has needed at least 1 thousand hectares or more of land for SEZs; and so Land Acquisition on a massive scale is taking place in India so as to set up more and more SEZs in the country.

SEZs and Land Acquisition is taking place mainly in agricultural lands and the Central and State governments are acquiring the land from the farmers. Across India, the total amount of land, which will be acquired, is around 150,000 hectares and this amount of land is capable of producing around 1 million tons of agricultural produce. The various advantages of SEZs and Land Acquisition in India are that it has helped to bring in huge amounts of foreign currency into the country, increased the number of jobs for the people of the country, and is also expected to bring in highly technologically advanced machines into the country.

However, there are many disadvantages attached to SEZs and Land Acquisition in India. It is estimated that more than 10 lakh people who are

dependent upon agricultural lands will be evicted from their farm lands; due to which as estimated those farming families will have to face loss of around Rs.212 crores each year in total income; and it will also lead to putting the food security of India at risk. Owing to such scenario surrounded by resentment by general public the SEZs and Land Acquisition in India has now resulted in dissent, uproar, and opposition from the farmers, for their livelihood has been put at stake.

SEZs and Land Acquisition has been taking place in India in a very fast pace over the last few years. The government of India must make sure that Land Acquisition and SEZs must prove beneficial for the people of the country and not harmful.

1.7.1. ACQUISITION OF LAND

In the wake of controversies on land acquisition, the Ministry of Commerce and Industry has advised all the State Governments that in case of land acquisition for setting up of Special Economic Zones, first priority should be the acquisition of waste and barren land and, if necessary, single crop agricultural land could be acquired for the SEZs. If a portion of double cropped agricultural land has to be acquired to meet the minimum area requirements, especially for multi-product Special Economic Zones, the same should not exceed 10% of the total land required for the SEZ.

In pursuance of the decision taken by the Empowered Group of Ministers, the Commerce Secretary vide D.O. letter No. H.7/1/2007 dated 15 the June 2007, issued guidelines to the State Governments that the Board of Approval will consider only those cases where the land has been allotted by the State Government or its undertakings out of the land acquired by them for industrial purposes before 5th April, 2007 or where the land was acquired by the State Government/ its undertakings pursuant to SEZ in-principle approval and the land acquisition proceedings are over on or before 5th April, 2007 and there are no disputes relating to such land; or where no land acquisition is involved and the applicant is in possession of the land. The State Governments

were informed that the Board of Approval will not approve any SEZs where the State Governments have carried out or propose to carry out compulsory acquisition of land for such SEZs after 5th April, 2007. The Board of Approval only approves those proposals which are duly recommended by the State Governments.

However, cases in which all persons interested in the land either have not submitted any objection or have withdrawn the objections submitted and have thus acquiesced in the proposed acquisition of land can be considered. In other cases, where there are objections, the Collector/Acquiring Authority may not proceed with the acquisition for the purpose of SEZ and such cases, if any, brought before the Board of Approval may not be considered.

1.7.2. Who can set up an SEZ? And what are the prior requirements for setting up of a SEZ?

An SEZ can be set up jointly or individually either the Central Government, a State government or any other body, including a foreign company, for the purpose of (1) manufacturing goods, (2) rendering services, (3) for both of these reasons or (4) as a Free Trade and Warehousing Zone (FTWZ). The SEZ Rules specify the minimum land area that is required for setting up an SEZ in general. This requirement depends on the type of SEZ to be established. The requirements concerning the minimum size of an SEZ are relaxed with regard to certain small states.

1.7.3. Minimum Land Requirement

The State Government shall forward the proposal within forty five days to the Board of Approvals (*Deputy Secretary, Ministry of Commerce & industry, Department of Commerce, Udyog Bhawan, New Delhi-110011*) after ensuring that the minimum land requirement as per Rule 5 of the SEZ Rules, 2006 has been complied with. Rule 5(2) of SEZ Rules, 2006 lays down the minimum area requirement for development of SEZ. According to Indian constitutional law (see table 1 and 2). Table 2 illustrates some sector specific

SEZs restrictions on foreign-owned equity and other requirement. The minimum area requirements stipulated for various categories of SEZ are:

Table No. 1.1
Minimum Contiguous Area Requirements for Certain Types of SEZs

Type	Area	Area for Special Sates/ UTs
Multi-product	1000 hectares*	200 hectares
Multi-services	100 hectares	100 hectares
Sector specific	100 hectares	50 hectares
Electronic Hardware & Software Including ITES	10 hectares (and min. Built up area of 1 lakh Sq. Mtr. for IT)	10 Hectares
FTWZ	40 hectares (min. Built up area of 1 Lakh sq. mtr.)	40 hectares (min.built up area of 1 lakh sq. mtr.)
Handicraft	10 hectares (min. Built up area of 1 Lakh sq. mtr.)	40 hectares (min.built up area of 1 lakh sq. mtr.)
Bio Technology & Non Conventional Energy	10 hectares (min. Built up area of 40 Thousand sq. mtr.)	10 hectares (min.built up area of 40 thousand. Sq.mtr.)
Gems & Jewellery	10 hectares (min. 10 hectares (min. Thousand sq. mtr.)	10 hectares (min.built up area of 50 thousand Sq.mtr.)
* Not exceeding 5000 hectares		

(Source: INCE-2009 & sezindia.nic.in)

As per proviso to sub Rule 2(a) Rule 5 of SEZ Rules, 2006 at least fifty per cent of the area shall be earmarked for developing the processing area. Development Commissioner of the SEZ shall be authority for demarcating the processing, non-processing area etc. in the SEZ. Provided also that the Central Government may consider on merit the clubbing of contiguous existing notified Special Economic Zones notwithstanding that the total area of resultant Special Economic Zone exceeds 500 hectares.

As per proviso to sub Rule 2 (c) Rule 5 of SEZ Rules, 2006, a Free Trade and Warehousing Zone may also be set up as part of a Special Economic

Zone for multi-product. In a Special Economic Zone having area less than one thousand hectares, Free Trade and Warehousing Zone may be permitted with no minimum area requirement but subject to the condition that the maximum area of such Free Trade and Warehousing Zone shall not exceed twenty per cent of the processing area.

Table No. 1.2
Sector Specific SEZs and Foreign Equity Allowed

Industry/Sector	Foreign Allowed	Comments
Advertising and Film	100%	Certain conditions apply in the film Industry
Alcoholic beverages	100%	Prior Government Approval is need
Automobiles	100%	Automatic approval route available
Cigars/cigarettes of tobacco	100%	There are no automatic approvals and a license From the Defense Ministry is required
Defence and strategic industries	FDI cap of 26%	Automatic approval route is available subject to some conditions
Drugs and pharmaceuticals	100%	Automatic approval route is available except for aerospace and defense sectors.
Information technology	100%	Automatic approval route is available except for certain products.
Manufacturing	100%	FDI limits and incentives vary in subsectors and an approval from the FIPB is required except for Private sector oil refining.
Petrochemicals and Petroleum	Varies:100% And automatic approvals are available in some sectors	Automatic approvals route available for Manufacturing and construction.
Ports and harbors	100%	Automatic approval route available for Construction and maintenance.
Road, highways and mass rapid transit system	100%	Limited to 49 % for the operation and Maintenance of satellites.
Satellites	49%	Licenses well be required in some cases, however 100% FDI is allowed for the manufacturing of telecommunications equipment
Telecommunications	Varies according to sub-sectors	

(Source: INCE-2009)

1.8. PROCEDURE FOR SETTING UP SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONE

Special Economic Zones are specially demarcated geographical regions that have more liberal economic laws as compared to the centralized laws of the country. The very purpose of a SEZ is to develop the area covered under the special economic zone by the following special economic policies.

1.8.1. Procedure of Setting up SEZ Unit in India

SEZ is governed by a three tier administrative set up. The Board of Approval is the apex body in the Department; The Unit Approval Committee at the zonal level dealing with approval of units in the SEZs and other related issues, and Each Zone is headed by a Development Commissioner, who also heads the Unit Approval Committee.

1.8.2. Indian Special Economic Zones - Organizational Set-up

SEZs are controlled by a three tier Organizational Set-up described as under:

Supreme controlling body in the Department is known as The Board of Approval At district level, The Unit Approval Committee tackles with SEZs development and other associated issues every district is led by a Development Commissioner, who also controls the Unit Approval Committee.

1.8.3 Features of SEZ

An SEZ is a geographically demarcated region that has economic laws that are more liberal than the country's typical economic laws and where all the units therein have specific privileges. SEZs are specifically delineated duty-free enclaves and are deemed to be foreign territory for the purposes of trade operations, duties and tariffs. The principal goal is to increase foreign investment. Through the introduction of SEZs, India also wants to enhance its somewhat dismal infrastructural requirements, which, once they have been improved, will invite even more foreign direct investment.

As far as trade and commerce are concerned, SEZs are regarded as international territory wherein local raw materials bought by producers within SEZs are regarded as exports whereas those goods that are produced in SEZs and sold in the DTA (Domestic Tariff Area) are regarded as imports.

Mentioned below are some of the salient features of Indian Special Economic Zones:

Indian SEZs are developed by government, private and joint sector, unlike its international counterparts where zones are chiefly maintained by their respective governments. This provides equal prospects to both Indian and global players.

Government has allocated a least favorable area of 1,000 hectares for green field SEZs. Although, there are no limitation in context of favorable area in constructing sector specific SEZs. 100% of Foreign Direct Investment is allowed for all endowments in Special Economic Zones, apart from activities cataloged under the unconstructive record.

SEZ divisions are obligatory to be encouraging net foreign exchange yielders and are not entitle to any least amount of value addition guidelines or export responsibilities. Commodity surge from Domestic Tariff Area (DTA) into a SEZ is recognized as exports and commodity surge into DTA from SEZ are recognized as imports

The salient features of the Indian SEZ initiative further include the following points

- 1) Unlike most of the international instances where zones are primarily developed by governments, the Indian SEZ policy provides for development of these zones in the government, private or joint sector.
- 2) 100 per cent FDI is permitted for all investments in SEZs, except for activities included in the negative list.
- 3) SEZ units are required to be positive Net foreign-exchange earners and which is not subject to any minimum value addition norms or export obligations.
- 4) Goods flowing into the SEZ area from a domestic tariff area (DTA) are treated as exports, while goods coming from the SEZ into a DTA are treated as imports. In addition to the duty exemptions, the units in the Indian SEZs do not have to pay any income tax for the first five years and only pay half their tax liability for the next two. SEZ developers also enjoy

a 10-year “tax holiday”. The size of an SEZ varies depending on the nature of the SEZ. At least 50 per cent of the area of multi-product or sector-specific SEZs must be used for export purposes. The rest can include malls, hotels, educational institutions, etc. Besides providing state-of-the-art infrastructure and access to a large, well-trained and skilled workforce, the SEZ policy also provides enterprises and developers with a favorable and attractive range of incentives.

- 5) Facilities in the SEZ may retain 100 per cent foreign-exchange receipts in Exchange Earners’ Foreign Currency Accounts.
- 6) 100 per cent FDI is permitted for SEZ franchisees in providing basic telephone services in SEZs.
- 7) No cap on foreign investment for small-scale-sector reserved items which are otherwise restricted.
- 8) Exemption from industrial licensing requirements for items reserved for the small-scale-industries sector.
- 9) No import license requirements.
- 10) Exemption from customs duties on the import of capital goods, raw materials, consumables, spares, etc.
- 11) Exemption from Central Excise duties on procurement of capital goods, raw materials, and consumable spares, etc. from the domestic market.
- 12) No routine examinations by Customs for export and import cargo.
- 13) Facility to realize and repatriate export proceeds within 12 months.
- 14) Profits allowed to be repatriated without any dividend-balancing requirement.
- 15) Exemption from Central Sales Tax and Service Tax

1.8.4. Advantages of Special Economic Zones (SEZs)

India has over 1022 prospective SEZs units to be established. It has more than 09 fully functional SEZs and over 7 Export Processing Zones (EPZs) which have been transformed into SEZs. Each entirely functional SEZs has a standard dimension of 200 acres and are spread in different parts of India.

The need for a Special Economic Zone was realized by India in April 2000 in order to augment the foreign direct investment in the nation, to trigger its exports revenues and to provide a global platform to local firms and manufacturers. Indian government has always been upbeat about the expansion of SEZs and to supplement their plans it has also introduced policies which are assessed on quarterly basis. This ensures the supply of enough facilities to the SEZ developers along with the firms establishing their business units in it.

1.8.5. Indian Special Economic Zones – Benefits

Besides offering high end infrastructure and availability to a large skilled workforce, SEZ also offers attractive incentives and advantages to firms and developers. Mentioned below are some of the benefits of Indian Special Economic Zones:

- Full Income tax exemption for a period of 5 years and an extra 50% tax relief for additional two years.
- Manufacturing industry is allowed an FDI influx of 100% via automatic channels excluding few industries.
- Services to establish off-shore banking divisions in SEZs Service Tax and Central Sales Tax exemption External commercial lending of up to US\$500 million is allowed for SEZ divisions In a year sans any maturity limitations via certified banking networks.
- No import authorization obligations.
- Services to sustain foreign exchange proof of payments of up to 100% in Exchange Earners' Foreign Currency Account.
- SEZ franchisees are allowed 100% FDI in offering customary telephone facilities in the areas.
- No limitation of foreign endowments for small scale industry reticent products.
- Tax relief from sectoral authorization obligations for goods reticent for SSI industry
- Tax relief from custom tariff on import of merchandize, raw products, spare parts etc.

- Tax relief from Central Excise tariff on acquirement of merchandize, raw products, spare parts etc. from the local market.
- No regular assessments by Customs for export and import freight.
- Capacity to comprehend and repatriate export advances within a year.
- Revenues permitted to be repatriated sans any dividend assessment needs
- Authorization for Employment prospects on behalf of local exporters for direct export.
- Authorization for off-shoring of local and global players. This service is accessible to jewelry sector also.

1.8.7. The objectives of SEZ

The prime objective behind an SEZ is to enhance foreign investment, increase exports, create jobs and promote regional development. To put in the government's own words, the Central Government, while notifying any area as a Special Economic Zone or an additional area to be included in the Special Economic Zone and discharging its functions under this Act, United Nations publication of 1985 listed the most common objectives underlying the establishment of zones. Following are the main objectives of the SEZs are:

Objectives:

- a) To generate the additional economic activity
- b) To promote the exports of goods and services;
- c) To promote the investment from domestic and foreign sources;
- d) To generate employment opportunities;
- e) To development infrastructure facilities; and
- f) To maintain sovereignty and integrity of India, the security of the State and friendly relations with foreign States.
- g) To introduce new technology.

In a broader perspective SEZ would play important dynamic function, and very different, dynamic crucial initiating role in the development of national industrial capacity by-

- Offering a platform for internationally competitive productive units;

- Creating an environment conducive to concentrated development of technology and skill in domestic sector with foreign participation;
- Initiating a shift in the orientation of the domestic sector towards export activities; and
- Providing as example for the government to adopt a administrative efficiency that encourages domestic and foreign investment.
- In addition, the zones allow countries to focus resources in particular sectors or areas, to soften the economic shocks of opening n economy and adjusting to more competitive and global world. In some cases they even provide islands of stability and relative transparency even in the most extreme conditions in today’s world of uncertainties.

The modern zones focus on providing an internationally competitive business environment with improved infrastructure, sophisticated communication, reliable power, dependable transport, well educated workers and efficient customs operation.

1.9. Objective of the Study

Following are the broad objectives of the present study are as follows:

- (1) To study the Special Economic Zones (SEZs) and its impact on Socio-economic Development of Rural peoples in Konkan and Marathwada region.
- (2) To know the policy of Govt. behind the Special Economic Zones (SEZs) and its effective implementation.
- (3) To analyses the Performance of Special Economic Zones (SEZ) in general and Konkan and Marathwada region in particular.
- (4) To study the SEZs and Its impact on rural development. i.e. employment, entrepreneurship, Social, Economic, and overall industrial development.
- (5) To know the Problems and prospects of Special economic zones (SEZs) and its impact on Konkan and Marathwada region Industrial area.

1.10. Hypothesis

1. Special Economic Zones (SEZs) has been especially beneficial to the Konkan region as compare to Marathwada region.
2. Special Economic Zone (SEZs) is accepted by the rural peoples for the overall development in both the regions.
3. Due to lack of proper and healthy Special Economic Zone (SEZs) Policy. Government of India is unable to get success in both the regions.

1.11. Scope and Limitations of the study

This study is limited to Konkan and Marathwada region. The overall 13 Districts are covered under Special Economic Zones on which its impact would be assessed on socio-economic development of rural people in Maharashtra. The Konkan region of Maharashtra accounts for the largest number of SEZ units: Konkan includes 69, the Western Maharashtra 50, Marathwada 15 and Vidarbha 10. Overall unites shall be studied and analyzed keeping view the acquisition; proposed total area wise investment and employment generation capabilities in all Maharashtra state. The study is primarily undertakes to assess the impact of SEZs between the year 2006 to 2013 on rural people viz. land owners, farmers, small and micro industrialists and unemployed youth residing in Konkan and Marathwada region of Maharashtra state.

1.12. Research Methodology

Collection of Data: To complete this study primary as well as secondary source of information is used.

Primary Data:

Primary data is collected from selected 200 respondents who are directly or indirectly affected due to implementation of SEZ policy by Central and State Government. For the purpose a scheduled questionnaire was framed highlighting issues, plights and privileges in compliance with SEZs Act. Which

bears direct impact on people living in industrial area as well as land owners, in particular in the districts covered in Konkan and Marathwada region. With the help of two different questionnaires distributed among entrepreneurs, workers, land owners and other factors the primary data was collected by interviewing the respondents.

Secondary Data

The Secondary data is gathered from books, journals, magazines, different published thesis, Govt. Committee reports, Govt. annual reports and related web sites.

1.13. Selection of Samples

Present study highlighted effects of SEZ on Konkan and Marathwada Region. In Konkan and Marathwada region, there are total 13 districts for administrative purpose. Konkan Region includes Mumbai, Thane, Ratnagiri, Raigad and Sindhudurg districts and Marathwada region includes seven districts viz. Latur, Nanded, Parbhani, Osmanabad, Beed, Jalna, and Aurangabad. Adopting Simple Random Sampling method in all 200 respondents from selected 07 districts were considered as samples where SEZ projects are in full swing. Keeping in view the relative importance of districts, in terms of socio-economic activities the researcher selected 30 respondents from Raigad, 30 Thane, 30 Mumbai and 10 Ratnagiri and likes wise 50 respondents from Aurangabad, 25 from Latur and 25 Nanded district in Konkan and Marathwada region, respectively. Data is collected by using scheduled questionnaire and by directly interacting with, especially, farmer family, who have been issued orders by the Govt. for land acquisition under Special Economic Zone (SEZ). The observed data has been discussed, analyzed, and major inferences have been drawn thereof.

Selection of Samples

Table No:-1.3
Approval and started SEZs in Selected Regions

Sr. No	Status SEZs	SEZs in Konkan Region	SEZs in Marathwada region
1	Employment (lack)	43.58	1.53
2	Notified	25	7
3	Formal Approval	50	9
4	In-Principal Approval	22	5
5	Total	67	21

1.14. Tools and Techniques to be used

The data, so collected, is scrutinized, tabulated, and analyzed compiled finally used for the study purpose. For analysis and tabulation process simple tools and techniques such as Percentile, Average, and co-relation is used.

1.15. Presentation of the Study:

Chapter-I: Introduction:

Chapter first has dealt with the overall conceptual development of Special Economic Zones (SEZs) in India on the backdrop of International trade and business growth. The chapter in particular has assessed the peripheral phenomena at the level of Central and State government that implies deceives changes in the socio-economic life of general public. It has attempted to trace SEZ policy implementations and its impact on Indian polity and industrial factors. The chapter has elaborated the statement of the problem, rational behind the study, objectives of the study, research methodology, and future scope of further research and overall relevance of the study.

Chapter 2 : Review of Literature:

Chapter second has dealt with the review of literature on the subject including studies related to SEZs projects in the country. An attempt has been made to co-relate the developments undergoing in India to the international trade organization.

For this around 60 articles and 70 books have been thoroughly read and referred to make an action plan and plot/design of the present study.

Chapter 3 : Special Economic Zones (SEZs) and Government Policy

Chapter third has thoroughly explored and evaluated the Policies of the state and central Government regarding the SEZ and its implementation. It has dealt with SEZs Policies, Rules Regulation, and Guidelines for development of SEZs units, Special assistance and overall implementation of the policy.

Chapter 4 : Special Economic Zones (SEZs) and Rural Development

Chapter fourth has dealt with very important aspect of Special Economic Zones (SEZs) and Rural Development. The government of India introduced a special economic Zones (SEZ) Policy. The aim of the Policy is to promote export oriented industrial and economic development for the proponents of rapid development of India. SEZs are engines of high economic growth. India has largest sector of Agriculture & Allied economy providing employment to nearby 60 per cent of the total population. Chapter fourth has thoroughly explored the SEZs status and prospectus in India and Its impact on Rural Development in respect of employment, entrepreneurship, socio-economic lives and overall industrial and infrastructure development with the help of Special Economic Zones.

Chapter 5 : Special Economic Zones and Socio-Economic Development in Selected Regions (Konkan and Marathwada Regions)

Chapter fifth has explored the Socio-Economic development caused by SEZs in Marathwada and Konkan regions. The socio-economic benefits and harmonious construction of rural development and policies designed to remove poverty, unemployment and backwardness of the rural people are some of the positive impact of SEZs. SEZs are aimed to foster economic growth by development of infrastructure and foreign direct investment (FDI). This study has evaluated the problems occurred during the development of SEZs in respect of land acquisition process, compensation process and so on. It has also suggested suitable antidotes and panaceas to improve the performance of SEZs in India for the overall welfare of rural people in India un to this last. The fifth chapters has

analyzed Special Economic Zones (SEZs) and socio-economic development in Konkan and Marathwada for overall social, cultural, political, economic, and regional development, infrastructure development, technological development, overall development of stakeholders in project affected areas in Konkan and Marathwada regions in the state of Maharashtra through implementation of SEZs. This chapter has examined whether the main objectives of the Socio-economic development of selected regions are fulfilled: to prepare demographic and growth profiles of all the villages under the focused areas; to assess socio-economic characteristics of the people; to assess the nature of existing resources and means of livelihood; to examine possible impact of the project on local population due to their displacement, loss of land, and other means of livelihood etc.; and an last but not the least, to evolve preliminary suggestion and guidelines for an effective R&R of the 'project affected persons (PASs).

The present chapter has focused on the SEZs and Socio-Economic development in selected regions of Maharashtra within the framework of rural development and addressed social justice to the marginalized sections of the society. This study has recorded an account of the people's struggle for their livelihood rights especially land, water, and forest and employment rights. It has also described the opposition of the affected people to the concept of Special Economic Zones, which is, from the point of view of general public anti-poor, anti-labor, anti-farmers, and anti-people in general, and various issues. This chapter also examined the situation which has compelled the common people to challenge the establishment of SEZs in Maharashtra and across the country.

Chapter 6 : Data Collection and Analysis:

Chapter Six has presented Data required and its critical Analysis precisely for the propose of "Critical Analysis of Special Economic Zones (SEZs) and Rural Development in Maharashtra State" With Special Reference to Konkan and Marathwada Region". It has dealt with available dada for SEZs and Rural development in Maharashtra state by the help of respondents of selected samples in Konkan and Marathwada regions by prepared questionnaire, Interview schedules for affected farmers and land owners who loss their land and

entrepreneurs views , Social leaders' opinions, and general opinions of the affected people. Secondary sources of SEZs data and government published report and information also used for the said study. These facts and figures are analysed and interpreted in this chapter for calculating or testing hypothesis.

The analysis and interpretation is based on field survey undertaken in SEZs units in the study area. For the purpose, over 200 respondents, 100 from each of the regions, including male and female workers, farmers, landowners, were selected who are directly and indirectly affected in SEZ units operational in the regions. It has been observed that majority of the farmers and general public in Navi Mumbai, Raigad, Ratnagiri of **Konkan region and Nanded, Latur, and Aurangabad** in Marathwada region staged protest against SEZs projects in the respective regions. This chapter has brought forth factual reasons behind discontent among public who have been alleging irregularities in implementation of Labor Laws, Industrial Acts to promote SEZ policy. Thus, an honest attempt has been made to highlight socio-economic aspects such as displacement issues, rehabilitation and resettlement of project affected people, rural development, industrial and infrastructural development, and urbanization in Konkan and Marathwada regions, in particular, as proposed to be addressed through SEZ policy.

Chapter 7 : Conclusions and Recommendations:

This concluding chapter highlights some major conclusions, findings, and important ant suggestions, and recommendations of special economic Zones (SEZs) and rural development in Maharashtra state with special reference to Konkan and Marathwada regions being faced by the SEZ policy. It argues that SEZs need to be viewed as testing laboratory of the problems that any socio-economic, and rural development, and employment generation, land acquisition and project affected peoples/farmers and in general's opinion of peoples and respondents of project affected areas in selected regions and industrialization programme might face in the country. It has also highlighted the policy recommendations for better performance of SEZs and their future prospects in India

Concluding Remarks

This chapter has discussed all the basic contexts and history of Special Economic Zones (SEZs) with required and suitable research methodology which is useful for the study purpose for the “Critical Analysis of Special Economic Zones (SEZs) and Rural development in Maharashtra state –with special reference to Konkan and Marathwada regions.” It has also stated the overall development of SEZs in India in respect of silent features of SEZs, Tax benefits, procedure of setting up SEZs Units, Land requirement for the SEZs project, SEZs policy, advantages and disadvantages of SEZs, SEZs projects and the Rural development in Indian particularly affected areas in Konkan and Marathwada regions in Maharashtra state from the perspectives of SEZs policy. This chapter has focused on study objectives, hypotheses, research methodology and future scope and limitations of the study to find out the social economical and rural development and varied aspects of SEZs.

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6. Noida Special Economic Zone-www.nsez.gov.in
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9. Visakhapatnam Special Economic Zone-www.vsez.gov.in
10. MEPZ Special Economic Zone-www.mepz.gov.in
11. Falta Special Economic Zone-www.fsez.nic.in
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CHAPTER - II

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Introduction

An attempt has been made to identify the gap that exists in the research area. In order to have an in-depth review of literature, the studies have been classified into the following two points:

1. Studies relating to Indian experience of SEZs.
2. Studies relating to Global experience of SEZs.

The present study aims to analyze the SEZ scheme in India, performance of SEZs in India and working environment of SEZs in India. In this context, the review of studies already done would be quite useful to draw some important conclusions that can serve as a guide mark for the present study.

1. Studies Relating to Indian Experience of SEZs

K.R. Gupta (2001) The Special Economic Zones are considered a highly visible component of *former Chinese Premier Deng Xiaoping's* economic modernization programme. The original four SEZs- Shenzhen, Zhuhai, Shantou and Xiamen- were established in 1979 and have been source of much discussion and inquiry ever since. Encouraged by the grand success of china's particularly Shenzhen and Shantou, both of which have become hung urban agglomerations, the Indian Government has envisaged the SEZs as the new mantra for export-oriented economic activity.¹

Subrahmanian and Mohanan (1978) analyzed the central idea behind the setting up of EPZs in underdeveloped countries to motivate Multinational Corporations (MNCs). In their paper the authors studied the Santa Cruz Electronics Export Processing Zone (SEEPZ) and brought out that operations of the MNCs have not achieved the expected results. First, the overall production and export, as well as the proportion of value added, by units in the SEEPZ have been far below the targets. Second, the proportion of the value added has varied inversely with the degree of foreign control, with Indian

owned units using Indian technology performing far better than units controlled by the MNCs.¹

Bhatta (2003) highlighted the importance of SEZs, provided an overview of the rules, regulations and incentives, the possible implications for the environment of the region, and the importance of ensuring transparency in conducting an environmental impact analysis. The study emphasized that maintenance of ecological balance along with industrial development is required.²

Aggarwal (2004) analysed the export performance of Indian EPZs since their inception. The growth rates of aggregate exports, foreign exchange earnings and employment showed a steep jump when new EPZs were created in the early eighties. The share of EPZ export to total export showed a very gradual rising trend during the last twenty years. This is due to the rising trend in electronics exports. However, lack of single window clearance facilities, the attitude of the officials, centralized governance, stringent labour laws and poor physical and financial infrastructure resulted in relatively poor investment climate in the zones.

Aggarwal (2005), in his research paper revealed that the SEZ scheme introduced by the Government of India in April 2000 has its genesis in the EPZ scheme which was introduced way back in 1965 when the first zone was set up in Kandla. The SEZ Act is a major step in the direction of providing a long-term comprehensive policy framework and fiscal incentives are very important in determining the attractiveness of the zones. The Act has reinforced the authority of the central government. She further stated that the problem of co-ordination between the centre, states and zones will remain and may perhaps aggravate with the creation of different authorities looking after approval and management.³

The study conducted by Confederation of Indian Industry, Northern Region (2006) analyzed the export performance of SEZs in India. Export from SEZs grew by 16.4 per cent during the period 2000-01 to 2004-05. In the same period, total export in India grew by 12.1 per cent. Electronics and gems &

jewellery contributed more than 75 per cent of the exports from SEZs during the year 2002.⁴

Curtis et al. (2006) compared China's experience using SEZs to promote regional export-oriented economic growth with the experience of Post-Soviet Russia, Mexico and the Dominican Republic, and found that SEZs will only succeed in countries with a strong central government, geographic ties and cultural ties to developed markets and competitively low-wage labour.⁵

Jain (2006) analyzed the SEZ scheme in India. The author examined the need of SEZs, minimum area requirement for various types of SEZs in India, incentives and facilities provided to SEZ units and developers, provisions relating to establishment of units in SEZs in India. The author further suggested that the need for development of SEZs can be attributed to various factors, viz. foreign investment, technological and know-how advancement, development of backward regions, employment generation etc.⁶

The study by Nishith Desai Associates (2006) concluded that the establishment of the SEZs has, undoubtedly, helped to increase the volume of international trade. Further, a large amount of foreign investment has found its way not only into the export trade, but also into infrastructure construction and commerce. Foreign companies have been encouraged to establish their presence in the territories and the export industry has grown. Advanced foreign technology has been brought in with the inflow of foreign investment. All these factors have contributed to the growth of the Indian economy. The enactment of the SEZ Act and its implementation would enable the GOI to fulfil its agenda of economic reforms as the multiplier effect on the economic activities triggered by SEZ materializes.⁷

Viswanadhan (2006) analyzed the export performance of SEZs in India. The author examined that total export from the existing EPZs notified as SEZs after the SEZ Act, for the year 2004-05 were Rs. 18300 crore. Nearly 45 per cent of the total exports came from just one such zone, SEEPZ, the most successful zone among the early zones.⁸

Aggarwal (2007) examined the impact of SEZs on employment, poverty and human development. The empirical findings of the study are based on the primary as well as secondary data sources. The primary data was generated through extensive interviews of entrepreneurs and workers across the three largest SEZs, namely, SEEPZ, Madras and Noida. The analysis reveals that employment generation has been the most important channel through which SEZs affected human development in India. Employment generated by zones is remunerative. The role of SEZs in human capital formation and technology upgradation is found to be rather limited. The study argues that the potential of zones could not be exploited fully in India. The study highlighted that the new SEZ policy has given a major thrust to SEZs. However, the creation of SEZs alone does not ensure the realization of their potential. The government will need to play a more proactive role to get benefits from SEZs.⁹

Bloodgood (2007) analyzed the role of government in attracting foreign investment. The author examined that like many other countries, Government of India has offered certain incentives to attract foreign investment, many of which are concentrated in Special Economic Zones. Due to this, net foreign direct investment (FDI) flows into India reached at \$ 15.7 billion in 2006-07.¹⁰

Datt (2007), in his article titled, "Development, Displacement and Rehabilitation" stated that the Central government should formulate a socially balanced policy on SEZs. It is no use blindly following China which has only five such Special Economic Zones, but in India there is a plan to have 285 SEZs. Unlike China, in a democratic country like India, it is not possible to ruthlessly muzzle the voice of the displaced people in favour of generating profits for the industrial and business classes, and developers.¹¹

Dogra (2007), in his article, criticized the SEZ policy in India. He stated that the SEZ legislation is an arbitrary act of economic violence against the people of India which can play havoc with livelihood, food security, environment, justice to workers, fiscal health and balanced development of the economy. The sooner it is scrapped, the better will it be for the country, its people, its peace, its justice and its democracy.¹²

Gopalakrishnan (2007a) attempted to examine SEZs as a part of larger pattern of change in the Indian policy and economy. SEZ should not be seen and evaluated on the basis of their stated policy goods alone; these goals have little relationship to the actual structure of SEZ policy. Rather, the approach will be to examine some of the more unusual features of the SEZ policy, using them as indicators to explore the policy from other angles. The conclusion that emerges is that SEZs can be seen as a response to constraints that have arisen on capital in the recent Indian context, aimed at allowing super-profits and rapid accumulation to continue. However, the consequences are likely to be complex and very dangerous.¹³

Grasset and Landy (2007) studied and compared the evolution of the Indian economic policy vis-a-vis the adoption of the SEZ policy, and found that the SEZs as a peculiar device wherein a segregated territory within a country is meant to be a part of the globalization process. Such a measure represents on a part, two evolving tendencies in the industrial and export scenario of post-independence India. First, the individual states more as a critical factor in spending up the industrialization process and second, multinational corporations are acquiring a greater role to play in India's overall economy. For that matter, the success of SEZs is contingent upon the favourable policies and investment climate of individual states and their impact would be more regional than national.¹⁴

Krishan (2007) examined the extent and concentration of SEZs in India. He found that as on 3 October, 2007 there were 173 notified SEZs in India. 19 among them were operational prior to SEZ Act, 2005. Among the various states, Andhra Pradesh takes the lead with 47 SEZs followed by Tamil Nadu, Maharashtra, Karnataka, Haryana, Uttar Pradesh and Punjab. He also found that there is a tendency of clustering the SEZs in a particular district, adjoining Hyderabad in Andhra Pradesh accommodates 24 SEZs, Bangalore in Karnataka 13 SEZs, Kancheepuram in Tamil Nadu 11 SEZs and Pune in Maharashtra 10 SEZs; and other concentration of SEZs is observed in Gurgaon district in

Haryana and Gautam Buddha Nagar district of Uttar Pradesh. At least 54 districts have only one SEZ each.¹⁵

According to India's Foreign Trade Policy, the SEZ units may export goods and services including agro-products, partly processed goods, sub-assemblies and components except prohibited item of export in ITC (HS). The units may also export by-products, rejects, waste scrap arising out of the production process. Export of Special Economic Chemicals, Organic material, Equipment and Technologies (SCOMET) shall also be undertaken, through subject to fulfillment of the conditions indicated in the ITC (HS) classification of Export and Import items. Further, SEZ units, other than trading and service units may also export to the Russian Federation in Indian Rupees against repayment of State Credit/Escrow Rupee Account of the buyer, subject to RBI clearance, if any. The hung resources of the country shall provide abundant raw material to the SEZs to manufacture various items for export.⁵

Kumar (2007) analyzed some of the key features relevant to the creation of SEZs. In the article, it is argued that the SEZ policy is a part of the policy of 'growth at any cost' with the cost falling on the already marginalized sections in the rural area. The employment generation in SEZs will not be able to compensate for the loss of employment in the activities that SEZ will displace. The output and investment will be much less than claimed in these SEZs.¹⁶

Majumdar (2007) examined various aspects of SEZs and concluded that zones can play a long-term dynamic role in the host country's development if they are set up appropriately, managed well and integrated with the overall national economy. The author argued that the problems of displacement of farmers and labourers and potential tax revenue losses may be offset through gains accrued in terms of higher export earnings, flow of investments, employment creation and technology upgradation. The study suggests that the policy should be designed to encourage large-sized SEZs, so that they can exploit scale-related advantages.¹⁷

Mitra (2007a), in his paper titled "Special Economic Zones in India White Elephants or Race Horses" looked at the policy of SEZs in India and

their suitability for fulfilling the goals of exports promotion, employment generation and maintenance of the tempo of economic growth. On the basis of economic theory and history he concluded that absorption of agriculture labour is necessary for sustained economic development of a developing country. SEZs constitute a means for such sustained development in India. However, the SEZ policy in India has suffered from permission being granted for far too many SEZs which are either sub-optimally sized or are appendages to mega cities.¹⁸

Mitra (2007b) examined the rationale behind SEZs and pitfalls in the implementation of the SEZ strategy with special reference to India. The study highlighted that SEZs can generate several benefits. The clustering of industries, resulting from the benefits provided to SEZs leads to better utilization of infrastructure and therefore lower infrastructure costs per unit of output. However, there are several deficiencies in the implementations of SEZ policy in India. The inability of the state to provide a country-wide network of infrastructure facilities implies that SEZs are still being located close to the major cities and are thereby adding to the congestion of these cities and generating diseconomies of agglomeration. The study suggested that the selection of SEZs should not only take into account the economic impact generated from within the SEZs through higher production or employment but also the impact of SEZ on other areas through its effect on the resource base and environment. It is also recommended that the government should not act as an intermediary in acquisition of land.¹⁹

Pillai (2007) in his study on SEZs highlighted that in India, the SEZs that were set up prior to the SEZ Act, are providing employment to about 1.85 lakh persons of which about 40 per cent are women. Export from the existing SEZs increased from Rs. 13854 crore in 2003-04 to Rs. 34789 crore in 2006-07, an increase of about 151 per cent in the last three years and expected investment of Rs. 100000 crore including foreign direct investment of US\$ 5-6 billion by the end of December, 2007. He concluded that SEZ scheme will act as a catalyst in the development process of the country.²⁰

Ramachandran and Biswas (2007), in their study focused on the possible locations of SEZs, and developed a set of criteria and methodology for identifying such locations. The most critical consideration in their case pertains to proximity to the national highways, broad gauge railing lines and large cities. Only the wasteland is related for the establishment of SEZs instead of productive agricultural land. Applying such criteria, they found 64 districts in 16 states as most suitable for setting up of SEZs. The authors warn that the politicians may be in a hurry to implant such zones anywhere but it does require care and patience for not only finding desirable location but also working for their impact on mankind.²¹

Roychowdhury (2007) in his study analysed the pros and cons of the SEZ model for resettlement and rehabilitation. He stated that land for land can be an effective and justified mode of resettlement, provided comprehension for developing the new land is made available. For that, a land bank should be set up after taking the stock of present barren and infertile land in the states and the land available under the sick units and closed factories. In no circumstances, a very fertile land should be acquired as that will dampen the growth and productivity of agriculture which is dangerous for economy as that will endanger food security.²²

Sanyal et al. (2007), in their research study criticized the SEZ policy in India and stated that the claim of creating lakhs of jobs in SEZs is a complete hoax. The corporate who will establish production units in SEZs, will also seek jobless growth and only a small number of jobs for a highly skilled workforce can be expected in sectors like IT. Acquisition of cultivable land will not only make millions of farmers and agricultural labourers lose their livelihood but also will definitely have adverse effect on production of agriculture and environmental resources such as water and forest resources. In the SEZs, there will be exploitation of labourers as labour law does not applicable within these zones and there will also be a possibility of sex harassment of women labourers.²³

Social activists like Medha Patkar have stressed the need to abolish the Land Acquisition Act, 1894 as it is an outdated law and makes development and people enemies. She says that the Law, made during the British rule, is still being used in a shameless manner for acquiring not only properties but also the livelihoods of people in exchange for meager amounts of cash. Providing housing plots and a few civic amenities is preached as resettlement. The fact that this does not address serious economic deprivations and on many occasions does not even ¹⁴

Sen and Dasgupta (2007), in their paper, which is based on a field study found a state of severe insecurity in terms of job contracts, income and other labour status for those employed in the highly subsidized and growth-oriented enclaves of SEZs. They further stated that India's drive towards industrialization by setting up a large number of SEZs in different parts of the country needs to rethink. Unconditional benefits to capital as are offered to these privileged zones only with the sections to expropriate labours on legal huge landscapes by displacing the agrarian community open up the need to revisit India's current industrialization policy.²⁴

Mukund Ghare, Director of an organization for sustainable land and water management, says: When there is a crying need to distribute the scarce water equitably between urban and rural sectors and between the rich and the poor, there is an apprehension as to how much water the SEZ will use? Who will own the water? How it will be used, when there is no environmental law applicable to the SEZ? This is nothing but an attempt to privities water. In the Pen taluka of Raighad district, the farmers have been fighting for water from the Hetawane dam. There are 52 villages in the command area of the Hetawane project, proposed in 1980 to irrigate about 5,750 hectares of land provide drinking water to Pen and Navi Mumbai. Now a hung area of the land is being given to Reliance Industries in violation of the law that says that once the land falls in the command area of an irrigation project, it cannot be used for any other purpose. The other problem is that if 5000 Ares of land is given to Reliance Industries to set up the proposed SEZ at Pen, Which covers 86 per

cent of the total command area of the project, who will supply drinking water to Navi Mumbai and the remaining part of Pen? The project is a progress since 1983 and over Rs. 220 crore have already been spent on it. All this effort and money will go waste if the command area is acquired for the proposed SEZ.

The farmers from the Raighad district have plans to develop the area for growing sugar beet, a five –month crop, if they get irrigation. If the Government sets up a processing factory, sugar can be produced. They can also grow *basmati* rice if sufficient water is made available from the project. The farmers have suggested that setting up a special agricultural zone in the area shall be more useful than the SEZ. ²¹

Sengupta et al. (2007), concluded in this study, that the SEZs policy has run into a public debate on the logic of special concessions being granted to already well-entrenched and well-performing capital and the manner in which the required land is being acquired with state intervention. It has also brought into sharp public focus the resistance of local residents facing the prospect of displacement and their plight in the absence of viable alternative livelihood system. Although the need for accelerating infrastructure development for industrialization and taking advantage of agglomeration economies within these zones is acceptable but the way in which they are being sought to be created and their overall implications for industrial growth and economic development need to be thoroughly examined. It is, therefore, necessary to analyse SEZ Policy and orient it to a justifiable economic programme. The National Commission for Enterprises in the Unorganised Sector (NCEUS) suggests “Growth Pole” as an alternative form of SEZs utilizing their potential benefits but avoiding the pitfalls into which unrestricted expansion of SEZs may fall in our country. Instead of creating ‘special enclaves’ for the big and the strong on freshly acquired land, the authors feel that a hard look is warranted towards areas that have spawned clusters of single products or multi-products and services. ²⁵

A study conducted by Seth Associates (2007) explored the Indian policy framework for SEZs. The study also examined the various incentives and

facilities available to SEZs, and recent legal and regulatory development pertaining to SEZ in India. The study highlighted that in India during 2004-05, as many as 948 units were in operation in the SEZs, providing direct employment to about 1.10 lakh persons from which 40 per cent of them were women. The exports from the SEZs during 2004-05 have registered a growth of 32 per cent in rupee terms over the previous year.²⁶

Aggarwal (2008a), in his research study emphasised the necessity of Special Economic Zone policies in the present World Trade Organization regime for the development of India's export and economic activities. The study also focused on the philosophy behind the land compensation, expectations of farmers from compensation package and the critical role of a Chartered Accountant in this whole exercise of fair land compensation valuation and the investment by the farmers for future growth.²⁷

Aggarwal (2008b) made a systematic analysis of the contribution that SEZs have made to technological capabilities and industrial diversification at the sectoral level in India. He first explored the importance and nature of technology transfer and technology creation efforts in SEZs. The analysis is based on a fully structured questionnaire based survey of technology management in 75 firms across three SEZs namely, Santacruz SEZ, Madras SEZ and Noida SEZ. The author also examined success stories of technology trends/creation in introducing new products and promoting new industries in the country. This part of the analysis is based on extensive interviews with zones entrepreneurs in ten operational zones. Of these, seven are the central government zones, while three other are new upcoming zones. This analysis reveals that SEZs have helped the country in exporting new product and in building up the country's image in certain products in international market. Though they could not induce technology-based dynamism in the local or national economy due to relatively small scales of operations compared with the domestic tariff area, they did play an important role in seeding new industries and transforming some of the existing industries and it is expected to

result in significant inflows of technology and knowledge in SEZs and subsequently, in the rest of the economy through spillover effects.²⁸

According to Vivek Mehra, state Executive Director of Price Waterhouse Coopers (PWC) who advises a lot of SEZ developers, the present crisis is fallout of bad land acquisition policy and politics. The States Governments need to adopt “pragmatic land acquisition polices that do not lead to deprivation among the displaced.”¹⁷

Ahmed (2008) in his article stated that SEZ legislation is an arbitrary act against the people of India which can play havoc with their livelihood, food security and environmental safety, justice to workers, fiscal health and a balanced development of the economy. There is an urgent need the government seriously revisit and rethink these two anti–people and undemocratic legislations and take concrete steps to remedy the distortions inherent in them, including repealing them to enact few more reasonable legislations in the interests of justice, social harmony equitable development and respect for human and natural rights of the citizens over their land and livelihoods.²⁹

Avhad and Chintamani (2008) concluded that when IMF and the World Bank picked up the idea of SEZs, the world scenario changed. In 1990 there were 847 SEZs in the world. At present, there are about 4000 SEZs in 120 countries in the world. In India, SEZs can be set up in public sector, private sector or joint sector or even by state governments. The central government encouraged the state governments to pursue the policy of SEZ rigorously. The largest number of SEZs are sanctioned in the developed states like Maharashtra. Out of 75 SEZs in Maharashtra, 08 SEZs are in Marathwada, 07 in Vidharbha and remaining SEZs are in Pune-Raigad-Thane-Mumbai belt.³⁰

Bharati and Khedkar (2008) made a detailed analysis on the concept and meaning of SEZ, characteristics of SEZ Act 2005, tax exemptions and concessions available under the scheme of SEZ and progress and performance of SEZ. The study is based on the secondary data. The authors found that 404 valid formal approvals were received by Government of India. Out of this, number of notified SEZs (as on 9th Jan., 2008) were 193. The notified SEZ as

on 30th September, 2007, provided an investment and employment of Rs. 285279 crore and created over 2230277 additional job opportunities respectively. The exports in 2006-07 were Rs. 34787 crore. The study concludes that SEZ, no doubt, would act as a catalyst in bringing a progressive change in the economic growth and development of our country. The study suggested that the economic development should be a win-win process for all sections of the society. The government should consider the public opinion in respect of SEZs.³¹

According to the *Ministry of Finance*, will inflict a loss of Rs.90, 000 cr. on the exchequer-an unacceptably large amount for an investment of Rs.1,00,000 crore, SEZs will bleed the larger economy, feel some quarters. The International Monetary Fund's (IMF) Chief Economist R. Rajan has blatantly criticized the hung economic incentives offered to the Zones. He says that the concern is if you focus on tax incentives to set up these Special Economic Zones, the incentives diminish and you hurt the revenues of the government. Overall, it becomes yet another give-away which the Government cannot afford. However, The Commerce Minister Kamal Nath has set aside such criticism, saying that the benefits to the economy, one of the production activities of Special Economic Zones gather momentum, shall be many times the amount forgone through tax exemptions. As a counter-reaction to R. Rajan does attract on India's Special Economic Zones, the Commerce Minister remarked that the concept of revenues loss did not arise.⁹

Chatterjee (2008), analyzed the conceptual framework, incentives and facilities to SEZ developers, SEZ policy and economic aspects of SEZs in India. Exports from SEZs grew by 16.4 per cent during the period 2000-01 to 2004-05. During the same period, total exports from India grew by 12.1 per cent. Employment generation, both direct and indirect, has been the most important channel, through which SEZs have impacted on human development and poverty reduction in India. Even though their contribution to national employment has been rather limited, they have contributed significantly to employment generation at the regional level. Due to stagnation, their ability to

absorb surplus labour has been declining. It can only be reversed if fresh investment is attracted to SEZs. With the SEZ Act in place, there has been a surge in the establishment of new zones, which is likely to generate huge employment potential in the economy. Most of this will be a net addition to employment as investment relocation in export-oriented production is likely to be limited.³²

Govilkar (2008) analyzed SEZ Act, 2005 and SEZ Rules, 2006. The study found that policy of SEZ has been adopted and implemented with the objective that it will develop sufficient and high quality infrastructure by private sector, will attract considerable foreign investment, will increase employment opportunities, will boost the export, and thereby will expand economic activities in the country. The industrial islands could become engine of growth. India, to get better share in world trade, must undertake special efforts, when the global export opportunities are increasing. SEZ could be a prominent policy for the same.³³

Guha (2008) examined the evolution of the new development enclaves–SEZs– in India in the light of the space relation of capital. The process of establishing SEZs in India is essentially a classic unfolding of the process of “accumulation by dispossession” which is a part of recent strategy of global capital to overcome the chronic problem of over accumulation. The paper also throws light on the ongoing reorganizations of the space relation of capital in India. Kumar (2008), in his article, emphasized that SEZ area will develop substantially at the expense of non-SEZ area. This is likely to accentuate the already rising regional disparities. There is likely to be diversion of resources from non–SEZ area to the SEZs. SEZs will usher in enclave development. Migration to urban areas will rise and urban infrastructure will face enormous pressure. The excess land being allotted to SEZs will result in the creation of new landlords. If the overall gains from SEZs are so unclear and government is still going ahead with the scheme, then it can only be because it wants to give concessions to certain sections. He further suggested that for the sake of accountability, land should be acquired in phases as the project is set up. Thus,

it is necessary that the party interested in setting up an SEZ or any other project should give a time bound plan and if that is not adhered to, more land should not be acquired and what was acquired should be returned. A fine should be imposed on the party involved and distributed to those whose land has been acquired.³⁴

Mistry (2008), in his article observed that the SEZs seem to be a phenomenon which will become a bane in the Indian development experience. Further, the cost of SEZs in terms of human rights violation, lose a livelihood, slack rehabilitation and environment degradation will in the long run, prove to very high. Therefore, government should rethink its policy of SEZs and should implement it only on an experimental basis with caution in the backward areas where no development has taken place.³⁵

Sampat (2008) explored some stand in the political schema of SEZs in India with specific reference to one immediate fallout of serious concern and contestation the imminent displacement of thousands of people livelihoods in countrywide where these SEZs are stated to come up. A factsheet on SEZs on the Government of India website gives details of the number of approved and proposed SEZs, their land requirements as well as export and employment potential. However, there is no mention of the number of people to be displaced by these zones and it is not clear, how the government intends to attend the issues of displaced.³⁶

Shankar (2008) analyzed that the SEZ Act and Rules have evoked considerable interest and a large number of applications for approvals continue to receive almost on daily basis, especially from the private sector. The anticipated exports, investment and employment send positive signals. Another positive development is that the SEZ scheme is being overseen by an Empowered Group of Ministers. At the same time an effort should be made to see that the scheme parameters are not changed frequently since certainty and stability of Government policy is necessary for investment.³⁷

Sikidar and Hazarika (2008), in their study highlighted that the SEZ is being increasingly seen as an alternative way of economic growth through

exports and duty exemption. As a part of SEZ policy, the government offers several incentives to investors like tax holiday for up to 10 years, duty free imports and exports, world class infrastructure, strategic locations and market access. The article provides an overview of SEZs evolution and global growth besides focusing on several operational aspects of the SEZs, related constitutional requirements and relief and exemption from income tax. The authors suggested that there is an urgent need to pay attention to some key issues to ensure a transparent and effective SEZ management.³⁸

Raj and Roy (2008), in their article concluded that the SEZ Act, 2005 is anti-democratic and unconstitutional as it completely violates the right to life and livelihood of the people, who are being forcibly displaced for the implementation of these projects. The Act promotes large scale privatization and monopolization of resources into the hands of a few private developers at huge costs to the state exchequer as well as the economy and environment of this country. In their case study they found that the issue regarding Nandigram and Singur is a purely economic one. Politicians have merged this issue with the political framework which emerges as the crux of problem. Public participation is necessary for the welfare of the community. The economic aspect has been neglected which should be addressed by the state. Policies have to be streamlined to ensure that the pain and profits of growth are more equitably distributed.³⁹

Reddy and Srinivas (2008) explained that the promotion of SEZs is an attempt to deal with infrastructural deficiencies and procedural and bureaucratic complexities caused by monetary, fiscal, taxation and labour policies. The objective of setting up of SEZs is to gain structural growth with world-class infrastructure, which is helpful to the economic growth of India. This study presents an overview of the process and progress of SEZs in the country in general and in Andhra Pradesh in particular.⁴⁰

Gope and Ghosh (2009) analyzed the SEZ environment in India and the contribution of SEZs to economy. Prior to SEZ Act 2005, there were 19 SEZ projects in operation throughout the country. Under SEZ Act, 222 projects had

been notified. Out of 462 formally approved SEZs as on 15.05.2008 and the number of valid in principle approvals is 135. These had proposed to acquire 1855 sq. km. (for both FA+PA) area of land which is only 0.112 per cent of the total agricultural land. SEZs established prior to the Act coming into force, there were 1122 units providing direct employment to over 1.93 lakh persons, about 37 per cent of whom were women.⁴¹

Menon and Mitra (2009) provided an overview of the rationale of the SEZ policy. The study points out the benefits of an export-led growth strategy and argues that the SEZ policy is driven by the objective of increasing (a) export, (b) infrastructure, (c) investment, (d) employment, and (e) economic activity. But otherwise, the core objective would be to increase export-oriented economic activity. Investment and infrastructure would be prerequisites for this to happen, while employment would be a consequence of increased activity. It states that “with the country’s GDP growth being fuelled by the services sector, particularly IT and IT-enabled services, it was necessary to promote manufacturing activities” and recommended that the “location for the new SEZs should be selectively done so that they spread development and address existing regional imbalances”.⁴²

Mukhopadhyay (2009) examined the structure of fiscal concession, the compensation policy adopted and the credibility of the project figures, based on the variation across different projects of the similar type and finds them lacking. Based on data available from Ministry of Commerce, the study finds that most of the SEZs are in the IT/ITES sector and a large share of projected employment is also expected to come from this sector. Furthermore, the SEZs also appear to be concentrated in few relatively developed districts, near urban centers. This will mean that the additional economic activity engendered by the fiscal concessions for SEZs will be in the sector that is already doing well, as in the Information Technology Enabled Service (ITES). Further, regional imbalances will worsen as a result of the concentration of SEZs in a few locations.⁴³

Mukhopadhyay and Pradhan (2009) explored the location of SEZs. The study examines the district-wise location of SEZs and relates them to the characteristics of district as available in the census. It finds that most of the SEZs, especially the tiny (less than 100 hectares or 1 sq. km. in size) SEZs are concentrated in districts in top quartile of urbanization. These tiny SEZs and IT/ITES SEZs appear to be concentrated in the districts that are proximate to the six mega cities of Delhi, Kolkata, Mumbai, Hyderabad, Bangalore, and Chennai. The study then statistically examines the concentration of SEZs in the IT/ITES sector. It was identified that more than 70 per cent of all SEZs and 93.4 per cent of all notified IT/ITES SEZs are having less than one square kilometer size.⁴⁴

Prabu (2009) highlighted many issues related to SEZs such as land acquisition, the problem of rehabilitation, loss of tax revenue, incentives and facilities to the developers of the SEZs, etc. The researcher concluded that though theoretically, conceptually, economically, financially and operationally SEZs appear to be a blessing, but actually it is not true. Throughout the country the creation of SEZs has created a big fever among politicians, economists, farming community, tax people and social workers. Specifically, the states in which the SEZs have been approved are facing intense protests from the farming communities accusing the government of forcibly snatching fertile land from them at heavily discounted prices as against the prevailing in the commercial real estate industry.⁴⁵

Sharma (2009) in the report of Conference held at the Indian Institute of Advanced Study on SEZs raises doubts about their desirability on different counts: It is centered around three themes: (1) SEZs and economic development; (2) SEZs and distributed implications; and (3) SEZs and legal issues. The study found that SEZs can lead to some serious consequences. Struggles on the land issues are already surfacing in different parts of the country. The SEZ policy can lead to serious and adverse consequences including social conflict, civil strife and breakdown of democratic institutions. It is also likely to lead to increased inequalities: and there is possibility of

shrinking of economic space for the ordinary people by making their production more unremunerative.⁴⁶

Sivaramakrishnan (2009) focused on implication of SEZ policy for urban growth and the governance of the SEZs. It has been argued in the paper that the SEZ is conceptual not only as a production centre but it is also an urban centre. However, the existing policy is unclear about both urban growth implications and their management. The emerging model of governance promoted by different states and also encouraged by the center appears to be 'non-municipal'. The paper presents the views of various stakeholders such as government departments and individuals expressed in the hearings of the Parliament's Committee on SEZs. Nevertheless, the 'non-municipal' approach, enabling an SEZ to become a private 'fiefdom' rather than a part of the country subject to the Constitution and the laws of the land appears to be prevailing. The paper also critically examines how a constitutional loophole, namely, the Proviso to Article 243Q, is being exploited for this purpose.⁴⁷

Reddy (2009) made a detailed analysis on the need and evolution of SEZs in India and the performance of Indian SEZs. The study highlighted that the overwhelming response to the SEZ scheme is evident from the flow of investment, creation of additional employment, export performance and attracted FDI in the country. The study concluded that the SEZs are real growth engines for the economic development of the country.⁴⁸

Reddy et al. (2009) analyzed the nature and significance of SEZs in India, inter-state formal approvals of SEZs and land allocated to them. The study is based on the secondary data drawn from the Ministry of Industry and Commerce, Government of India. It is found that southern-region has not only dominated with the highest number of formally approved SEZs, but also in all the other categories of SEZs. The state-wise comparison reveals that Maharashtra and Andhra Pradesh have occupied first two positions in the total formally approved SEZs and also in IT/ITES, Pharma/Bio-tech and other categories of SEZs. On the other hand, a large portion of land was allocated to

multi-product SEZs and a meagre share of land was allocated to IT/ITES and Pharma/Biotech SEZs in the country.⁴⁹

Khan (2010) analyzed the SEZ is the need of today's economy to support India's target of becoming developed nation. The physical exports done in year 2007-08 were Rs. 66637.68 crore from these SEZs. The creation of SEZ provided employment to around 3.5 lakh persons. The manufacturing and research projects are set up in these SEZs. Many large MNCs as well as Indian MNCs set up state of the art plants in these SEZs. This all will continue to contribute India's GDP. The study suggested that though, SEZ policy adopted by India to support economy in a big way, the conversion of fertile land into industrial land may create food crisis in near future. The use of waste land available in India (around 552692 sq. km.) for SEZ development will ensure that the farmers are not displaced from their farmland, the development not concentrated near cities and the fertile land will continue to be used for agriculture use.⁵⁰

Reddy et al. (2010) highlighted on the employment generated by SEZs in southern India. The data has been drawn from the Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India. The study is confined to notified SEZs only. The study found that of the total current employment generated by notified SEZs in India (370700 persons), about 41 per cent employment has been generated by SEZs of southern-region. Among the states in the southern region Tamil Nadu stands first with about 20 per cent followed by Karnataka and Andhra Pradesh with about 10 per cent each in the total current employment in India as on 31st March 2008.

The Finance Minister has suggested that since there was no obligation on SEZs to export if they do not import any capital goods or raw materials, tax breaks should be Commerce Ministry has turned down this suggestion saying that it will send wrong signals. Thus, the whole policy of tax and tariff exemptions needs to be reviewed.²²

IMF Economist *Raghuram Rajan* argues that "in the long run, capital account opening is unlikely to help poor countries grow by providing

resources.... Foreign capital is no panacea for capital poor countries.”Even China, a much stronger economy than India has fiercely resisted CAC. ²³

Employment: According to the Commerce Ministry, the SEZs shall create employment for hundreds and thousands of people. However, serious doubts have been raised over this claim. Since the SEZ units shall work with latest machinery and technology, they may not actually generate much employment. They will hire only people with technological skills who have the ability to get employment anyway. Their numbers may not be as large as anticipated by the Ministry. Moreover the number of people-farmers and others-who are displaced due to setting up of the proposed projected may actually be more than the employment created by the SEZs. Since most of these displaced people are illiterate and unskilled, they may not find employment elsewhere easily. As such, there may not be any advantage of setting up SEZs so far as the issue of employment is concerned. ²⁴

According to CPM leader, “Land acquisition cannot be left to the mercy of developers”. ²⁶

Ramakrishna Nallathiga, in his book “The Role of Special Economic Zones in Regional and National Development”, says that India and China Comparison in term of Economic Parameters, International Experience of the SEZs and Chinese Experience of SEZs and Silent Features of the SEZ Development in Various Countries for Export as well as evaluation of SEZs in India his performance, some critical issues of SEZ Development, Labour Issues, factors Attracting Highly Educated High Skilled Population, Good Transportation Network and Logistical Hubs, Size of the SEZs, Institutional and Governance Reforms, Conclusion;- Incidentally, the benefit-cost ratio was negative unit 1986, ²⁷

Twisha Adhikary (2005). “Resettlement and Rehabilitation Strategy for Displacement Caused due to Mining,” National Seminar on Policies, Statues and Legislations in Mines, Postal. The following categorization has been taken from this paper. For further reference please refers to page 6 of this article,

Op.cit.2005 mention: - People who have not been physically dislocated as a result of acquisition fall into this category. The livelihood and impoverishment risks that they undergo as a result of acquisition qualify them for rehabilitation.

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Geeta Das in her Book, “Special Economic Zones(SEZs) in India “lesson from China, said that the spectacular economic progress of the two Asian economies, China and India, in recent years, resulted in a paradigm shift of global attention from West to the East. And despite endowment and potential, India’s slow growth in comparison to that of China baffles economists, researchers and informed observers.

Against this background, the book presents a lucid analytical framework combining theoretical perspective and management practice for identification of area central to China’s successful strategy, particularly Special Economic Zones(SEZs) as ‘engine of growth’. It is a logical synthesis of the trends of a number of factors that outline of the growth options drawing relevant lessons from China’s development experience to model SEZs as a drive for India’s advancement. The latest statistics relating to the investment and performance of SZE in India have been collected from the industry association and the Department of Commerce, Government of India. The book is the result of extensive research and emerging issues may provide some useful inputs to the policy makers’ investors, social activists and research scholars. ³¹

Manmohan Shingh (Dr), The then Prime Minister of India Spoke in the annual general meeting of the Federation of Indian Chambers of Commerce and Industry at New Delhi on February 15,2008, We begin the year with renewed confidence in the sustainability of growth process, saving rate, and 35 per cent India’s development to this stage is broadly analyzed with reference to the development strategy, process of development including success, failure along with the challenges for sustaining the growth momentum . ³⁴

Sarwade W. K, Professor Department of Commerce, and Mgt. Science, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad expressed his

views on Globalization & Foreign Direct Investment in Indian Context, (2007) at He tried to enumerate the experienced in last decade that is a changing situation in each filed of production, industry, trade, service and education. It is because of our new economic policy. In globalised scenario India is trying hard to stand on international map as a powerful and economically strong country as “Asian Tiger”. The Indian Government has planned started to implement globalization and liberalization of Indian economy since 1991.” The book “Globalization & Foreign Direct Investment in Indian” while appeared and appealed most relevant and appropriate in the present context at revolutionary changes in the Globalization and Foreign Direct Investment. His suggestions: FDI to India the following aspects can be suggested,

1. Study the economic performance or existing FDI identity their key problems most from subjective perceptions to researched facts.
2. Arrange tax categories with national priorities of FDI employment growth and revenue generation. So also make the process transparent.
3. From a new innovated body between GATT and business. So that expectation can be joint shouldering of responsibility for economic progress.
4. Need to make procedure as simple as simple as possible.
5. A greater degree of synergy with states.³⁵

Dr. Gauri Farah Naaz, Dept of Commerce, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar Marathwada University, Aurangabad, in her Article “Indian Economic: Future Growth and Prospects” noted that India has a clear picture of her aspiration to be achieved through the process of economic development, which is manifested in the constitution and plan documents growth of the economy is one of the most important condition to realize the other goals The success that we have achieved in the services and manufacturing sector required that we must extend similar reforms to agriculture too. Otherwise the sector is languishing with no or poor growth, is certain to derail the reforms and the attendant growth opportunities, certain issues regarding growth strategy need attention and improve the condition of common people.³⁶

According to K.R. Gupta, “Special Economic Zones Issues, Laws and Procedures, Special Economic Zones (SEZs) are specially delineated duty-free enclaves deemed to have foreign territories for the purposes of trade operations, duties and tariffs. A scheme for setting up the SEZs in the country was announced in the EXIM Policy in March, 2000 with the objectives of developing integrated world-class infrastructure for exports including carrying out manufacturing of goods and rendering of services. Components of Special Economic Zones (SEZs) include roads, airports, ports, transport system, generation and distribution of power, telecom, hospitals, hotels, educational institutions, leisure and entertainment units, residential / industrial / commercial complex, etc.

2. Studies Relating to Global Experience of SEZs

Wong and Chu (1984) examined the general concept of free zones which include customs bounded warehouses/factories, EPZs and SEZs to free ports or comprehensive free trade zones. Special emphasis is placed on discussing the objective and characteristics adopting a strategy of export led growth by way of establishing EPZ/SEZs in the Asian region. Major difference between EPZs in countries with market economies and SEZs in socialist country (China) are brought out. Performance of Asian EPZs/SEZs is evaluated in terms of achievements in attracting foreign country investment, earning foreign exchange, export growth, employment generation, transfer of technology, backward and forward domestic linkages and regional development. Common problems encountered by the Asian Zones include inadequate infrastructure provision, social problem due to high percentage of female workers and the exploitation of the indigenous labour force, inefficient government administrations and low standard of management. Despite great regional variations in the source of EPZs/SEZs, the continuing growth in the number of such zones indicates an increasing interest on the part of Asian governments to adopt the EPZ.⁵¹

Stoltenberg (1984) in his study examined the SEZ which have begun to bear fruit for China. Indeed, they represent the focus of a substantial share of

all foreign investment to date. While the source of the vast bulk of such investment has been Hong Kong and overseas Chinese, there are indications that the base is broadening. Although gaps remain in the framework of administrations and significant uncertainties continue to confront potential investors, the flexibility shown by the Chinese in responding to problems as they arise must be encouraging from the investors' point of view. Such a response is not surprising in view of the support the central leadership has voiced for continued SEZ development. The SEZs provide environments for testing structural reforms and learning about the law of value and market forces and have also provided employment opportunities. The degree to which the zones will serve to filter foreign capital, technology, and equipment to other regions, remains to be seen generators of economic growth.⁵²

Wang and Bradbury (1986) examined the role of SEZs along China's coast zone and their place in the progress of modernization in Chinese industry. A special case study is made of Shenzhen SEZ where the Chinese government has attempted to promote the inflow of foreign capital and technology, while at the same time maintaining control over direction and types of development taking place. The state has developed joint ventures and local firms as the platform into which new technology is injected and from which new industries in the interior of country will be spawned. Total investment in Shenzhen increased from \$ 120 million in 1979 to \$ 1130 million in 1983 due to government efforts. Shenzhen's manufacturing employment grew from 5000 persons in 1978 to 25000 persons in 1980.⁵³

Wong (1987) attempted to provide a review of the latest development of China's SEZs, assessing their achievements in terms of the attraction of foreign capital, export growth and foreign exchange earnings and technology transfer. Reforms and innovative measures initiated in the zones that have implications for other parts of China are also discussed. Problems encountered in the course of SEZ development are examined, nothing in particular the heavy capital expenditure on infrastructure provisions, the development of trade-based economy, the over-ambitions objectives which would be difficult to achieve in

a short period of time as well as other economic and social issues. It is observed that the development of the SEZs has been proceeding without careful and co-ordinated planning and that the designation of economic development zones in the open coastal cities stands to undercut the allures of the SEZs and has made the latter much less “special” than they used to be.⁵⁴

Warr (1989) examined that EPZs are economic enclaves within which manufacturing for export occurs under virtual free trade conditions. Many developing countries have established EPZs with the hope of reaping economic gains through employment, foreign exchange earnings and technology transfer. This article studies the benefits and costs of EPZs in Indonesia, the Republic of Korea, Malaysia and the Philippines; and reviews the relationship between the welfare effects of EPZs and the host country’s economic policies.⁵⁵

Jenkins et al. (1998) examined the median zones that have been in operation for five or more years; and found that these median zones were providing lot of employment. In Asian countries, they provided employment to 10500 persons and in Latin countries 3500 persons till 1998.⁵⁶

Kusago and Tzannatos (1998) estimated that SEZ units move upward in value chains. This is reflected in the educational attainment of workers in SEZs which has changed dramatically over time in countries such as Korea, Taiwan and Sri Lanka. SEZs cannot therefore, be dismissed as islands of low productive jobs.⁵⁷

Ge (1999b) sort out implications of Special Economic Zones in China’s economic transactions; and attempted to draw some policy lessons for economic liberalization in a more general context. Establishing the zones has been the first and most crucial step that China took to reform and open its economy since 1979. The zones establishment, performance and impact on China’s transition are examined in addition to related reform efforts and policy issues. It is argued that the zones may serve as a policy means in facilitating trade and financial liberalization, enhancing resource utilization and promoting economic growth and structural changes. During the period 1980-95, the

overall Chinese economy expanded at an annual average rate of 10 per cent, while Shenzhen SEZ has grown at an astonishing 35.5 per cent in real terms.⁵⁸

Madani (1999), in his research study, argued that successful human capital formation depends on the sophistication of the economic activities carried out in the zones.⁵⁹

Armas and Sadni-Jallab (2002), in their study, analysed that SEZ investment does not bring the same technology as investment in the rest of the economy. The low skill assembly type operations in the SEZs leave little scope for technology transfer.⁶⁰

Mondal (2003) estimated that in Bangladesh, the growth of employment in the SEZs is much faster than that in the total organized manufacturing sector. It was over sixteen times than that of the organized manufacturing sector during 1983-84 to 1987-88 and over four times higher during 1988-89 to 1999-2000.⁶¹

Ota (2003) analysed the changing role of SEZs in the context of China's economic development and some of the emerging problems that SEZs were confronted with at the new stage of development. An attempt is laid here on study of policy and performance of the SEZs in comparison with those of Asian EPZs which managed to shift their industrialization strategy from the import-substitution to the export-orientation at the critical stage of development. The SEZs were in a better position to elicit lessons from the experiences of Asian EPZs, despite various conditions and limitations prevailing in China's socialist market economy. The study also finds that since the implementation of economic reform policy in 1979, China's economic development is quite impressive with her average annual rate of economic growth of over 10 per cent between 1980 and 1995, increasing her GDP from 451.8 billion yuan to 5826 billion yuan. SEZs apparently triggered her economic growth.⁶²

Aggarwal (2005) examined that EPZs contribute 64 per cent of the total exports in Mauritius, while in Mexico, Maquiladora's contribution in total exports has been around 40 per cent.⁶³

Bangladesh and Sri Lanka started their EPZ programme in 1981 and 1978 respectively. By 2000, the share of EPZ exports in their total exports increased to over 20 per cent and 33 per cent respectively.⁶⁴

Aggarwal (2006), in his another study titled “The Performance of Export Processing Zones: A Comparative Analysis of India, Sri Lanka and Bangladesh” found that in Bangladesh, total SEZ employment grew from mere 624 persons in 1983 when the first zone was set up in Chittagong, to over 144000 by 2003-04.⁶⁵

The study conducted by World Bank (2008) examined 30 years of experience of Zones, reviewed development patterns and economic impact of zones world-wide. The experience shows that while zones have been effective in addressing economic growth and development objectives, they have not been uniformly successful. Success in East Asia and Latin America has been difficult to replicate, particularly in Africa and many zones have failed.⁶⁶

Murayama and Yokata (2009) examined the historical trajectories and outstanding labour and gender issues of EPZs/SEZ on the basis of the experiences of South Korea, Bangladesh and India. The findings suggest the necessity of enlarging our analytical scope with regard to EPZ/SEZ, which are inextricably connected with external employment structure. Further, the study calls for an immediate and comprehensive review of the labour and gender conditions in Indian SEZs where workers are in a disadvantageous position not only against capital but also in comparison with workers in South Korea and Bangladesh EPZs/SEZs.⁶⁷

Wang (2009), in his research paper examined the impact of SEZs on foreign direct investment and other economic outcomes by using a comprehensive and unique data set on Chinese municipalities from 1978 to 2007. The study found that SEZ policy increased per capita foreign direct investment by 58 per cent. It did not crowd out domestic investment and domestically owned capital stock and increased total factor productivity growth rate by 0.6 percentages point. The results suggest that creating SEZ not only

brings capital, but also more advanced technology; and provides important policy implications for many developing countries.⁶⁸

Concluding Remark

The review of literature brings out that most of the studies relating to Indian experience of SEZs analyzed the SEZ scheme in India, incentives and facilities provided to the developers of the SEZs. The sector-wise, state-wise and region-wise distribution of formally approved, approved in principle, and notified SEZs in India has been undertaken in many studies. On the other hand, some studies have taken up the issues such as land acquisition, problem of displacement and rehabilitation of farmers and agricultural labourers, effect of SEZ on agriculture sector, labour laws, concentration of SEZs, revenue losses to government, effects of SEZs on environment etc.

The studies relating to global experience of SEZs examined the performance of SEZs in terms of employment generation, export promotion, attracting investment (both domestic and foreign), technology up gradation and skill formation.

But in India, there are very few studies which examined the performance of SEZs and these studies are narrow in scope. So, there is a need of comprehensive analysis on the performance of SEZs in India. The present study is a modest attempt to fill the gap in SEZ literature.

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CHAPTER - III

SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONE AND GOVERNMENT POLICY

Introduction

The present chapter highlights thoroughly the subtle relationship between Special Economic Zones (SEZs) and Government Policy from a few theoretical approaches for the preparation and implementation of SEZs policy in India. It covers all theoretical approaches, and historical background of EPZs and SEZs in various phases and evolution of SEZs policy. The objective of this chapter is to explore the genesis of SEZs and to outline its historical evolution. The said chapter traces origin of SEZ as facilitators of transshipment trade to its present primary role as catalysts of economic activity. It also analysis changes in its structural, spatial, functional, and administrative dimensions. It takes a critical overviews of SEZs Act, 2005 and focuses on the constitutional formworks of SEZs Act, and Amendments and Rules of SEZs Act, 2006. It explore the benefits caused by Special economic zones to the people. Last but not the least the said chapter also cortically analysis, interprets, evaluates, appreciates, and the roughly examines the overall polices of the government in respect of the implementation and execution SEZs in India. This policy intended to make SEZs as an engine for economic growth supported by quality infrastructure, complemented by an attractive fiscal package, both at the Centre and the State level, with the minimum possible regulations. SEZs in India functioned from 1.11.2000 to 09.02.2006 under the provisions of the Foreign Trade Policy and fiscal incentives were made effective through the provisions of relevant statutes.

Historical Background of SEZs Policy:

Historically, India's economic policies focused on import substitution and protectionism: the government imposed high barriers to trade and high levels of red tape. An essential stepping-stone in India's economic history was the formation of the Planning Commission in 1950 - a government institution focused on formulating Five-Year Plans with the overarching goal of economic efficiency and economic development. Planned growth has been an essential

facet of India's government policy right from the implementation of Constitutional and democratic rule in India.

In 2005, the Government of India announced a Special Economic Zone Policy, as an extension of the Export Processing Zone Policy established in the 1960s. This Special Economic Zone (SEZ) policy has become part of Indian legislation with the intention of fostering economic growth and development on a local level and increasing foreign direct investment, as well as increasing employment and productivity. Areas designated as Special Economic Zones (SEZs) are ones that the government of India provides with fiscal incentives and improved infrastructure. Those are a form of unbalanced economic development initiatives – defined as growth initiatives that only affect specific areas or industries in a country, rather than the country as a whole. Unbalanced initiatives often manifest in the form of government efforts to jumpstart growth in specific places. The SEZ policy has been controversial in India, and the value of similar policies is debated in the larger economic literature. The debate between unbalanced and balanced economic development initiatives has a long history. Opponents suggest that it is expensive and ineffective, whereas exponents describe it as cost-effective. One critic speculates that the policy has “resulted in the displacement of poor farm families and villagers, brutal land acquisition, and gross human rights violations by the state at the behest of private capital” (Ananthanarayanan, 2007)

The SEZ Act of 2000 outlined the following objectives for the policy: increased economic activity, expanded exports, more investments - both domestic and foreign, increased employment, and improved infrastructure. Indeed, the Ministry of Commerce and Industry introduced the SEZ policy in April 2000 “with a view to overcome the shortcomings experienced on account of the multiplicity of controls and clearances.” Furthermore, in the “absence of world-class infrastructure and with [an unstable fiscal regime, [the Indian government had] a view to attract larger foreign investments in India” (SEZ India website).

Theoretical Perspectives: - Towards a Better Understanding of the SEZ Impact:

This chapter critically examines the theoretical proposition that seek to explain the rational and economic effects of SEZs on developing countries and argues that the existing theoretical approaches are limited to fully capture the phenomena. For a better understanding of socio- economic impact of contemporary SEZs, it processes an alternative approach based on the economics of agglomeration, in general, and industrial clustering, in particular, and integrates theoretical accounts with an agglomeration theoretic framework to develop an eclectic overview of their relevance and impacts, and provide compressive evaluation criteria.

Theoretical Approaches of SEZs: There are five distinct theoretical perspectives on the rational and benefits of Special Economic Zones (SEZs): Neoclassical, Neo-Marxist, and Heterodox.

The Neo Classical Approach: *The Trade-theoretic Approach* -The mainstream neo-classical economic theory views SEZs as enclaves offering open and freer trade policies set up with the objective of promoting trade. According to this theory, free trade is the best policy for a government to adopt. If freer trade is not politically viable at economy wide level, some welfare gains may be obtained from SEZs. SEZs therefore represent, at best, a second best policy. When viewed from a static perspective, SEZs are distortionary trade instruments which distort trade patterns, promote unfair competition between domestic and SEZ firms, drain government revenue and if the rest of the economy is not liberalized they remain production enclaves with little economic contribution. It argues that SEZs are useful only when the government uses them as a vehicle to further economy wide reforms. Their role should therefore be transitory, facilitating the transition of an economy from import substituting regime to free trade regime with minimal government intervention. They lose their significance as countries implement country wide systemic trade, macroeconomic and exchange rate reforms (Madani 1999).

Cost-Benefit Approach - Warr (1983) in his seminal work proposed a ‘cost-benefit’ framework to assess the role of SEZs in a host economy. This approach, like the trade theoretic approach, maintains that SEZ are ‘economic enclaves’ within which manufacturing for export occurred under virtually free trade conditions while the rest of the economy follows an import-substitution regime. Unlike the mainstream approach, however, it assume that SEZs do generate backward linkage with the host country’s economy. They use domestic capital, workers, public utilities, and local inputs, and benefits the economy by making payments for their use in the form of wages, electricity tariffs, taxes, and payments for local inputs and by generating profits channeled to domestic shareholders. If the excess of actual payments at the market price over the opportunity cost of the resources exceeds the cost of setting up and maintaining zones, then their contribution to the economy is considered to be positive. Forward linkage are assumed to be insignificant in this exercise.

Figure 3.1. The Enclave Model (Source: Jayanthakumaran (2003))

This approach for the first time underlined the importance of backward and forward linkage in the context of SEZs and hence revealed the possibility of indirect effects of SEZs. Subsequently, many studies focused on SEZ linkages with the rest of economy.

The Political Economical Approach: The political economy perspective of SEZs is based on the ‘public choice theory’ (Buchanan and Tullock 1962), which draws on the interest group theories of Political Science and neo-classical

economic school. It argues that the provision of government intervention promotes lobbying by interest groups for rent seeking. The main lesson of this perspective which supports the principle of “minimalist government” is that the best strategy for all countries and in all situations is to liberalize - and not do much else. Free trade with minimal state intervention alone can ensure growth. The objective of the SEZ policy according to this approach is to generate rents to a few capitalists by facilitating land acquisition and offering tax incentives at the cost of the rest of the population, which in turn would reduce the overall welfare. The argument of the self-regulating market and minimalist government has increasingly been criticised. Evidence suggests that governments in industrialised countries manipulated and maintained rents to create a capitalist class and after the creation of this class used these rents to encourage them to invest in growth (Khan 2004).

The Neo-Marxist Dependency Theory

The basic tenet of this theory is that the primary rationale of setting up SEZs is to offer cheap labour to augment CVG, rather than tax and tariff privileges. According to this theory, SEZs are a tool to facilitate the production systems (global value chains) largely driven by TNCs to exploit differences in location costs, in particular labour, and are an outcome of capitalist industrialization. The main argument is that the fragmenting of production process and relocating some of them to developing countries has led to changes in the spatial division of labour to the extent that a New International Division of Labour (NIDL) has emerged between the developed and developing countries (Lanchrriere, 1969; Frobel et al., 1978). It divides the world economy into core of dominant national and a periphery of dependent economy into a core of dominant nations and a periphery of dependent ones (Frank, 1967). The Neo-Marxist framework seems to have been a little outdated for most countries. Yet, it has highlighted the importance of the social impacts of SEZs, along with the economic implications, enriching the literature further.

The Heterodox Approach:

The central premise of the heterodox approach is that SEZs are a strategic initiative of the government to create enabling conditions for export promotion in an export-oriented regime.

The Global Value Chain Approach: from the perspective of this approach the globalization process is accompanied by a rapid emergence of “global value chains”. The whole process of producing goods, from raw materials to finished product, has increasingly been “sliced” and each process is carried out wherever the necessary skills and materials are available at competitive cost either through off-shore outsourcing and/or offshoring.

Agglomeration Economies Approach: This approach does not focus on augmenting resources for growth but on reallocating them for promoting productivity and innovativeness.

The advantages of agglomerations are rooted in: knowledge spillovers, resource sharing, and labour pooling. Within this framework, SEZs are government promoted clusters of outward oriented firms, both foreign and local, and are set up to exploit the benefits arising from global value chains. These clusters enhance productivity and spur innovation by bringing together technology, information, specialized talent, competing companies, supporting companies, academic institutions, and other organizations.

The success of clusters depends on four sets of factors: firm’s structure, strategy and rivalry, demand conditions, factor conditions and supporting industries.

IV. Evolution of SEZ Policy in India (Evolution of SEZs and Government Policy in India)

India inherited an agriculture-dominated economic structure at Independence, with agriculture accounting for more than 50 per cent of the total GDP. The processes of industrial growth was initiated as early as 1948, when the government announced its first Industrial Policy Resolution, IPR 1948. The centerpiece of the development strategy was the promotion of import-

substitution-based industrialization with particular emphasis on basic and heavy industries (Aggarwal, 2001).

The country, however, faced a severe foreign exchange crunch in the early 1960s due to multiple crises such as the failure of agriculture, mounting imports, and tow border conflicts. To promote exports, many fiscal incentives such as cash compensatory support (1967), duty drawback (1972), and the import entitlement licence scheme (1962) were offered to exporters. As part of these programmes, the government set up an EPZ in Kandla in 1965 and become the first Asian country to adopt this model. Since then, the policy has undergone significant changes. This chapter reviews the evolution of the EPZ policy through different phases of growth and critically assesses changes in the SEZ policy from national and international perspectives. In addition to consulting policy documents, the analysis has benefited from interviews with various stakeholders during filed surveys.

SEZs policies have developed in India through three evolutionary phases such as; *The EPZ regime (1965-2000)*, *The transitional phase (2000-2005)*, *The SEZ regime*

Objectives of the policy:

The SEZ Act, 2005, supported by the SEZ Rules, come into effect from 10th February 2006, providing for simplification of procedures and for single window clearance on matters relating to Central as well as State Government. The main objectives of the SEZ Act/Policy are (i) Generation of additional economic activity, (ii) Promotion of exports of goods and services, (iii) Promotion of investment from domestic and foreign source, (iv) Creation of employment opportunities and (v) Development of Infrastructure facilities. It was anticipated that the new law would trigger a large flow of foreign direct investment as well as domestic investment in infrastructure and productive capacity leading to creation of new employment opportunities.

The sole purpose of the SEZs is to export goods and services and earn foreign Exchange. Government of India had announced a SEZ Scheme in April

2000 with a view to providing an internationally competitive environment for exports. The objectives of SEZs include making available goods and services free from taxes and duties supported by integrated infrastructure for export production, quick approval mechanisms and package of incentives to attract foreign and domestic investments for promoting exports.

3.2.2 SEZ Policy

The SEZ Policy recognizes the issues related to economic development and provides for developing self-sustaining Industrial townships so that the increased economic activity does not create pressure on the existing infrastructure. Considering the need to enhance investment and promote exports from the country and realizing the need that a playing field must be available to the domestic enterprise and manufactures to be competitive globally, “the EXIM policy-1997-2002 of government of India” introduced a new scheme from 1st April, 2000 for establishment of the SEZ in different parts of the country.

3.3 SEZ Act, 2005:

The Special Economic Zone Act, 2005, was passed by Parliament in May 2005. This Policy was intended to make SEZs an “engine for economic growth” supported by quality infrastructure completed by an attractive fiscal package, both at central and state levels, with minimum possible regulations. The Act stimulates Public-Private partnership for the purpose of establishment, development and management of SEZ with a view to promote exports.²⁰ Under SEZ Act, 2005 “Special Economic Zone” means each SEZ notified under the provision to sub-section (4) of section 321 and sub-section (1) of section 422 (including Free Trade and Warehousing Zone) and includes an existing SEZ. This is based on the China model. Export has a wider connotation in the Act and it is defined to mean (i) taking goods or providing services, out of India from SEZs by land, sea or air or by other model physically or otherwise, or (ii) supply goods or providing services from DTA to a unit or developer in SEZ, or (iii) supply goods or providing services from one unit to another unit or developer in the same or different SEZ. Similarly ‘import’ has a wider connotation so as to include bringing goods and services into a SEZ by a unit or developer from a

place outside India by land, sea, air or receiving goods or services by a unit or developer from another unit or developer of the same SEZ or a different SEZ Manufacturing includes agriculture, aquaculture, animal husbandry, floriculture, horticulture, pisciculture, poultry, sericulture, viticulture and mining. Another significant definition is the enlarged definition of 'Infrastructure' which includes all facilities needed for development, operation and maintenance of SEZ including industrial, business and social generation and distribution of power, telecommunication, data transmission network, information technology network, hospitals, hotels, educational institutions recreational facilities, residential and business complex, water supply, to mention a few among many other facilities envisaged etc. With all these facilities, SEZ are intended to self-contained township

Overview of the Special Economic Zone Act, 2005:

Previously Special Economic Zones in India were governed by Chapter X-A of the Customs Act, the Special Economic Zones Rules, 2003, and the Special Economic Zones (Customs Procedures) Regulations, 2003 and Chapter 7 and 7A of Foreign Trade Policy. However, w.e.f. 10th February, 2006 the activities relating to Special Economic Zones are guided by the provisions contained in the Special Economic Zones Act, 2005 and the Special Economic Zones Rules, 2006. After the enactment of the Special Economic Zones Act, 2005 Chapter X-A of the Customs Act, the Special Economic Zones Rules, 2003, and the Special Economic Zones (Customs Procedures) Regulations, 2003 are not in operation.

Special Economic Zones Act 2005 consists of 8 chapters, 58 sections and 3 schedules. The provisions of this Act shall have effect notwithstanding anything inconsistent therewith contained in any other law for the time being in force or in any instrument having effect by virtue of any law other than this Act. (Section 51)

Bird's eye view of the Special Economic Zones Act, 2005:

The following table provides an insight to the Special Economic Zones Act 2005

Table No.3.1: Bird's eye view of the Special Economic Zones Act, 2005

Chapter	Sections	Title
I	1-2	Preliminary
II	3-7	Establishment of SEZ
III	8-10	Constitution of Board of Approval
IV	11-12	Development Commissioner
V	13-25	Single Window Clearance
VI	26-30	Special Fiscal provisions for SEZ
VII	31-41	Special Economic Zone Authority
VIII	42-58	Miscellaneous
The First Schedule		The First Schedule
The Second Schedule		Modifications of the Income Tax Act-1961
The third schedule	Part I	Amendments to certain Enactments
	Part II	Amendments to the Banking Regulation Act,1949
	Part III	Amendments to the Indian Stamp Act,1899

(Source: SEZs Act, 2005, Draft Ministry of Commerce, Government of India)

The Special Economic Zones Act 2005 includes for the following Provision:

1. Procedure for making proposal to establish SEZ (Sec 3)
2. Establishment of SEZ with the approval from Board of Approvals (Sec 4)
3. Notifying an area as SEZ by Central Government (Sec 5)
4. Approval by Board of Approval for establishment of SEZ (Sec 8 to 10)
5. Development Commissioner as administrative Authority for the SEZ (Sec 11 and 12)

6. Approval Committee to approve setting up of an unit in SEZ (Sec 13 and 14)
7. Single window clearance by Approval Committee for setting up unit in SEZ, setting up an OBU and setting up an IFSC.(Sec 15 to 20)
8. Enforcement officer or agency for notified offences (Sec 21 and 22)
9. Special civil courts and criminal courts to try notified offences and appeal to High Court (Sec 23 and 24)
10. Special Fiscal provisions for special economic zones(Sec 26 to 30)
11. Establishment of SEZ Authority (Sec 31 to 41)
12. Reference of dispute to arbitration (Sec 42 and 43)
13. Exemptions and relaxations from provisions of some Central Acts (Sec 49 and 54)
14. Power of the Central Government to make rules and to remove difficulties (Sec 55 and 56)

The SEZ Act 2005 envisages key role of the State Governments in Export Promotion and creation of related infrastructure. A Single Window SEZ approval mechanism has been provided through a 19 member inter-ministerial SEZ Board of Approval (Annexure-I BoA). The applications duly recommended by the respective State Governments/UT Administration are considered by this BoA periodically. All decision of the Board of approvals is with consensus.

The SEZ Rules provide different minimum land requirement for different class of SEZs. Every SEZ is divided into a processing area where alone the SEZ units would come up and the non-processing area where the supporting infrastructure is to be created.

3.4 SEZ Rules 2006

In exercise of powers conferred by section 55 of SEZ Act,²³ the Central government notified the SEZ rule, 2006 on 10th February 2006. The rule comprehensively provides the essential requirements for setting up a unit in a SEZ, guidelines for the developer, the procedure to be followed from submission of application for approval, procedure for the procurement of inputs, sub-

contracting from outside, sale in DTA, monitoring of the performance of individual units to de-bonding of the units. The SEZ Rules provide for different minimum land requirement for different class of SEZs. Every SEZ is divided into a processing and non-processing area where alone the SEZ units would come up and the non-processing area where supporting infrastructure is to be created.

5.1 Overview of the Special Economic Zones Rules, 2006:

The policy relating to special economic zones is contained in Special Economic Rules, 2006 notified in the Gazette of India, Extraordinary No. GSR 54 (E), dated 10.2.2006. The Rules contain 8 chapters, 77 rules, 11 forms - A to K and 2 Annexures

Bird's eye view of the Special Economic Zones Rules, 2006:

The following table provides an insight to the Special Economic Zones Rules, 2006.

Table No.3.2: Bird's eye view of the Special Economic Zones Rules, 2006

Chapter	Rules	Title
I	1-2	Preliminary
II	3-16	Procedure for establishment of SEZ
III	17-21	Procedure for establishment of an unit
IV	22-46	Terms and conditions subject to which entrepreneur and developers shall be entitled to exemptions, drawbacks and concessions
V	47-52	Conditions subject to which goods may be removed from a SEZ to DTA
VI	53-54	Foreign Exchange earning-Requirements and Monitoring
VII	55-69	Appeal
VIII	70-77	Miscellaneous

(Source: SEZs Act, 2006, Draft Ministry of Commerce, Government of India)

The significant features of the Special Economic Zones Rules 2006 are as follows:

1. Simplification of procedures for development, operation, and maintenance of the Special Economic Zones and for setting up and conducting business in SEZs;
2. Single window clearance for setting up of an SEZ;
3. Single window clearance for setting up a unit in a Special Economic Zone;
4. Single Window clearance on matters relating to Central as well as State Governments;
5. simplified compliance procedures and documentation with an emphasis on self-certification;
6. A wide range of services can be rendered from SEZs;
7. Documentation for various activities of the units has been reduced to the barest minimum with an emphasis on self-certification.
8. No requirement for providing bank guarantees, thereby reducing transaction costs;
9. Contract manufacturing for foreign principals allowed;
10. Option to obtain sub-contracting permission at the initial approval stage;

Other significant features of the Rules are:

1. Documentation for various activities of the units has been reduced to the barest minimum with an emphasis on self-certification.
2. No requirement for providing bank guarantees, thereby reducing transaction costs;
3. Contract manufacturing for foreign principals allowed;
4. Option to obtain sub-contracting permission at the initial approval stage;
5. Import-Export of all items, through personal baggage has been allowed

Important definitions in the Rules include:

“Special Economic Zone for multi-product” means a Special Economic Zone where Units may be set up for manufacture of two or more goods in a sector or goods falling in two or more sectors or for trading and warehousing or rendering of two or more services in a sector or rendering of services falling in two or more sectors (Rule 2(za))

“Special Economic Zone for specific sector” means a Special Economic Zone meant exclusively for one or more products in a sector or one or more services in a sector (Rule 2(zb))

“ Special Economic Zone in a port or airport “ means a Special Economic Zone in an existing port or airport for manufacture of goods in two or more goods in sector or goods falling in two or more sectors or for trading and warehousing or rendering of services (Rule 2(zc))

Recent developments on Special economic zones

- A) Special Economic Zones (Amendment) Rules, 2006
- B) Removal of caps on SEZ
- C) List of authorised activities in non-processing area of SEZ’s to be notified
- D) Criteria for approval of SEZ developers
- E) No SEZ on prime agriculture Land An amendment has been made in the Special Economic Zones Rules by way of -The Special economic Zones (Amendment) Rules, 2006 which came into force on 10.08.2006. The relevant notification is reproduced hereunder:

A) Special Economic Zones (Amendment) Rules, 2006

Special Economic Zones (Amendment) Rules, 2006 - Amendments in rules 5, 11, 18 and 76; insertion of rule 5A, and Notification NO G.S.R. 470(E), dated 10-8-2006. *In exercise of the powers conferred by section 55 of the Special Economic Zones Act, 2005 (28 of 2005), the Central Government hereby makes the following rules to amend the Special Economic Zones Rules, 2006, namely:-*

1. (1) These rules may be called the Special Economic Zones (Amendment) Rules, 2006. (2) They shall come into force on the date of their publication in the Official Gazette.

2. In the Special Economic Zones Rules, 2006 (hereinafter referred to as the principal rules), in sub-rule (2) of rule 5,- (1) in clause (a), for the third proviso, the following proviso shall be substituted, namely :-

Provided also that at least thirty-five per cent of the area shall be earmarked for developing the processing area, which may be relaxed up to twenty-five per cent by the Central Government on recommendations of the Board for the reasons to be recorded in writing;” (2) In clause (b) in the second proviso, for the words “the area shall be ten hectares or more”, the following shall be substituted, namely:-

“The area shall be ten hectares or more with a minimum built-up area as under: (i) forty thousand square meters in case of a Special Economic Zone proposed to be set up exclusively for bio-technology and non-conventional energy sectors including solar energy equipment’ s/cells but excluding a Special Economic Zone set up for non-conventional energy production and manufacturing; (ii) fifty thousand square meters in case of a Special Economic Zone proposed to be set up exclusively for the gems and jewellery sector.”

(3) In clause (c), - (i) for the first proviso, the following proviso shall be substituted, namely:-

“**Provided** that in a standalone Free Trade and Warehousing Zone at least fifty per cent of the area shall be earmarked for developing processing area: **Provided further** that a Free Trade and Warehousing Zone may also be set up as part of a Special Economic Zone for multi-product;” (ii) in the second proviso, for the words “provided further”, the words “provided also” shall be substituted.

3. After rule 5 of the principal rules, the following rule shall be inserted, namely:-

(a) twenty-four hours uninterrupted power supply at stable frequency in the zone; (b) Reliable connectivity for uninterrupted and secure data transmission; (c) Provision for central air-conditioning system; and (d) a ready to use, furnished plug and pay facility for end users.”.

4. For sub-rule (10) of rule 11 of the principal rules, the following sub-rule shall be substituted, namely:-

“(10) No vacant land in the non-processing area shall be leased for business and social purposes such as educational institutions, hospitals, hotels, recreation and entertainment facilities, residential and business complexes, to any person except a co-developer approved by the Board **Provided** that the developer or co-developer may lease the completed infrastructure along with the vacant land appurtenant thereto for such purposes:

Provided further that infrastructure for business or social purposes in the Special Economic Zone, as may be approved by the Board, shall be eligible for exemptions, concessions and Drawback.”

5. In sub-rule (4) of rule 18 of the principal rules, after clause (f), the following clause shall be inserted, namely: - “(g) the use of any plant or machinery previously used for any purpose in Domestic Tariff Area.”

6. In rule 76 of the principal rules, - (i) For the words “sub-clause”, the word “clause” shall be substituted; (ii) The following *Explanation* shall be inserted at the end, namely:- “*Explanation.* - the expression “Trading”, for the purposes of the Second Schedule of the Act, shall mean import for the purposes of re-export.”

3.3.1 Amendment in the SEZ Act, 2005:

SEZ policy has taken one more turn with the announcement from the Empowered Group Ministers (EGOM). The freeze on them is being lifted but several parameters will be changed to accommodate the farmers, tribal and the civil society groups who have been agitating against the SEZs. From the earlier “no limit” set on the maximum size of the multi-product SEZ now the limit has been fixed at 5000 hectares. The state governments are prohibited from acquiring land for private players and they cannot form a joint venture with a private player unless the latter has the land to offer the Zone. Finally, the export requirements have been made more stringent compared to earlier.

5.2 Overview of Special Economic Zones (Amendment) Rules, 2006:

An amendment was made in the Special Economic Zones Rules by way of -The Special economic Zones (Amendment) Rules, 2006 which came into force on 10.08.2006 (vide Notification NO G.S.R. 470(E), dated 10-8-2006)

The effect of this notification which is mainly on area requirements and processing area can be summarized as below: Area requirements for different SEZ can be summarized as follows table No 3.3:

Table No.3.3

Area requirements for different SEZ can be summarized as follows:

Sr. No	SEZ Type	Minimum Area		Minimum Area for Specific State(s)	Minimum Processing Area	
		OLD	NEW		OLD	NEW
1	Multi Product	1000 hectares	1000 hectares	200 hectares	25%	35%
2	Multi Service	100 hectares	100 hectares	100 hectares	25%	25%
3	Specific Sector	100 hectares	100 hectares	50 hectares	50%	50%
4	Electronic Hardware and Software	10 hectares (with 1 Lac square meter built up area)	10 hectares (with 1 Lac square meter built up area)	10 hectares (with 1 Lac square meter built up area)	50%	50%
5	Bio Technology/ Non - conventional energy	10 hectares	10 hectares (With a minimum built-up area of forty thousand square meters)	10 hectares (With a minimum built-up area of forty thousand square meters)	50%	50%
6	Gems and Jewellery Sector	10 hectares	10 hectares (With a minimum built-up area of fifty thousand square meters)	10 hectares (With a minimum built-up area of fifty thousand square meters)	50%	50%
7	Free Trade and warehousing Zone	40 hectares (with 1 Lac	40 hectares (with 1 Lac	40 hectares	-	-

(Source: Data Collected from Ministry of Commerce, GoI, 2013)

Besides the above, the other changes made are as follows:

➤ **Infrastructure requirements relating to information technology**

A new rule - 5 A has been inserted detailing infrastructure facilities that a Developer of Information Technology specific SEZ should provide. They include:

- twenty four hour uninterrupted power supply at stable frequency;
- reliable connectivity for uninterrupted and secure data transmission;
- central air-conditioning system;
- Ready to use, furnished plug and pay facility for end users.

➤ **A Developer was earlier permitted to allot land in the non-processing area for business and social purposes.**

The SEZ Amendment Rules have amended the above condition to the effect that no vacant land in the non-processing area shall be leased for business and social purposes to any person except a Co-developer approved by the Board. Further, it has been provided that a Developer or Co-developer may lease completed infrastructure along with vacant land appurtenant thereto.

➤ **Previously used Plant & Machinery**

It has been provided that any proposal for setting up SEZ Unit by using plant and machinery previously used for any purpose in the Domestic Tariff Area (“DTA”) shall not be considered.

➤ **Trading activity in the SEZ**

The SEZ Rules have been amended to provide to the effect for claiming Income-tax benefits, the term trading shall mean import for the purpose of re-export. This means profits from trading (exports) of locally procured goods shall not be eligible for Income-tax benefits.

3.4.1 Performance of SEZs Law and Policy

Foreign Trade Policy intended to make SEZs a rapid economic growth with quality infrastructure complemented by an attractive fiscal package, both at the Centre and the State level, with the minimum possible regulations.²⁴ SEZs in India functioned from 1.11.2000 to 09.02.2006 under the provisions of the Foreign Trade Policy and fiscal incentives were made effective through the provisions of relevant statutes.²⁵

The Special Economic Zones Act, 2005, was passed by Parliament in May, 2005 which received Presidential assent on the 23rd of June, 2005. The draft SEZ Rules were widely discussed and put on the website of the Department of Commerce offering suggestions/comments. Around 800 suggestions were received on the draft rules. After extensive consultations, the SEZ Act, 2005, supported by SEZ Rules, came into effect on 10th February, 2006, providing for drastic simplification of procedures and for single window clearance on matters relating to central as well as state governments.²⁶

EVOLUTIONARY CHANGES IN THE POLICY

Highlighted below are changes as the EPZ policy transformed into the SEZ Policy, and their critical assessment.

Structural Characteristics

Objectives Units the 2005 Act: the objective of EPZs were not clearly spelt out in policy documents in India. The site of Kandla for the First EPZ was selected with the multiple objectives of assisting the development of Kandla Port, developing an industrially-backward regions of Kutch, and helping the refugee population from Sindh settled there after Partition. A second zone followed in 1973 at Santa Cruz with the aim of accelerating the progress of electronics manufacturing in India and to take advantage of fast-expanding GVCs in the electronics sector which were primarily based in SEZs in other parts of the world (Tondon Committee, 1982). However, EPZs were essentially viewed as a tool for export promotion and earning foreign exchange, and not for

promotion of industry (Kundra, 2000). The predominant condition in selecting EPZ units has been the expected value addition component of exports, which was also used to assess their performance (Kumar, 1989). This did not allow EPZs to augment GVCs and facilitate the insertion of domestic firms in these chains.

The SEZ Act entailed a major shift in the objectives of the policy from export promotion to generation of additional economic activity and development of infrastructure. SEZs are now typically viewed as engines of outward-oriented industrialization. The condition of minimum value addition has been dropped in favour of ‘positive net foreign exchange earnings over a stipulated period of time’. The objectives started in the policy document ignore some of the most important reasons for establishing SEZs, such as attracting foreign technologies, generating backward and forward spillovers (Johansson 1994:394-5) and, in turn, diversifying exports and upgrading human resources; nonetheless, a distinct departure from the past is evident.

Structural Set-up While an EPZ was essentially a manufacturing-oriented industrial estate, the purpose of which was to attract export oriented Industries, ‘SEZs’ subsume a variety of zones, as follows:

- ***Free Trade and Warehousing Zones (FTWZs)***: These are trade-based SEZs with the focus on trading and warehousing. They are ‘international trading hubs’ established in area proximate to seaports, airports, or dry ports so as to offer easy access by rail and road.
- ***Sector-specific SEZs***: Sector-specific SEZs offer highly-specialized facilities, configured to the need of specific industries and activities. While some SEZs are based on Labour-intensive sport shoes and textile sectors, others are specialized in highly capital and technology intensive petrochemicals, bio-tech, electronics and pharmaceutical products.
- ***Service-based SEZs***: All IT and IT - enabled Service SEZs are service-based SEZs. In addition, there are multi-service SEZs as well.

- **Port-based SEZs:** Port-based zones are logistics parks set up in port hinterlands.
- **Hybrid SEZs:** These zones have both DTA and Export area adjacent to each other. Mahindra World City and Sri City SEZs are examples of Hybrid zones.
- **Single -enterprise:** Captive SEZs are equivalent to EOUs.
- **Multi-product SEZs:** These SEZs are large in scale and can function as independent towns by providing residential, medical, educational, and business services.

Following the global spread of SEZ policy innovations, different varieties of SEZs have evolved in India too. They vary in size, location, infrastructure, management and, most importantly, economic activity. All of them are However, Fenced-in-zones, unlike Chinese SEZs which are large open territories governed by independent governments.

Sectoral Coverage: Prior to 1990, EPZ activities were manufacturing-oriented; trading, service, and agriculture - related processing activities were out of the purview of the policy. In 1992, agriculture, horticulture and aquaculture, animal husbandry or similar activity, and production of software were also permitted. In 1997, special thrust was given to software units and by 1999 EPZs permitted units in 'other service'. Thus the scope of EPZ activities had covered almost all economic activities except trading even before the SEZs policy was announced. The SEZ policy expanded the scope by including trading. While this may be instrumental in generating linkages between SEZ units by forming local value chains and ensuring spillover effects, its potential is not fully recognized by the policymakers. Trading is normally discouraged by denying tax breaks on profits generated from this activity.

Size: Internationally, the size of SEZs has been growing. Until recently, China had the largest zones with Hainan SEZ spreading over 34,000 s.q. km. Malaysia now claims to be developing the largest SEZ in the World.

Prior to the SEZ AVCT, India had rather small Special Economic Zones. Kandla was the largest with a land area of 10 sq.km. Realizing that only large zones can generate economic activity on a reasonable scale, the policymakers have provided for minimum land requirements for different classes of SEZs in SEZs Rules (Table No3.4)

Table 3.4 SEZ Rules 2006: Sector-wise land Requirement

Type of SEZ	Area	Area for Special States/UTs
Multi-product	1000 hectares	200 hectares
Multi- service	100 hectares	100 hectares
Sector-specific	100 hectares	100 hectares
IT	10 hectares and min. built-up area of 1 lakh sq. mtrs	10 hectares and min. built-up area of 1 lakh sq. mtrs
Gems and Jewellery	10 hectares and min. built-up area of 50 thousand sq. mtrs	10 hectares and min. built-up area of 50 thousand sq. mtrs
Bio-tech and non-conventional energy (including solar energy equipment/cell but excluding SEZs for non-conventional energy production and manufacturing)	10 hectares and min. built-up area of 40 thousand sq. mtrs	10 hectares and min. built-up area of 40 thousand sq. mtrs
FTWZ	10 hectares and min. built-up area of 1 lakh sq. mtrs	10 hectares and min. built-up area of 1 lakh sq. mtrs

(Source: SEZs Rules, 2006, Department of Commerce, Government of India.)

To facilitate the expansion of large sized SEZs, an amendment was effected to the SEZ Rules 2006 on 16 March 2007 providing conversion of one class of SEZ into another class if the developer acquires more contiguous and vacant land subsequent to approved or notification of an SEZ. This allowed developers to start setting up a sector-specific SEZ on a minimum area available and then progress towards setting up a multiproduct SEZ. On 12 October 2007, however, following protests over land acquisition, in particular in Nandigram and Singur in West Bengal, SEZ size was capped at 5000 hectares. Subsequently, in an amendment to the Rules on 20 May 2009, clubbing of whether the total area of the resultant Special Economic Zones exceeded 5000 hectares. Further, since it is difficult to acquire large tracts of contiguous land, the Board now holds the power to relax the condition of absence of public thoroughfare, on a case-to-case basis, with respect to all classes of SEZs, as a measure to ensure large-size SEZs.

The thrust has not only been on promoting large-size SEZs but also on encouraging large-sized production units within them. In most countries, this is ensured through investment thresholds necessary to avail tax benefits. In India, policy documents do not specify any such eligibility criteria but it was learned in discussion with officials that in practice large units requiring a threshold size of land are given preference in approval. Considering that land is a scarce resource, it would be better if the focus were on investment and employment as eligibility criteria to ensure a minimum scale of activity.

Ownership: Until the year 2000, development of EPZ was the primary responsibility of the Central Government. Since then, it has been responsible only for making policy and monitoring its implementation. New SEZ are being established and operated by state governments, public sectors undertakings, the private sector - including foreign companies, and the joint sector. It has been learnt from official sources that the authorities of Central Government SEZs have of late been contemplating the setting up of new zones independently/jointly with other sectors. This may herald a new phase of expansion in Central Government

SEZs. Private SEZs have been at the center of the SEZ debates in India. However, from the global perspective this is not new; there has been a worldwide trend towards private zones. Indian perspective, government's initiative to promote private investment in SEZ development is a part of its policy of encouraging and facilitating private investment in large-scale residential, commercial, infrastructural, and industrial projects through various incentives.

Location: Strategic location and multi-modal connectivity with major trading destinations are factors critical to the success of SEZs. It is generally believed that if zones are strategically located near ports they provide investor/ units with an easy gateway to international trade. Proximity of Chinese SEZs to the seaports and airports of Hong Kong and Taiwan is believed to have played a critical role in the growth and success of these SEZs (World Bank 2009). Many, however, argue that locating manufacturing SEZs near urban centers and existing industrial estates/clusters can significantly cut down the cost of developing outside infrastructure and is more likely to ensure success (Warr, 1989; Jayanthakumaran, 2003;). In India, in a major departure from the past, the policy allows an interplay of market forces in location choice. It does not impose any preferences or restrictions on SEZ location. Erstwhile EPZs were created along the coastline, Noida being the only exception. New SEZs are, however emerging near urban centers (Mukhopadhyay and Pradhan, 2009; Kemmedy, 2009). This has an important implication in terms of their performance.

INSTITUTIONAL CHARACTERISTICS

Prior to the SEZ Act, there was no overriding EPZ legislation or an EPZ authority. The proposal for an autonomous EPZ Authority was moved by the Tondon Committee in 1982 and was endorsed by several subsequent committees (Kendra, 2000). But the government could introduce neither an EPZ Act nor an autonomous authority to govern the EPZs. It was in 2005 that the SEZ Act 2005 was enacted which, along with the SEZ Rules, provides an umbrella legal framework for each of the three principal stakeholders; developers (and co-developers), operators, and tenant/units. The Act does not, however, cover

subjects which are exclusive legislative powers of state governments such as states commercial taxes and duties, local taxes and duties, land, power, water, pollution control and environment, labour, law and order. Governments are advised to formulate a SEZ policy or Act to cover these state subjects, and the policy is to be implemented through state and municipal government departments. Apparently, the overriding powers have not been used to reduce interference by different layers of government. This makes the implementation of the policy contingent upon political cooperation between different levels of government. Since a state government, party politics may affected the implementation of the policy as well (Jenkins, 2007; Kennedy, 2009). The devolution of powers between Centre and states has created frictions in the bureaucracy, with the state-level bureaucracy feeling alienated. From filed surveys, it has been observed that the general feeling among state bureaucrats was that the state governments were better equipped to manage their SEZs since they already offered a signal-window mechanism for non-SEZ investment approvals and had vast administrative infrastructure in place for promoting industries. They felt they were not sufficiently empowered to take key policy decisions related to SEZs and their operation, and that their role was that of mere facilitators. This feeling of alienation is likely to affect their involvement in implementation.

Further, a comparative analysis of EPZ and SEZ policies reveals that typical administrative structure of SEZs has not changed significantly under the new policy regime. Prior to the SEZs policy, the zone administration was tree-tiered. At the apex level was the EPZ section within the Ministry of Commerce which was headed by the Commerce Secretary. Who used to be responsible for all policy issues and periodically reviewed the working of zones. At the next level was the Board of Approval, an inter-ministerial body responsible for examining proposals for its day-to-day administration.

Under the SEZs Act also, the administrative set-up of SEZs is three tiered. At the apex level is a non-statutory 19-member inter-ministerial body responsible for policy matters and offering a single –window approval

mechanism for SEZ developers; next in the hierarchy is the Unit Approval Committee constituted under the state government and department of revenue which acts as the single-window clearance mechanism for SEZ units and deals with the working of the zones; at tier three is the development commissioner who is the executive directors of SEZs. Thus the basic administrative framework remains the same; only the functions, powers, and constitution of various authorities have undergone some changes.

Finally, while single-window mechanisms are ostensibly in place for the approval of SEZs and units therein, in practice government agencies at the central, state, and municipal levels need to be coordinated to operationalize a single window for post-approval formalities and governance. Problems arise for both the developers and the units if there is lack of coordination among these administrative agencies. In many interviews with developers and entrepreneurs, it was learnt that many departments at the state and municipal government levels had not altered their rules even after the SEZ rules come into force. As a result, whenever there is conflict between the local and SEZ rules, officials override SEZ rules due to lack of knowledge and sometimes out of insecurity. The problems can multiply because there is no formal appeal and grievance redressed or accountability mechanism within the SEZ set-up.

In most countries, an autonomous body is created as the absolute authority for any legal procedure, implementation issue, or marketing of SEZs, which acts as a single window for all SEZ-related issues and is accountable to SEZ actors. However, the policy in India did not override the federal structure of decision making. Some of the ancillary issues, most importantly land acquisition which has been at the center of debate, were overlooked in the expectation that the state governments would address them. The policy did little to experiment with innovative features. The Act has not only faced the vagaries of federal coordination and cooperation. If inter-ministerial conflicts crop up, there is no provision to address them within the SEZ framework. The Finance and Commerce ministries, for instance, have been looked in dispute over revenue forgone ever since the SEZ rush started in 2006. By creating instability in policy

and exposing the government's claims of commitment to it, thus has defeated the very logic of introducing the Act. In the initial phase, it was resolved by the intervention of the Prime Minister's Advisory Economic Council and an Empowered Group of Ministers (EGoM) constituted by the government. However, much done around 'ministerial and bureaucratic politics' was created in the media that it shook the confidence of foreign investor and badly affected inflows of FDI. The controversy flared up once again when the Finance Ministry diluted tax benefits offered to SEZs in the current budget of 2011-12, overriding the SEZ Act. The developers of the Mundra SEZ have already filed a petition against this 'arbitrary move' while other SEZ developers are contemplating doing the same. Further, the policy completely ignored some core issues such as land acquisition and governance of multi-product zones. These issues eventually become the most contentious issue in the SEZ debate, the upshot being that the policy could neither craft a careful coordination between various actors involved in its implementation nor could it provide accountability safeguards to create a climate conducive to the credibility of the policy.

EVOLUTION OF THE SEZ BENEFIT PACKAGE

The evolution of SEZ policy in the benefited by high-quality infrastructure, good location, incentive package, simple administrative procedures, and relaxed regulatory machinery.

INCENTIVES

An attractive incentive package confers a comparative advantage on EPZs over the wide economy. The objective is to wipe out the distortions created by high tariff and non-tariff barriers, high tax rates prevalent and the rigidly tight regulatory regime outside the zones. These incentives relate to direct and indirect taxes, foreign exchange management, labour, immigration, DTA sale, investment, and foreign direct investment

Direct Tax Incentives: Prior to 1981, no income tax advantage was available to zone units in India. Concession were made available under Section 80-HH and 80-I of the Income Tax Act. The former was related to the backward area incentives whereby 20 per cent of the taxable income of a units located in

any backward district was exempt from income tax for 10 years. Under the latter, any new unit profits up to 25 % were exempt from income tax for a period of eight years. In 1981, tax holidays for five years were extended to the EPZ units while income tax concessions under 80-I and 80-HH were withdrawn. In 1999, the tax holiday was extended to 10 years. The rules were changed once again in 2000 under the SEZ policy when 100 % income tax exemption for a block of five years, 50 % for the next three years under Section 10A of the Income Tax Act were offered to zone units. These incentives have been further enhanced in the SEZ Act which ensures tax concessions for 15 years for SEZ units, that is, 100 % tax exemption for five years, 50 % for the next five years⁷. The SEZ developers are offered 100 per cent income tax exemption for 10 years in a block period of 15 years. A 100 per cent income-tax exemption for three years and 50 per cent for two years is applicable for offshore banking units as well. The SEZs are also exempt from dividend distribution tax, education cess and minimum alternative tax until recently. In addition, external commercial borrowing by SEZ units up to US\$ 500 million a year through recognized banking channels is permitted without any maturity restrictions.

While an attractive package of direct tax incentives is being offered to SEZ units, income tax exemption extended to outside units has been phased out over the period from 2000 to 2004. The 10-year holiday enjoyed by EOU/STPI units was rolled back in 2011. This has significantly enhanced the relative attractiveness of the incentive package to the zones. However, the government is seriously considering the dilution of SEZ tax benefits, which may have a considerable impact on the future prospects of SEZs.

Indirect Tax Benefits

Traditionally, SEZ units and developers are exempt from all custom duties on their production directed for export markets. In general, zone units also enjoy exemptions from other indirect taxes as well. In India, for instance, units supplying goods to zone units have been exempted from excise duty since 1981. Central sales tax exemption on all goods required by zone units from their

activity was extended to the zone in 2001. Most states had also given exemption from state sales tax. However, under the new scheme, both units and developers enjoy exemption from nearly all indirect taxes, including customs/ excise duties, central sales tax, service tax, value added tax, and all state sales taxes and other levies. In the last 10 to 15 years, the Indian taxation system has undergone tremendous reforms. Tax rates have come down sharply and the tax structure has been rationalized. Nevertheless, there still remains a problem of multiple taxation of commodities and multiplicity of taxes, resulting in a cascading tax burden. Therefore, tax exemptions extended to SEZs are likely to have a significant impact on the cost competitiveness of exports. These exemptions may also get diluted during the course of time.

Offshore Banking Units (OBUs): Prior to 2002, OBUs were not permitted to set up in the zones under the Foreign Trade Policy. The SEZ Act offers them attractive incentive packages. In some of the zones, these units have already been set up but progress is tardy perhaps due to the small scale of activity in the initial phases. These branches are working under highly-restrictive regulatory conditions which a mandate to serve predominantly the customers in the zone or lend to SEZ developers. Tariff Area (DTA). They cannot lend overseas nor participate in international syndications or consortia on a par with foreign branches. This restricts their growth and inhibits them from going for benefits from scale economies. They can neither finance overseas acquisitions nor found third-country trade. This limits their future growth prospects in SEZs also.

DTA Sales: Prior to 1982-83, DTA sale was not permitted. The 1982-83 budget allowed domestic tariff sales up to 25 % against veiled import licenses of domestic buyers. However, import licenses were very rarely issued for products that were being produced in the zones. Most licenses were for intermediate products or raw materials and not final products due to the highly-restrictive regime in place. The policy was, therefore, not effective. In 1991, the condition of import licence for DTA sales was waived and sales up to 25 %, subject to the domestic content of the product and fulfilment of the minimum value addition

obligation on payment of 50 % customs duty, were allowed. No permission was required for the sales/supply of samples in DTA and transfer of goods to DTA for repair, replacement/testing (after 1998). Subsequently, the conditions were further relaxed and, by 1999, DTA up to 50 per cent was permissible against full duty payment subject to fulfilment of obligations.

Under the SEZ Act there is no limitation on DTA sales subject to the fulfilment of positive net Foreign exchange earnings over five years and full duty payment. However, SEZ units find it difficult to compete in domestic markets. They report that it is not viable for them to sell in the domestic markets, primarily because zone units have to pay full duty on the finished product while outside units are paying duty only on components. India is currently on a signing spree of regional/bilateral trading agreements allowing partner countries duty-free access to its markets. Domestic sales from SEZs on the other hand, are subject to the payment of full duties. This is likely to divert import demand to mother countries, harming the development of domestic industrial capacity and the process of employment generation in the country.

FDI Policy: In the initial phase, FDI policy for the zones was rigid due to a restrictive attitude of the government towards FDI in the domestic economy. Each proposal was considered on a case-by-case basis. The zones did not permit foreign investors to hold hard currency accounts until 1980. There were severe restrictions on dividends and profit repatriation and transfer of shares. According to the business environment rating index which rate investment climate in 43 countries on the basis of 18 independent factors, Indian zones were placed at the bottom for FDI (TCS, 1997). The automatic route introduced in 1991 was applicable to FDI also. Permission through the automatic route was given by the DC while for the rest of the economy RBI was the approval authority. In 1992, 100 % foreign equity was permitted in the case of EOUs and EPZs, whereas outside the zones/EOUs, maximum equity permitted was 51 %. Under the SEZ rules, a distinguishing feature of the FDI policy in the zones is that no cap is applicable on foreign investment in items reserved for small-scale industries. In

the domestic economy foreign equity up to 24 % is allowed in small-scale industries. Zone foreign units have no other relative advantages vis-à-vis those outside the zone.

Labour laws India's EPZs/SEZ have never offered relaxation from domestic labour Commissioner and an officer of the Labour Department was posted in the SEZ to deal with labour matters; or an officer was nominated by the DC as labour officer. Zone were also declared public utility service which meant that no strike was permitted without notice. However, the SEZ Act is silent on the regime relating to labour. All labour laws of the land are applicable to the zones. In fact, labour laws are executed from the purview of section 49 of the SEZ Act which empowers individual states to modify the SEZ Act (Singh, 2009). While some states have conferred the powers of labour commissioner on DCs, most others have not modified any provision. Thus the SEZ policy has not seem to have offered any advantage in respect of labour laws.

Environment laws: As with labour laws, all environment laws are also applicable to EPZs/SEZs. Developers need to obtain environment clearance from the state government, state pollution board and, finally, the ministry of environment and forests. The units also have to acquire individual clearance from the state pollution boards. There is thus no race to the bottom for attracting investment in India's zones. It must also be noted that the policy prohibits recycling of plastic scrap or waste or other goods, and certain special chemicals, organisms, materials, equipment and technologies. Zone-specific and environment-specific considerations also figure in the approval process for the zones. For instance, water-intensive units are not allowed in the Madras, Falta, and Kandla EPZ.

INFRASTRUCTURE IN SEZs:

One of the objectives of SEZs is to create to world-class infrastructure. Provisions made towards this end are as follows.

Concept of processing and non-processing Area: Every SEZ is divided into a processing area designated for production activity and a non-processing

area where the supporting infrastructure is to be created. The SEZ developer is responsible for all civic amenities and infrastructure, including roads, sewerage system, open spaces, green spaces, educational facilities, power, water supply and housing, etc., in both the processing and non-processing area for SEZs.

SEZ Authority: In each of the central government zones an ‘SEZ Authority’ has been constituted, in particular to develop infrastructure. For raising funds, it has been authorized to fix user charges, fee, or rent for the use of property belonging to it. The objective is to grant autonomy to the Central Government-owned SEZs.

Infrastructure Development Norms: Infrastructure that need to be created within an SEZ has been notified in the notification of 27 October 2006. In order to ensure substantial investment in infrastructure that the developers need to provide - by way of industrial infrastructure - roads, telecom and other communication facilities, electricity, water, common effluent treatment plants, sewage treatment plants, etc. in addition, sector-specific SEZs such as IT, Biotech, and gems and jewellery, are also allowed to provide apartments, convention Centre, cafeterias and restaurants, and recreational facilities. Sector-specific SEZs may also have hotels, schools, and other educational and technical institutes. Multi-product SEZs are allowed to have ports, airports, and golf courses. Maintenance agencies assisting the developer have chambers within the SEZ.

Through an amendment in August 2006, it was stipulated that SEZs in the IT/ITES sector should also meet certain minimum infrastructure requirement such as uninterrupted 24-hours power supply at stable frequency; reliable connectivity for uninterrupted and secure data transmission; provision for central air-conditioning systems; and a ready-to-use, furnished plug-and-play facility for end-users. For the Approvals assesses the scale of infrastructure required as regards housing, commercial spaces, recreational facilities, etc., based on the employment-generation potential of the SEZ. Approvals for infrastructure development are given by the BoA in a phased manner. In the first phase, only a maximum of 25 % of the approved housing is allowed while the other approved

infrastructure will be allowed to be created as per the developer's plans and approved in the Master Plan. The Remaining houses required shall be allowed to be taken up in three phases depending upon the progress in allotment/occupancy of units in the processing area. The Approval Committee is headed by the DC and is in place to ensure that the authorized activities are carried out strictly as per the SEZ Act and Rules.

In general, the intent is that the social infrastructure in the non-processing area would predominantly service the requirements of those working in the processing area. However, since no duty concession are available for operation and maintenance of the social infrastructure located in the non- processing area, no such restrictions are imposed in the SEZ Act or SEZ Rules on the use of social infrastructure in the non-processing area.

While addressing concerns that SEZ developers might veer off into real estate project, policymakers have specified cap on social infrastructure on the basis of the social and commercial infrastructure required for SEZs. Further, the minimum processing area for multi-product SEZs has been raised up to 50 % vide an amendment to SEZs rules on 10 August 2006. Initially, in the case of multi-product SEZs with minimum land requirement of over 1000 hectors, the minimum processing area was 25 %, Realizing that this might defeat the purpose of the policy to build townships, in the new rules notified for the Special Economic Zones (SEZs) in February 2011 the mandatory built - up processing area has been halved for 15 cities-including Raipur, Varanasi, Jabalpur, Amritsar, Nasik, Dhanbad, and Madurai - and has been cut to one - fourth of the standard norm (125 hectares) in smaller towns. The amended SEZ rules will encourage developers and units to go to semi-urban and rural areas.

Concluding Remarks

The EPZ policy was introduced in the mid-1960s to promote exports and earn foreign exchange. During the course of time, the policy underwent several incremental changes. However, these were not sufficient to address the fundamental weakness in the policy and restore confidence among investors. In 2000, the government introduced profound structural changes which were finally institutionalized in 2005 with the passage of the SEZ Act 2005. These changes put together a highly-attractive package with emphasis on quality infrastructure, private ownership, highly-simplified rules pertaining to day-to-day operations, freedom over choice of location, time-based approvals, delegation of powers to DCs, continuous up gradation of rules, and introduction of e-governance. This has been generally referred as a paradigm shift. But the analysis in this chapter has shown that the changes, though profound, are not as revolutionary as the rhetoric would have made us believed. The policy has certain institutional flaws which make its implementation excessively contingent on a high level of political commitment.

Viewed from the international perspective, the package offered by the policy is not sufficiently attractive to divert international investment to these SEZs. Restriction on the size and infrastructure of SEZs; and absence of single-window governance mechanism, an exit policy, land acquisition policy, and a grievance redressed mechanism are serious obstacles in the development and prospectus of SEZs in India.. There are three basic principles of administration: accountability, effective partnership, and community responsiveness. These are not strongly upheld by the SEZs policy. A shift in paradigm means 'thinking outside of the box' or 'change in mindset'. In that sense, the new SEZs policy is not a paradigm shift, but nonetheless, it has indeed introduced many structural changes in the erstwhile policy and hence the said chapter has explored the positive and negative effects of SEZs on Indian life and Government Policies.

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CHAPTER - IV

SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONE (SEZs) AND RURAL DEVELOPMENT

4.1. Introduction

The present chapter deals with important aspects of Special Economic Zone (SEZs) and Rural Development. The government of India (GoI) introduced a Special Economic Zone (SEZ) Policy. The aim of the Policy is to promote export oriented industrial and economic development for the proponents of rapid development of India. SEZs are considered as engines of high economic growth. Agriculture and allied activities are largest sectors in Indian economy and employing about 60 % of the total population. It contributes about 25 % GDP and provides forward and backward linkage to industry and service sectors. The main objectives of SEZs policy is to create employment opportunities for introducing better facility, to improve lifestyle of rural area and develop industrial corridor of manufacturers and service sector, provide sustainable rural development in agriculture most particularly to farmers, poor people and landless people, to get employment opportunities, to increase income sources directly and indirectly. Overall attitude towards the SEZs project is to develop import-export services thereby attract foreign investors. The government provide such types of infrastructural facility for Special Economic Zone (SEZs) projects in order to start manufacturing units, to develop industrial sector and increase foreign direct investment for sustainable economic development to the backward region and rural area and thereby provide better facility through road, transportation, water, electricity, communication facility, health facility, education, and generation of employment opportunities.

4.2. Concept of Rural Development

Given the prevalence of poverty and the range of socio-economic factors that affect rural areas, poverty reduction in rural areas requires comprehensive treatment. For growth to be sustainable and its benefits to be equitably distributed, it should be broad-based, multi-sectoral and inclusive. In Maharashtra rural labour force is predominantly engaged in agriculture. Inclusive growth meant social protection and redistribution of income opportunities for the poorest within the short-span & time. Effective and sustainable poverty reduction requires improvements in productivity across both farm and off-farm employment activities. This requires supporting households with secure rights to land, access to markets and resources and an enabling environment for businesses and individuals.

4.2.1 Rural Development Objective before SEZs

Sustainable poverty reduction is achieved through broad-based growth across sectors in rural areas by improving land use, increasing the productivity of agriculture, enabling graduation from extreme poverty, and connecting rural communities to economic opportunity through improved infrastructure development of Special Economic zones. The main objectives for establishment of Special Economic Zone throughout country are; a) Generation of additional economic activity;

- a. Promotion of exports of goods and services particularly in the key sectors;
- b. Promotion of investment from domestic and foreign sources;
- c. Creation of employment opportunities;
- d. Development of infrastructure facilities;
- e. Generation of additional foreign exchange reserves;
- f. Promotion of transfer of technologies and skills;
- g. Development of deprived regions; and
- h. Raising the living standards of the people (Cling and Letilly, 2001; Lang, 2010; Madani, 2009). Ultimately, the aim of SEZs is to increase

standard of living of people and to initiate economic development (Milberg and Amengual, 2008).

4.2.2. Concept of Rural Development

The term ‘**rural development**’ is defined as the process of improving the quality of life and economic well-being of people living in rural areas. The primary objective of rural development is to reduce poverty in the rural areas. Targeting rural poverty reduction also means focusing on strengthening social cohesion and reducing inequality. Poverty reduction is a complex process and many factors will determine whether economic growth is associated with poverty reduction, such as the initial level of inequality, the composition of growth and how inequality changes over the period of growth. Given Maharashtra geographical and demographic composition, sustained economic growth requires large gains in poverty reduction and *vice versa*.

Rural Development emphasises the foundations and linkages of rural growth and the coordination between sectors such as land, infrastructure, agriculture and rural finance, while at the same time understanding the need for broader urban and rural linkages.

Off-farm job creation and large-scale investment to open up the economy are also essential. These aspects are addressed in the Productivity, Youth and Employment, Thematic Strategy and the Economic Transformation Thematic Strategy. The combination and coordination of these focus areas will catalyse rural development in Maharashtra.

Maharashtra is the second largest state in India both in terms of population and geographical area (3.08 lakh sq. km). It has a population of 11.24 crore (Census 2011) which is 9.3 % of the total population of India and is highly urbanised with 45.2 per cent people residing in urban areas.

The State has 35 districts which are divided into six revenue divisions viz. *Konkan, Pune, Nashik, Aurangabad, Amravati and Nagpur* for administrative purposes, with effective machinery for planning at the district level. For local self-governance in rural areas, there are 33 Zilla Parishads, 351

Panchayat Samitis and 27,873 Gram Panchayats. The urban areas are governed through 26 Municipal Corporations, 220 Municipal Councils, 12 Nagar Panchayats and seven Cantonment Boards. Mumbai, the capital of Maharashtra and the financial capital of India, houses the headquarters of most of the major corporate & financial institutions. India's main stock exchanges & capital market and commodity exchanges are located in Mumbai. The Gross State Domestic Product (GSDP) at current prices for 2012-13 is estimated at Rs 13, 23,768 crore and contributes 14.1 % to the GDP. Industry and Services sector both together contribute 89.1 % to the State's income while the contribution of Agriculture & Allied Activities sector is 10.9 %.

The State has 231 lakh hectares of land under cultivation and area under forest is 52.1 lakh hectares. Many irrigation projects are being implemented to improve irrigation. A watershed mission has been launched to ensure that soil and water conservation measures are implemented speedily in the un-irrigated area.

The Maharashtra state has maintained leadership position in the industrial sector in India. Presence of strong industrial sector remained backbone of the State's economic development. The industrial policy of the State has not remained static, but has undergone many changes during the course of time. In order to address the challenges of *globalisation*, *liberalisation* and *privatisation*, the State adopted first Industrial Policy in 1993, which was revisited in 1995, 2001 & 2006 and recently the new Industrial Policy of 2013 has been announced. Sectors which were exclusively in the public domain were opened to private sector, relaxation of norms for Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), favourable policies related to IT, BT, SEZ and Mega Projects, grape processing, etc. resulted in further development of the industrial sector in the State. Well-developed infrastructure, abundant natural resources, connectivity to all major areas, skilled manpower and quality education make Maharashtra an ideal destination for setting up of new industries. Besides Mumbai, Thane and Pune, second-tier towns like Nashik,

Aurangabad, Nagpur and Kolhapur have also emerged as industrial centers resulting in remarkable industrial growth in the State.

The researcher studied Sustainable Operation of Special Economic Zones in Maharashtra, *with Comparative Study of Marathwada and Konkan regions*. In 2005, the Government of India (GoI) introduced the Special Economic Zone (SEZ) Act, which changed the way India attracted foreign investors who wanted to utilize the country's natural and human capital. Impact of Special Economic Zones on Employment, Poverty and Human Development, The number of Special Economic Zones (SEZs) globally continues to expand. SEZs account for an increasing share of international trade flows and employ a growing number of workers world-wide. In the global economy, EPZs are viewed as an important if a second best policy instrument to promote industrialization, generate employment, and for regional development.

4.3. Indian Scenario of Special Economic Zone (SEZs): SEZs Units and Export Performance:

The central Government introduces SEZs Policy in 2005 and under the SEZs Act, 2005, granted SEZs Units in all States for achieving the main objectives of SEZs policy, for attracting foreign Direct Investment throughout the SEZs Units. The Government of Indian giving the approvals of SEZ in the form of Formal approval, In-Principal and Notified Approval under the SEZs Act, 2005 in all over the Indian.

4.3.1. Detail Fact Sheet and Approval position of SEZs in India:

The SEZs Policy / SEZs, Act, 2005, granted approval under this mechanism and maintained SEZ Policy in all State. But main Object of SEZs units is not fulfill to generate addition economic activity and Increase GDP, and generated employment opportunities to people. The Table No 4.5 Show detail potion of Special Economic Zone in India under the SEZ Act, 2005, 139 SEZs got notified and became functional. Thus, currently, there are 158 operational SEZs in the country. After the coming into force of the SEZ Act,

2005 on 10th February 2006, 588 formal approvals have been granted for setting up of Special Economic Zones, out of which 386 SEZs have been notified and are in various stages of operation (www.sezindia.nic.in referred on May, 2013).

Table No. 4.1:
No. of Formal, In-Principle, Notified SEZ, and Operational SEZs in India
(2006-13).

Year	Formal Approvals	In-principle approvals	Notified SEZ	Operational SEZs
2006-2007	386	-	149	-
2007-2008	439	138	201	-
2008-2009	568	144	315	90
2009-2010	573	147	347	104
2010-2011	580	155	374	130
2011-2012	583	45	380	154
2012-2013	588	49	386	158

(Source: Compiled from data base of SEZ India available in www.sezindia.nic.in referred, on May 2013)

Figure 4.1. Total No. of Formal, In-Principle, Notified & Operational SEZs Units in India

The above table indicates the figures of SEZs units granted the Formal Approval, In-Principle Approval, and Notified Approvals and total Operational SEZs during the period 2006 to 2013 as per the availability of secondary data. The Department of Commerce, giving permission for establishing SEZs units under the SEZs Act, 2005. In the year 2006-07, 386 Units were granted the Formal Approval, and 149 Units were notified.

In the year of 2007-08, increasing position of Formal approval is 439 and In-principal approval is 138, and 201 SEZs units are Notified. In the year of 2008-09, total Formal approvals units is 568, and In-principal approvals is 144 SEZs units, and 315 Units are Notified, and this year actually SEZs units in working his set up and his operational SEZs unit is 90. In the year 2009-10 increasing total no of formal approval SEZs units is that, 573, and In-principle units also increasing as comparatively in previous years that is 147 SEZs units, and Notified 347 SEZs units, and total operational units is 104. All the figures are increasing year to year in last year 2012-13 is total 588 formal approval SEZ units, and 49 is IN-principle, and 386 is granted Notified Approval, and 158 Units is working as operational units in overall India.

4.3.2. Export Performance Special Economic Zone (SEZs) in India

In the table no 4.1 is indicates total No of SEZs units speared in overall India, and it must know the export performance of this SEZs Units. The overall export position of SEZ units in India is embarked on the export oriented industrialization strategy, it can be observed that there is continuous increase in the exports from the SEZs units in India. The share of exports from SEZs in the total manufacturing exports has also been found increasing. The following table no 4.2 has given information about total Export Performance growth of SEZs Units in India. Exports from the functioning SEZs during the year of 2005-06 to 2013- 14 are as follows:

Table 4.2: Export Performance of SEZ units in India

Year	Exports		Growth over previous year
	Value in Rs. Crores	Billion USD	
2005-06	22,840	5.08	-
2006-07	34,615	7.69	52 %
2007-08	66,638	14.81	93 %
2008-09	99,689	22.15	50 %
2009-10	2,20,711	49.05	121 %
2010-11	3,15,868	70.19	143%
2011-12	3,64,478	81.00	15.39 %
2012-13	4,75,156	88.18	31%
2013-14	4,94,077	82.35	4%

Source: Compiled from data base of Ministry of Commerce, GoI available on www.commerce.nic.in referred, on May 2013(<http://www.sezindia.nic.in/about-ep.asp>)

Figure 4.2. Export Performance of SEZs Units in India

The above table indicates export performances Value in Rs. in Crores and Billion USD with Growth over previous year. In the year 2006-07 growth rate raised up to 52%, when export value is Rs.34, 615 /-crore, and USD value

of Export is 5.08 Billion. This kept increasing and in the year 2007-08 export value raised up to Rs.66, 638/- and growth rate was higher i.e. 93%. In the very next year there is 50% fall down in growth rate and export value rested at Rs.99, 989/- crores. And next year increasing and in the year 2009-10 export value raised up to Rs.2,20,711.39/- and growth rate was higher i.e. 121.40%. But, after 2012-13 export value is Rs 4, 75,156 and USD value is 88.18 But Growth rate is declined that is 31 %, and in the year of 2013-14 total export value is 4, 94,077 crores and USD export value is 82.35, and the growth rate declined that percentage is very negligence that is 4 %. Thus, after a thorough analysis of the above data one can observe a constant growth in export value and decline in growth rate.

4.4. The SEZs scenario of the Maharashtra State:

The state government announced SEZ policy in 2005 for making the objectives of Central Government and Central policy of SEZs. The State government granted the SEZs units under the SEZs Act, 2005, in Konkan, Marathwada, Vidharbha, and Western Maharashtra for generating additional economic activity and generated employment to people, and increasing FDI in state, for the purpose of increasing infrastructure facilities and increasing GDP of the State. The government of Maharashtra starting the procured of land acquisition in the selected areas in the states.

4.4.1. SEZs Units in Maharashtra State:

The Government of Maharashtra introducing SEZs State Policy for providing infrastructure facilities for Investor for that reasons state government call the proposal for interested foreign investor to establishment of SEZs Units and State government sending the all proposal for The Central Government receiving proposal for establishment SEZs Units under the SEZs Act, 2005, and Central Government approved and Notified SEZs proposal for the Maharashtra State. The table no 4.3 shows that detail position of SEZs units by the help of data generated as central government of India, thus information about position of received proposal, Approval & Notified proposal in details.

Table No 4.3
Detail Position of SEZs in Maharashtra: Received Proposal & Approved & Notified by Center Government

Year	No of Proposal Received	No. of Proposal Approved	No. of Proposal Notified
Up to Oct-2007	175	122 Formal-84, In principle-38	21
Up to Oct-2008	208	133 Formal-100, In principle-33	33
Up to Nov-2009	225	144 Formal-108, In principle-36 IT/ITES-59, Single Product-57, Multi Product-16, Multi service-12	58
Up to 31st Dec-2010	233	143 Formal-105, In principle-38	63
Up to 30th Nov-2011	233	116 Formal-82, In principle-24	63
Up to Nov-2012	234	124 Formal-104, In principle-20	64
Up to 31st Dec-2013	236	124 Formal-104, In principle-20	65

(Source: compiled from data base of Ministry of Commerce, GoI available on www.commerce.nic.in referred, on May 2013)

The researcher has collected secondary data from Ministry of Commerce, Government of India. This information is regarding state of Maharashtra has been received number of SEZs sanctioned Proposal by the central government and ministry of commerce received proposal of Special economic zone (SEZs) during the period 2007 to 2013. Table No 4.14 shows that information regarding No. of Proposal has been received and no of proposal approved by central government and no proposal notified during the period 2007 to 2013. In the year 2007 central government received 175 proposals and 122 proposal has been approved in the form of formal (84) and In-principle (38), and central government only notified 21 proposal in 2007 which first year for implantation SEZs policy in Maharashtra.

In the year 2008 central government received total 208 proposals and 133 proposals has been approved in the form of formal (100) and In-principle (33), and central government notified 33 proposal in 2008 which highest form 2007. In the year 2009 central government received 225 proposals and 144

proposals have been approved in the form of formal (108) and In-principle (36), and notified 58 proposal.

The Government of Maharashtra submitted 233 SEZ proposal to central and central government has Approved 143 proposals in the form of formal (105) and In-principle (38), and notified 63 proposal.

In the year 2011 central government has been received 233 proposals, but central government approved only 116 proposals in the form of formal (82) and In-principle (24), and notified 63 proposals.

In the year 2012 central government received total 234 proposals and 124 proposals has been approved in the form of formal (104) and In-principle (20), and central government notified total 64 proposal.

In the year 2012 central government has been received total 236 proposals and 124 proposals has been approved in the form of formal (104) and In-principle (20), and central government notified total 65 proposal. The researcher shows detail information about SEZs proposal in Maharashtra state in the form of received proposal, Approved proposal and Notified proposal during the period 2007-2013 in table no 4.3.

4.4.2. Land Acquisition for SEZs Projects in the State of Maharashtra:

The central government of India started SEZs policy in 2005 for industrial sector and for the proposed increasing FDI in India and attract Foreign Investor in Indian and government increased GDP and providing employment opportunities unemployed people. Due to that intention State government also starting SEZs policy in Maharashtra for taking global challenges and increasing infrastructure development, generating additional economic activity and creation employment in state. With that reasons Maharashtra government acquired land for starting SEZs Units in Maharashtra as following **Table No 4.4**, **Table No. 4.5** and **Table No. 4.6** Shows that information Area (ha) Approved for SEZs Project in Maharashtra, Area (ha) Notified for SEZs Units in Maharashtra, Area (ha) Executed For SEZs Units in

Maharashtra and total land acquired in regions wise Area hectares approved for Konkan western Maharashtra, Marathwada and Vidarbha in 2007 to 2013.

Table No.4.4:
Land Acquisition for Approved SEZs Project in Maharashtra
(Area in hectares)

Year	Regions				Total
	Konkan	Western Maharashtra	Marathwada	Vidarbha	
2007	29,668	10,228	3,980	6,004	49,880
2008	29,608	6,264	3,811	4,041	44,482
2009	29,996	6,715	3,771	4,910	45,392
2010	25,291	6,600	3,759	4,316	39,966
2011	12,769	4,235	896	4,316	22,216
2012	15,432	6,545	3,396	4,316	29,689
2013	15,432	6,545	3,396	4,316	29,689

(Source: compiled from data base of Ministry of Commerce, GoI available on www.commerce.nic.in referred, on May 2013)

Table No 4.4. Shows that information Area (ha) approved for SEZs Units in Maharashtra which is divided into four divisions such as Konkan, Western Maharashtra, Marathwada, and Vidarbha during the years 2007 to 2013. It is initial stage for acquired land for SEZs project and central government approved of the overall Area (ha) for developing SEZs Units in Maharashtra for attracting foreign direct investor get ready to start his project in the regions. The Central Government of Indian and Ministry of Commerce and Government of Maharashtra acquired total land for 2007 is 49,880 Area (ha), 2008 is 44,482 Area (ha), 2009 is 45,392 Area (ha), 2010 is 39,966 Area (ha), 2011 is 22,216 Area (ha), 2012 is 29,689 Area (ha), and last year 2013 is 29,689 Area (ha). It becomes where that land acquired were SEZs is decrease due to the opposing by farmer.

Table No.4.5:
Land Notified for SEZs Units in Maharashtra (Area in hectares)

Year	Regions				Total
	Konkan	Western Maharashtra	Marathwada	Vidarbha	
2007	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a
2008	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a
2009	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a
2010	2,407	3,469	786	3,206	9,868
2011	2,407	3,469	786	3,206	9,868
2012	2,407	3,778	786	3,206	10,177
2013	2,418	4,778	786	3,206	10,188

(Source: compiled from data base of Ministry of Commerce, GoI available on www.commerce.nic.in referred, on May 2013)

Table No 4.5 shows that information total Notified land for SEZs Units in Maharashtra and particularly divided in four divisions: Konkan, Western Maharashtra, Marathwada, and Vidarbha during the year 2007 to 2013. The central Government Notified Acquired land for SEZs Units heights details in above table no 4.5.

Table No.4.6
Land Executed for SEZs Units in Maharashtra (Area in hectares)

Year	Regions				Total
	Konkan	Western Maharashtra	Marathwada	Vidarbha	
2012	192	412	118	1,699	2,421
2013	192	412	225	1,699	2,528

(Source: compiled from data base of Ministry of Commerce, GoI available on www.commerce.nic.in referred, on May 2013)

Table no 4.6 shows that information **Land Executed for SEZs Units** in Maharashtra including sub-division of Konkan. Western Maharashtra, Marathwada and Vidarbha. In the year 2012 to 2013 the central and state

Government executed for SEZs units in Maharashtra. It is diversification of SEZ policy and interest of investor government take the decision to execute SEZs Units in Maharashtra in last two years.

4.5. Investment of SEZs Project in Maharashtra State for Rural Development:

The state government and central government developed infrastructure facilities of SEZs units to attract Foreign Investor and Entrepreneurs for the setup of industry in SEZs units. The Government invest the large amount of Investment for land acquisition and infrastructure development of SEZs project in Maharashtra.

4.5.1. Approved Proposed Investment of SEZs in Maharashtra:

The Table No.4.7 shows figures of approved proposed investment of Special Economic Zones (SEZs) in Konkan, Marathwada, Vidarbha, and Western Maharashtra, in the State of Maharashtra. The approved proposed investment in the year 2007-2013 as follows.

**Table No.4.7:
Details of Approved Proposed Investment of SEZs in Maharashtra
(Rs.Crore)**

Year	Regions				Total
	Konkan	Western Maharashtra	Marathwada	Vidarbha	
2007	95,296	22,607	4,265	10,409	1,32,578
2008	1,10,581	21,668	4,041	12,432	1,48,722
2009	1,14,406	57,202	4,962	12,578	1,89,148
2010	1,25,422	48,116	3,855	11,594	1,88,987
2011	77,974	43,614	2,845	11,595	1,36,028
2012	82,811	45,725	3,655	11,595	1,43,789
2013	82,814	45,725	3,655	11,595	1,43,789

(Source: compiled from data base of Ministry of Commerce, GoI available on www.commerce.nic.in referred, on May 2013)

The above table indicates the total figures of approved investment. In the year of 2007 approved Investment is Rs. 1, 32,578 crore. In the year 2008 total investment is Rs.1, 48,722 Crore. In the year, 2009 total investment of Rs.1, 89,148 crors, from Konkan regions of Rs.1, 14,406 (crore). Western Maharashtra it is Rs.57, 202. Marathwada region approved investment is Rs.4, 962, and Vidarbha region approved investment is Rs.12, 578. In the year of 2010 Konkan region approved investment is Rs.1, 25,422. Western Maharashtra approved Investment is Rs. 48,116. Marathwada region approved investment is Rs.3, 855, and Vidarbha region it is Rs. 11,594. The total of that is Rs.1, 88,987. In the year of 2011 to 2013 this investment is constant there will be no changes as per the above table and source of information. These are all approved investment for the physical and infrastructure development of SEZs units in Marathwada and Konkan regions. People of projected areas get direct and indirect employment and help through rural development of SEZs.

4.6. Exports Performance of SEZs in Maharashtra

The Maharashtra state represents highest percentage of Exports in compare to other part of India. The zone started operating in the month of Sept. 1974 with five units commencing exports. The main products exported from the State are gems & jewellery, software, textiles, readymade garments, cotton yarn, metal & metal products, agro-based products, engineering items, drugs & pharmaceuticals and plastic & plastic items. To recognise the efforts put up by the exporters and to boost the exports, the State is taking initiatives like giving awards based on export performance and implementing space rent subsidy scheme for small scale industries for participation in international exhibitions. Exports from the following statement gives the year-wise figures of actual exports, growth rate and number of units in production during the last five year in state of Maharashtra are given in Table 4.8.

**Table No 4.8:
Export Performance of SEZs in Maharashtra**

Year	Export (Rs. in Crores)	Growth in %	No. of Units in Production
2007-08	11,265	(-) 6.47%	245
2008-09	10,079	(-) 10.53%	264
2009-10	9,995	(-) 0.83%	287
2010-11	11,582	15.88%	311
2011-12	12,608	8.85%	319
2012-13	14,399	14.20%	336
2013-14	16,989	17.99%	336

(Source: compiled from data base of Ministry of Commerce, GoI available on www.commerce.nic.in referred, on May 2013)

Figure 4.3. Growth Rate Export Performance of SEZs in Maharashtra

Table no 4.8 highlights the information based on secondary source and available of secondary data of Export Performance of SEZ in Maharashtra including Konkan, Marathwada, Vidharbha and Western Maharashtra, particularly the overall export of state of Maharashtra SEZ. The Table No 4.8 highlights information regarding export performance of SEZs in Maharashtra. The data represents year-wise figures of actual exports, growth rate and number of units in production during the last five year.

In the year of 2007-2008 total export is Rs. 11,265 (Rs in crore) respective growth percentage is very less in terms of negative i.e. (-) 6.4 % in participation of 245 units in production activity in state of Maharashtra. In the year of 2008-09 SEZ project for Export is Rs 10,079 (corore) and the respective Growth is (-)10.53 % which is comparatively high in the year of 2007-08 that total 264 units is participation in production activities. In the year of 2009-10, total Export is Rs.9995 (in Crores) and there SEZ project for Export Rs 10,079 (corore) and the respective Growth is (-)10.53 % which is comparatively high in the year of 2007-08 that total 264 units is participation in production activities.

4.7. Land use for Special economic zones (SEZs) and Rural Development:

The Maharashtra State, total 336 SEZs Units out of which already been notified and the land acquired is estimated to be around 40,000 hectares, which is predominantly agricultural and typically multi cropped providing close to one metric ton of food grain (Hiremath,2007). If SEZs are seen to be successful in the future and if more cultivated land is acquired, this way affect country's food security. The issues regarding SEZs vis-à-vis agricultural land use and rural development are of major concern today and need to be discussed in a food, national and rural livelihood security context.

4.7.1. Land use for Rural Development (Non-Agriculture): Issues

Many rural infrastructure programs like rural connectivity, housing, sanitation and health, drinking water, rural institutions etc., are land based activities and need land, preferably non-agricultural and low or no productive land. The decision for allocation of land for such basic needs have to be taken at PRI level. In view of locally existing sociopolitical-economic dynamics, taking such decisions in a bottom up and comprehensive manner needs fairly good understanding of the land resources and their planning for multifarious activities. Thus there is a need to develop information on land resources as database at local level in a understandable manner

4.7.2. Impact of land Acquisition for Rural Development in Konkan and Marathwada Regions:

The land, which has been acquired by SEZs projects, is from agricultural areas in Konkan and Marathwada region, and people are depending firm and Agro base activity for fulfillment of their livelihood and social needs. But, it is very reverse position for SEZs projects.

The development of SEZs units in Konkan region and Marathwada region for sustainable rural development primarily need to acquire land for establishment SEZ units. In both the region without land it is not possible to develop infrastructure for industrial units and road, transportation, communication, employment for directly and indirectly for the people and fertile land being used by SEZ project. Is direct benefit to farmer and project affected person getting good health and educational facility and water, electricity, roads and employment in SEZs units or help of his own farm and starting small business nearest by SEZs Projected area. Table no 4.9 shows that region wise land acquired for SEZs units (Area in Hectare) during the years 2007 to 2013.

**Table No.4.9
Land Acquired for SEZs units (Area in Hectare)**

Year	Konkan Regions	Marathwada Regions	Total
2007	29,668	3,980	33,648
2008	29,608	3,811	33,419
2009	29,996	3,771	33,767
2010	25,291	3,759	29,050
2011	12,769	896	13,665
2012	15,432	3,396	18,828
2013	15,432	3,396	18,828

(Source: compiled from data base of Ministry of Commerce, GoI available on www.commerce.nic.in referred, on May 2013 & Statistics Department GoM, 2013)

In the year of 2007, total land acquired for the SEZs project in Konkan and Marathwada regions is 33,674 area in hectares out of whic in Konkan

regions is total land is 29,669 hectare and Marathwada region is total land acquired for SEZS project is 3,980 hectare.

In the year 2008, total land acquired for the SEZs project Konkan and Marathwada regions is 33,419 hectares out of which in Konkan regions has the total land acquisition is 29,608 hectares and Marathwada region the total land acquired for SEZs project is 3,811 hectares. In the year of 2009, 2010 one witnesses some little changes in the total land acquired for the SEZs project in Konkan and Marathwada regions. But in the year of 2012 some farmers opposed and they are starting Anti-struggle for saving their land there so change in the parameters of land acquisition during this year land acquisition Konkan region is 12,769 hectares and Marathwada region it is 896 hectares.

In the year of 2012, and 2013 there is same position of total land acquired for the SEZs project in Konkan and Marathwada regions which is 18,828 area in hectares out of which in Konkan regions the total acquired land is 15,432 hectare and Marathwada region the total acquired land for SEZS project is 3,396 hectares. The researchers analysis the above figures as per collected in source of secondary information.

It is very negative impact of the both regions of Konkan and Marathwada, the farmers facing the socio-economic problems of their livelihoods and employment factor for the fulfillment of basic needs. Because they are depending on Agriculture sector. Their opinions are that SEZs are not benefits for Rural Development. The rural economy is depending on Agriculture and Allied Sector and 70 % peoples are depending on Farming.

4.8. SEZs and Employment Generation in Rural Development

The SEZs are playing an important role for the employment generation, therefore, the present chapter focuses on SEZs and Rural development. The research question discussed in this chapter is whether SEZs have contributed towards employment generation, export promotion and attracting investment and achieving reality of rural development. How far these SEZs have been successful in generating employment for the affected people and nearest

projected areas in Konkan and Marathwada regions are thoroughly export in the said chapter.

4.8.1. Employment Generation

SEZs have been enclaves which offer labour friendly policies to the investors, attracting them to make investments in the Zone. Since most of the activities in the Zone are labour-intensive in nature, it offers direct employment to a number of persons. Table 4.8 shows the direct employment generated by the SEZs in Maharashtra .There has been an impressive expansion in employment opportunities in SEZ especially after the SEZ Act, 2005. The main objective of SEZs is the Creation of employment opportunities to the people into this last.

Employment generation has been the chief objective behind the development of these SEZs. SEZs are viewed as highly effective tools for job generation. The empirical evaluation shows that the creation of employment is frequently the main source of benefit for the host economy (Jenkins et al., 1998). World-wide direct employment in the SEZs has risen sharply in the last two decades from less than two million during 1986 to 66 million in 2006 (ILO, 2007). The employment effect of SEZs is analyzed through the following three channels: *1. Direct Employment Generation.2. Indirect Employment Generation. 3. Women Employment Generation.*

4.8.2. Direct Employment Generation:

Such types of employment are generated in the SEZs Units for the requirement of labours, technicians, Operators, Trainees, and Manages in sift wise. In so far as SEZs comprise labour-intensive activities, enterprises in SEZs constitute, a priori, a significant source of new employment. Due to the availability of labour at low wages, developing countries generally attract investment into simple processing labour intensive industries. This increases the demand for unskilled labour within the zone. Shift towards higher value added activities as SEZs grow, might increase demand for skilled labour also.

The following **table No. 4.10** gives information about approved proposed employment in Konkan and Marathwada Regions, It also gives information about Notified Proposed Employment in in Konkan and Marathwada Regions. It gives information about Executed Proposed Employment in Konkan and Marathwada Regions. All Konkan and Marathwada region is specially highlighted in the following tables.

The table No 4.10 indicates the approved proposed employment of Special Economic Zones in Maharashtra state with its four region: Konkan, Western Maharashtra, Marathwada, and Vidarbha. This all information collected from secondary source and analysed the regions wise and these all information during year of 2007 to 2013. In the year of 2007 approved proposed employment in Western Maharashtra is, 10.73 lakh, and Vidarbha is 5.84 lakh, and approved proposed employment in Konkan region is 35.36 lakh, and approved proposed employment in Marathwada region is 1.56 lakh.

Table No.4.10
Approved Proposed Employment of SEZs in Maharashtra
(in lakh)

Year	Regions				Total
	Konkan	Western Maharashtra	Marathwada	Vidarbha	
2007	35.36	10.73	1.56	5.84	53.48
2008	42.05	11.67	1.56	5.76	61.04
2009	43.58	14.33	1.53	5.81	65.25
2010	43.25	12.93	1.52	5.86	63.56
2011	33.56	11.78	1.15	5.85	52.34
2012	35.56	12.93	1.37	5.86	55.72
2013	35.56	7.42	1.37	5.86	55.72

(Source: compiled from data base of Ministry of Commerce, GoI available on www.commerce.nic.in referred, on May 2013 & Statistics Department GoM, 2013)

In the year of 2008 approved proposed employment in Western Maharashtra is 11.67 lakh, and Vidarbha is 5.76 lakh, and approved proposed employment in Konkan region is 42.05 lakh, and approved proposed

employment in Marathwada region is 1.56 lakh. In the year of 2009 approved proposed employment in Western Maharashtra is 14.33 lakh, and Vidarbha is 5.81 lakh., and approved proposed employment in Konkan region is 43.58 lakh., and approved proposed employment in Marathwada region is that 1.52 lakh.

In the year 2010 approved proposed employment in Western Maharashtra is 12.93 lakh, and Vidarbha is 5.86 lakh, and approved proposed employment in Konkan region is 43.25 lakh, and approved proposed employment in Marathwada region is 1.52 lakh.

In the year 2011 approved proposed employment in Western Maharashtra is 11.78 lakh, and Vidarbha is 5.85 lakh, and approved proposed employment in Konkan region is that 33.35 lakh, approved proposed employment in Marathwada region is 1.35 lakh. In the year of 2012 approved proposed employment in Western Maharashtra is 12.93 lakh, and Vidarbha it is 5.86 lakh., and approved proposed employment in Konkan region is that 35.56 lakh., and approved proposed employment in Marathwada region is that 1.37 lakh.

Figure 4.4. Approved Proposed Employments of SEZs in Konkan & Marathwada Regions

In the year 2013 approved proposed employment in Western Maharashtra is 7.42 lakh, and Vidarbha is 5.86 lakh, and approved proposed

employment in Konkan region is 35.36 lakh, and approved proposed employment in Marathwada region is 1.37 lakh.

The Table No.4.11 gives the information about Notified proposed employment under the SEZs Act, 2005. The direct employment generated in Konkan, Western Maharashtra, Marathwada, and Vidarbha regions in the State of Maharashtra as per available source of secondary information for the year 2007 to 2013.

Table No.4.11
Details of Notified Proposed Employment of SEZs in Maharashtra
(in lakh)

Year	Regions				Total
	Konkan	Western Maharashtra	Marathwada	Vidarbha	
2007	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a
2008	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a
2009	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a	n.a
2010	9.45	6.72	0.31	4.12	20.80
2011	9.45	6.72	0.31	4.32	20.80
2012	9.45	7.42	0.31	4.32	21.50
2013	9.54	7.42	0.31	4.32	21.59

(Source: compiled from data base of Ministry of Commerce, GoI available on www.commerce.nic.in referred, on May 2013 & Statistics Department GoM, 2013)

During the year of 2007 to 2009 all SEZ project are under development process for physical infrastructure and due to this reasons there was no any direct employment and notified proposed employment. The years 2007, 2008, and 2009 are not applicable for all SEZs Units in Konkan, Western Maharashtra, Marathwada, and Vidharbha in the state. But, Notified Proposed employment is generated and for skill and unskilled employment requirement in the year of 2011 notified proposed direct employment in Western Maharashtra is that, 6.72 lakh, and Vidarbha is 4.11 lakh., and approved proposed employment in Konkan region is 9.45 lakh., and approved proposed employment in Marathwada region is 0.31 lakh.

In the year 2012, and 2013 all figures are indicated which are constant. Total notified employment in state was 21, 69 lakh, there is not much more changes, and region wise notified proposed direct employment in Western Maharashtra is 7.42 lakh, and Vidarbha is 4.32 lakh., and approved proposed employment in Konkan region is 9.45 lakh., and approved proposed employment in Marathwada region is 0.31 lakh, as notified in the table no.4.11.

The table no 4.12 shows the information about Executed proposed direct employment under the SEZs Units and projected areas of Konkan, Western Maharashtra, Marathwada, and Vidharbha are mentioned in the following tables:

Table No.4.12
Details of Executed Proposed Employment of SEZs in Maharashtra
(in Lakh)

Year	Regions				Total
	Konkan	Western Maharashtra	Marathwada	Vidarbha	
2012	1.34	3.50	0.05	3.61	8.50
2013	1.34	3.50	0.15	3.61	8.60

(Source: compiled from data base of Statistics Department GoM, 2013, & Ministry of Commerce, GoI available on www.commerce.nic.in referred, on May 2013 &)

Figure 4.5. Executed Proposed Employment of SEZs Units in Konkan & Marathwada Regions

The above table no 4.12 highlights the information about direct employment generated for the executed proposed employment in SEZs units in, Konkan, Western Maharashtra, Marathwada and Vidharbha regions in the state. In the year 2012, and 2013, the total executed proposed employment generated is 8.50 lakhs out of them in Konkan region is executed employment is same, in both the year is 1.34, and Western Maharashtra is 3.50 lakh, and Marathwada region in the both year is same which is 0.15 lakh, and Vidharbha region in the both year 2012, and 2013 is the figures are same that is 3.61 lakh.

4.8.3. Indirect employment generation SEZ for Rural Development:

The main objectives to establishment of Special Economic Zones throughout country create employment opportunities and Development of Infrastructure facilities in the projected Areas, and raising the living standers of the peoples. In any Project or industries come in Rural ares for starting manufacturing sector defiantly peoples getting indirect employment.

The indirect effect is manifested as ancillary employment opportunities generated in sectors of the economy affected by the operations of the SEZ. These include, transport, communication, automobile, civil aviation, shipping, tourism, hospitality, packaging, banking, and insurance. Employment opportunities are, thus generated for both unskilled and skilled labour.

4.8.4. Indirect Employment Generation

The indirect employment effect has appeared as ancillary employment opportunities generated in sectors of the economy affected by the operations of the SEZ. These include transport, communication, automobile, civil aviation, shipping, tourism, hospitality, packaging, banking, insurance, etc. Employment opportunities are thus generated for both unskilled and skilled labour. The indirect employment effect of SEZs depends upon backward and forward linkage of the SEZ industry with local supplies of raw materials and other required inputs and the success of SEZs in attracting investment. The creation of backward linkages with the expansion of investment in zones would certainly help to generate more indirect employment (Aggarwal, 2007).

4.8.5. Women Employment Generation: Global Scenario

Women dominate the work-force in SEZs in most developing countries. For instance, in Philippines, the share of women workers in total SEZ work-force was 74 % in 1980. It remained the same in 1994. In Korea, it was 70 % in 1990. In Mexico, it was as high as 77.4 % in 1981. It declined to 60 % in 1995. In Dominican Republic, it was 60 % in 1995. In Bangladesh and Sri Lanka it was above 70 % (Aggarwal 2007). Madani (1999) reported that a 1981 survey in the Dominican Republic found that SEZ wages were the main source of income for 38 % of women working in these zones, and almost half of them were single, divorced or widows. ILO (1998) survey reported that in Guatemala zones were the sole source of income for 45 % of women workers and in Honduras zones were the main source of income for 22 % of women.

But there are several reports of exploitation of women in SEZs. A vast majority of workers in SEZ firms are young women aged between 16-25 years (Kreye et al., 1987). It is found that women are paid less than men for similar jobs (Jahan, 2003; Bhattacharya and Rahman, 1999) and are subjected to sexual harassment and violence.

4.8.6. Employment for Women

Evidence suggests that women's share in total employment of SEZs is substantially higher than both the economy as a whole as well as the manufacturing sector outside the SEZs (Kusago and Tzannatos, 1998). Women workers are considered more disciplined and hard working. It is found that employers prefer female workers to male workers in the belief that manual dexterity, greater discipline and patience make women more suitable for the unskilled and semi-skilled activities carried out in the zones. Besides, they are less likely to exert pressure for high wages and better working conditions. Majority of women are young, single and come from rural and poor backgrounds. SEZ employment can be said to afford them an independent source of income that would otherwise have been denied. SEZs are thus expected to contribute substantially to the empowerment of women (Madani

1999). Increase in employment opportunities has empowered women and made them more independent, improved their relative shares and bargaining power within household (Heyzer, 1988; Dunn, 1994; Joeques and Weston, 1995; and Kibria, 1995).

4.9. Influence of SEZs on Infrastructure Development

SEZs in India, as elsewhere, thrive on infrastructure directly or indirectly created. Infrastructure is essential for establishment and successful operation of businesses. For SEZs, the importance of infrastructure is even greater. The SEZ Act 2005 has increased awareness among the state governments as well as local bodies about the need to invest in adequate and strong infrastructure to support globally competitive economic activities. Infrastructure related to SEZs are of two types: that facilitating the internal functioning of SEZs (power generation plants and distribution network, internal water supply, sanitation and sewerage, internal roads etc.) with direct implications for productivity; and the other, linking SEZs with the non-SEZ world through a supply chain (railway tracks, roads and bridges, airport facilities, telephone lines and telecom network).

The success achieved by a number of SEZ units in India is a clear indication that these have been quite successful in influencing creation of adequate infrastructure in their respective areas. The infrastructure created for facilitating the successful operation of the SEZs has in all cases led the establishment of memorandum of understanding (MoU) between two or more business centres and in the process created infrastructure for the remote or previously inaccessible areas falling in between the two centres. These units have also contributed to infrastructure development in the surrounding areas.

4.9.1. Rural Development and Infrastructure Aspects of SEZs

The data collection for respondents and project affected people due to SEZs, and the information about SEZs projects or SEZ policy can provides physical infrastructure development for the rural development. The information and opinion of infrastructure dependence in Konkan and Marathwada Regions

presented in detail. This infrastructure issues are discussed in the responded and collected for opinion for both region, which for the development for Road, Water Facility, Power & Electricity, Sanitations, Transportations facilities, technologies, and educational facility, and health facilities etc., are thus SEZs provide such types of infrastructure facilities for Rural areas which is it questionable remarks.

The Table No 4.13 gives the information of whether the SEZs Project Provide Road and Transportation facilities for development of affected villages for maintaining aspect of rural development.

Table No.4.13.
Does the SEZs Provide Rode and Transportation facility for development of village

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total Average %
		Respondents	Respondents	
1	Yes	42	20	62
2	No	68	80	148
	Total	100	100	200

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2013-14)

Figure 4.6. Opinion of Respondents for SEZs provide Road & Transportation Facility for development of Villages

Responses in the above table indicate disillusion experienced by the village people after the establishment of SEZ projects. When enquired about

the basic amenities such as road and transport facility provided by SEZ in the vicinity, 148 respondents from Konkan and Marathwada region reported negative response. In all 62 respondents expressed their satisfaction over the facilities in the nearby villages. It can be concluded that SEZs have been neglecting their responsibilities towards the nearby areas.

The Table No 4.14 given the information whether SEZ s Provide Water for Rural people or village of affected villages for maintaining aspect of rural development.

Table No.4.14.
SEZ s Provide Water for Rural people or village

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total Average %
		Respondents	Respondents	
1	Yes	49	19	68
2	No	51	81	132
Total		100	100	200

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2013-14)

Figure 4.7. SEZs Provide Water Facility for Affected Villages

Supply of basic amenities such as water, road and electricity in rural areas needed utmost attention by the government agencies. Since, the SEZs are to be established in the rural area, it is expected that it should attend the rural problems too. Hence, in the survey the researcher found that SEZs are neglecting their responsibilities toward society. Majority of the respondents (132) expressed their concern over supply of water for rural people and

villages. However, 68 respondents in Konkan and Marathwada region reported their positive response. Konkan region 49 respondents stated their positive response regarding availability of water due course of establishment of SEZs. In contrast, only 19 respondents expressed satisfaction over the SEZs projects in Marathwada region.

The Table No 4.15 gives the information about, whether the SEZ Project provide electricity facility in the affected villages for maintaining aspect of rural development.

Table No.4.15.
Does the SEZ Project provide electricity facility in the village

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total
		Respondents	Respondents	
1	Yes	52	18	70
2	No	48	82	130
Total		100	100	200

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2013-14)

Figure 4.8. Does the SEZ Project Provide electricity facility in village

During the field survey it was observed that in the vicinity of MIDC area was surrounded by slums and residential localities. Most of the households live in scarcity of minimum infrastructure and amenities by the government agencies. It came to know that the households were in need of urgent electrification facility on street and in houses. In Konkan region, 52 households mentioned that they are provided with electricity facility as compared to lowest

18 households in Marathwada region. Thus, the government should look into the matter in order to justify distribution of electric facility to the 130 respondents i.e. 48 in Konkan and 82 Marathwada region households around the SEZs locality.

The Table No 4.16 given the information about, whether the SEZ project provide education facility to affected villages for maintaining aspect of rural development.

Table No.4.16.
Does the SEZ project provide education facility to affected villagers

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total
		Respondents	Respondents	
1	Yes	38	15	53
2	No	62	85	147
Total		100	100	200

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2013-14)

Figure 4.9. Does the SEZ project provide education facility to affected villagers

Education is the primary requisite in order to generate skilled man power. However, sole responsibility to educate the masses is left with the government instead of industrialists who direly needed skilled workforce to carry out complex processes in factories and offices. In the survey, an attempt was made to assess the responsibility, whether, carried out by SEZ units to nurture talent among local inhabitants to get them involved in production processes in factories. When asked about the educational facility, if any, provided by the SEZs units in the locality, in Konkan region, only 38

respondents gave positive reply whereas maximum i.e. 68 of them told absence of any such institution run by the factory owners. Similarly in Marathwada region, around 85 respondents had no idea about any educational unit running in the vicinity that can harness the local talent to meet future man power needs to the SEZs. It becomes clear that SEZ policy doesn't have any responsibility towards educating the future generation that would meet the demands of work-force in near future.

The Table No 4.17 gives the information about, whether the SEZs provide Communications and Technology for Villages affected villages for maintaining aspect of rural development

Table No.4.17.
Does the SEZs provide Communications and Technology for Villages

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total
		Respondents	Respondents	
1	Yes	36	27	63
2	No	64	73	147
	Total	100	100	200

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2013-14)

Figure 4.10. Does the SEZs provide Communications and Technology for Villages

The field survey attempted to assess the facilities provided by the SEZs units to the local inhabitants who in exchange of their land and labour forsook their land and assets. Since the inhabitants juxtaposed to techno-savvy area it is also expected that the locals too should get minimum benefits of any such

telecommunication facility. When asked to the respondents about any such facility, in Konkan region only 36 respondents confirmed the availability of telecommunication supported by SEZs as compared to 27 least number of respondents in Marathwada region. In contrast, maximum 64 and 73 respondents, in Konkan and Marathwada region respectively, gave negative reply to the question asked for any telecommunication facility made available by SEZs in the area.

The developer and State Government should take a long term view for developing infrastructure facilities within the Zone, particularly in case of multi-sector SEZs. The guidelines for development of Special Economic Zones are indicated overall guidelines for development of SEZs units, and telecommunications, Housing, and Mass Transportation for side and Physical infrastructure development for External Connectivity, Water Supply, Drainage, Sewerage, Solid Waste Management, and Power Supply, medical & Food Facilities, Training and Manpower, in SEZs Units and SEZs project being centres for economic activity, will have the influence of developing township around affected areas for the and Regional Development.

Concluding Remarks

India was the first country in Asia to set up an EPZ and has keenly pursued the policy of establishing EPZs/SEZs to further its economic policy objectives. The present study has shown that the SEZs and Rural Development in terms of exports, employment, investments and infrastructure development of selected area of SEZs which benefited socially and economically to the people as land owners and entrepreneurs in economic development. The social costs of human displacement and the economic costs of land acquisition have been observed to far outweigh the benefits that have accrued from the policy. Indeed, an Expert Group Report released by the Planning Commission appears to call into question the benefits of SEZs: Land acquisition for Special Economic Zones (SEZ) has given rise to widespread protest in various parts of the country. Large tracts of land are being acquired across the country for this

purpose which has ransacked common life. A rural development is very important achievement of generation of greater economic activity and employment through the establishment of SEZs, a comprehensive Special Economic Zones Act, 2005, was introduced. The main objectives of the SEZ Act are: a) Generation of additional economic activity b) Promotion of exports of goods and services c) Promotion of investment from domestic and foreign sources d) Creation of employment opportunities e) Development of infrastructure facilities. These objectives help rural development of SEZs project as well as economical and rural development of SEZs.

The present chapter has dealt with important aspects of Special Economic Zones (SEZs) and Rural Development. The government of India (GoI) introduced a Special Economic Zones (SEZ) Policy. The aim of the Policy is to promote export oriented industrial and economic development for the proponents of rapid development of India. SEZs are considered as engines of high economic growth. The main objectives of SEZs policy is to create employment opportunities for introducing better facility, to improve lifestyle of rural area and develop industrial corridor of manufacturers and service sector, to provide sustainable rural development in agriculture most particularly to farmers, poor people and landless people, to get employment opportunities, to increase income sources directly and indirectly. Overall attitude towards the SEZs project is to develop import-export services thereby attract foreign investors. The government provides such types of infrastructural facility for Special Economic Zones (SEZs) projects in order to start manufacturing units, to develop industrial sector and increase foreign direct investment for sustainable economic development to the backward region and rural area and thereby provide better facility through road, transportation, water, electricity, communication facility, health facility, education, and generation of employment opportunities.

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CHAPTER - VI

DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

Introduction

Chapter sixth is the subject matter of overall Data Collection and analysis of the data. It give the details about the primary data interpretation and secondary data. Government of India passed Special Economic Zone Policy Act in the year 2005. As proposed, the Act is aimed at promoting export oriented industrial economic development in India. As of now, 1064 SEZs have received approval for setting up industrial zones across the country to carry out the objectives laid out in the Act. These SEZs are, on the one side, meant for promoting economic growth, and on the other hand, they have attracted pervasive discontent amongst farmers, workers and common people. Due to enactment of SEZs policy, many of the affected people in and around SEZ area have to relocate their homes, loose land assets and thus lead a completely disturbed life. Indeed, the SEZ Policy has raised subsidiary fundamental questions confronted by general public. Hence it is need of the hour to address the socio-economic impact on the general public in Marathwada and Konkan regions.

The present chapter deals with the data analysis and interpretation of responses collected during the field survey based on the scheduled questionnaire. The data acquired primarily focusses on livelihood patterns of affected people who lost their land assets and employment resources. This study uncovers the impact of the SEZ Act in Marathwada and Konkan Region of Maharashtra.

The analysis and interpretation is based on field survey undertaken in SEZs units in study area. For the purpose, over 200 respondents, 100 from each of the regions, including male and female workers, farmers, landowners, were selected who are directly and indirectly affected in SEZ units operational

in the regions. It has been observed that majority of the farmers and general public in Navi Mumbai, Raigad, Ratnagiri of **Konkan region and Nanded, Latur, and Aurangabad** in Marathwada region staged protest against SEZ projects in the respective regions. This chapter brings forth factual reasons behind discontent among public who have been alleging irregularities in implementation of Labour Laws, Industrial Acts to promote SEZ policy. Thus, an honest attempt has been undertaken to highlight socio-economic aspects such as displacement issues, rehabilitation and resettlement of project affected people, rural development, industrial and infrastructural development, and urbanization in Konkan and Marathwada regions, in particular, as proposed to be addressed through SEZ policy.

Gender Wise Respondents in SEZ Units:

The data collected from gender-wise respondents in projected area of SEZ in Konkan and Marathwada Regions the data give the following Table No.6.1.

Table No. 6.1

Gender-Wise Distribution of the Deployment in SEZs Units

Sr. No.	Selected Region	Gender		Total	Percentage		Total
		Male	Female		Male	Female	
1	Konkan	85	15	100	85%	15%	100
2	Marathwada	90	10	100	90%	10%	100
Total		175	25	200	175 %	25 %	200

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.1. Gender-Wise Respondents of Konkan & Marathwada Regions

The above table shows gender wise distribution of man power deployed in SEZs in the target area. In each of the Region, 100 respondents were selected out of which 85 were male and 15 were female in Konkan region. Similarly, in Marathwada region, 90 male, 10 female respondents' noted their response about SEZ in the region. Thus, the SEZ units deployed 90% of the male & 10% female population. In both the Region, the researcher observed that overall 175 male respondents and 25 female respondents were affected by the SEZs projects in selected in villages and talukas.

Age group of Respondents in Konkan and Marathwada Region:

The Age factors of the respondents is very important to find out the appropriate opinion about the awareness and depth of situation and understanding the problems and prospects of SEZs in their areas. The data given from the age group of respondent in Konkan and Marathwada regions in the following table No. 6.2.

Table No. 6.2
Age Group of Respondents in the SEZ areas

Sr. No.	Konkan Region			Marathwada Region		
	Age Group	No of Respondent	Percent (%)	Age Group	No of Respondent	Percent %
1	15-24	24	24	15-19	30	30
2	25-34	32	32	20-24	28	28
3	35-45	24	24	25-29	23	23
4	Above 45	20	20	Above 45	19	19
Total		100	100	Total	100	100

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.2. Age Group of Respondents

Further, the number of workers (20) in the age group of 35-45 years was equal (24%) to that of 15-24 age group. Similarly, 20 respondents were in the age group of above 45 years who registered the adverse impact of SEZ in Navi Mumbai, Raigad, Ratnagiri and Thane districts of Konkan region.

On the same lines it was worth mentioning that the workers in the age group of 15-19 years were higher (30%) in number as compared to the age group of 20-24 years (28%). Further, the number of workers in the age group of 25-29 years was little higher (23%) to that of age group above 45 years i.e. (19%) respondents, who registered the socio-economic impact of SEZ in Aurangabad, Nanded and Latur districts of Marathwada region.

It can be concluded that majority of the respondents affected by the SEZs were in the age group of 15-35 years as they are responsible for earning income in the families living in the affected areas.

Marital Status

The following table no 6.3 and figures no 6.3 shows information about marital status of the respondents in Konkan and Marathwada regions.

Table No. 6.3
Marital Status of the Respondent

Sr. No	Marital Status of Respondent	Konkan Region		Marathwada Region	
		Respondents	%	Respondents	%
1	Unmarried	30	30	25	25
2	Married	66	66	73	73
3	Divorced	04	02	02	02
4	Widower	0	0	0	1
5	Other	0	0	0	0
Total		100	100	100	100

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.3. % of Marital Status of the Respondents.

The data in the above indicates the people directly and indirectly affected by the enactment of SEZ Act in the study area. The data suggest the domestic life of the respondents. An individual once got married needed to look after whole of the family. He or she bears the responsibility of feeding the family members, hence through the survey it was found that the establishment of SEZ in districts like Thane, Raigad, and Ratnagiri as well as Nanded, Aurangabad and Latur, the respondents over relied on industries for their income. It was found that majority of them i.e. 66 in Konkan and 73 in Marathwada region, were married. Whereas, 30 and 25 number of respondents, Konkan and Marathwada region, bore indirect responsibility of family

respective regions. Only, in all 06 respondents were divorced. However, none of them was found to be widower or any other category.

Hence, it is clear that majority of the population affected due to SEZ were married respondents. It suggests that at local level people needed employment facility but not at the behest of loosing security of sustenance in the target area.

Educational background of the affected people in Konkan & Marathwada Region:

The following table 6.4 represent the data for educational background of the affected peoples and their educational profiles and percentage are given.

Table No. 6.4
Educational Qualifications of the Respondents

Sr. No.	Education Qualification	Konkan Region		Marathwada Region		Total
		Respondents	%	Respondents	%	
1	Illiterate	30	30	35	35	65
2	Primary	20	20	11	11	31
3	Upper Primary	05	05	04	04	09
4	High School	10	10	08	08	18
5	S. S. C.	15	15	20	20	35
6	H. S. C.	30	30	16	16	46
7	Vocational Course / Diploma	05	05	02	02	07
8	Graduate	03	03	04	04	07
9	Post Graduate	02	02	00	00	02
10	Other (specify the degree)	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
Total		100	100	100	100	200

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.4. Educational Qualification of Respondents

The above information shades light on the educational background of the respondents who form the population in grip of SEZ policy. 65 of the respondents were illiterate having no education at all. Whereas, around 139 respondents particularly those with primary, upper primary, high school, SSC and HSC could complete minimum education and just 16 respondents acquired higher education. This indicates that in Konkan and Marathwada region maximum population affected by the SEZ was literate up to HSC and rest of them were illiterate. This also shows that the majority of the population had no idea about the policy of SEZ and hence its aftermaths have been pervasive-affecting socio-economic standard of the target area.

Religious Status of the Respondents:

It is very important to analysis the religious factors of the affected peoples in selected regions for easy understanding to the social economic and condition of respondents in selected areas in Konkan and Marathwada regions it is highlights following table no 6.5.

Table No. 6.5
Religious Status of the Respondent's

Sr. No.	Religions of the Respondent	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	Percentage
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Hindu	60	75	135	67.5 %
2	Muslim	05	00	05	2.5 %
3	Christen	10	00	10	05 %
4	Buddhist	20	15	35	17.5 %
5	Other	10	05	15	7.5 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.5. Religious Status of the Respondents

Above table indicates proportion of religious population residing in the SEZ areas. Majority of the population i.e. 135 respondents out of 200, belongs to Hindu community, whereas just 05 and least number of population belong to 05 Muslim community. Around 35 respondents belong to Buddhist community. It is clear from the data that majority of the population in both the regions was Hindu who are landowners. All the land assets required for the SEZ belonged to these section of population, but due course of establishment of industrial units in respective areas, this section had major concerns against SEZ policy.

Occupation of the Respondents

Table No. 6.6
Occupation of the Respondents

Sr. No.	Occupation of Respondent	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Farmer/ Farming	53	60	113	56.5 %
2	Business	02	00	02	01 %
3	Entrepreneurs	00	00	00	00 %
4	Service	05	01	06	03 %
5	Worker	20	24	44	22 %
6	Labour/ Helper	20	15	35	17.5 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.6. Occupation of the Respondents in Konkan & Marathwada Regions

From the above data it becomes clear the income sources of people nearby SEZ units. Majority of the land acquired for SEZ was farm land used for various agricultural activities. About 113 respondents earned their livelihood from farming activity. Further, 44 respondents were workers who depended daily wages and hence needed one or the other work daily. 35 of the respondents were labourers/helper in the SEZ units. They, somehow, could get sundry works in SEZ units with no security of job. Since, the SEZ units recruited specialists in the respective departments it was observed that the local

people had to strive to get just helper jobs or patch work labourers on the sites. The data also shows that there were just 02 business men that too in Konkan region, directly involved in the SEZ area.

It can be concluded from the data that both the regions the majority of the population relied for their income on farm land but with the opening of SEZ units in respective regions the land seems to completely invaded by industrial activity, leaving bare and unproductive.

Income of the Respondents

The SEZ units are established in areas where majority of the population strives to earn their livelihood by daily work. Herein women, children, tribal, Dalit's, bonded labourers, agricultural labourers, un-organised workers and the underprivileged in general strive to earn livelihood. Their occupational sources have become shrunken due to SEZ units as exemplified in following data.

Table No. 6.7
Income of the Respondents

Sr. No.	Monthly Income of Respondent	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	Percentage
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	500 to1000	36	30	66	33 %
2	1001 to 2500	24	23	47	23.5 %
3	2501 to 5000	21	19	40	20 %
4	5001 to 10000	15	12	27	13.5
5	More than Rs.10000	10	10	20	10 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.7. Total % of Monthly Income of Respondent in Konkan & Marathwada Regions

Income of a region indicates living standard of the respondents. Total 66 respondents, in both regions, earned least income in a month and just 20 respondents earned more than Rs. 10000/- per month. Total 114 respondents earned income from 1001/- to 10000/- per month. This section forms the majority of the work force. Monthly income of respondents also shows mediocre living standard of the areas in Konkan and Marathwada regions. As compared to Marathwada region the income of the Konkan region was higher, since Mumbai, Navi Mumbai metropolitan city is close to the SEZ areas.

Families Structure of the Respondents:

In rural areas most of the people are joint families. Table No.6.8 shows that different structure of family members in SEZs affected area.

Table No. 6.8
Type of Families

Sr. No	Types of Family of the Respondent	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Group Family	55	60	115	57.5 %
2	Individual Family	45	40	85	42.5 %
3	Others	00	00	00	00 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.8. Family Structure of Respondents

Konkan and Marathwada regions are getting used to modern living standard. Although, the above table shows majority of the population i.e. 115 respondents live in joint family. In Marathwada region this number is higher as most of the population follow traditional life pattern of joint family. However, in Konkan region single family system is prominent to that of Marathwada region.

Thus, majority of the population prefer single and joint family in Konkan region as compared to Marathwada region.

Number of Member in the House/Family

Table No.6.9
Number of Member in the House/Family

Sr. No.	Number of Member in the House/family	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	01 to 03	40	25	65	32.5 %
2	04 to 06	35	40	75	37.5 %
3	06 to 09	10	15	25	12.5 %
4	10 to Above	15	20	35	17.5 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.9. Number of Member in the House/Family

In the above table, data about number of family members in a house is shown in order to point out working population in the study area. Around 01-03 number of family members live in 75 households and maximum number of members live in 25 households. It also indicate that in Marathwada region the number of family member is higher than that of Konkan region where minimum members live in a households.

It can be concluded from the above analysis that majority of the family members living in joint family in Marathwada, and they needed more and more source of income in order to meet daily needs.

Head of Family Member / Responsible Person in the House/ Leader of Family:

In the Konkan and Marathwada most of the families follow traditional pattern of joint family in which most the decisions are taken by male members and that to head of the family member. The data in the table no. 6.10 analyses percentage of families in which the head of the family takes most of the financial decisions family.

Table No. 6.10
Head of Family Member / Responsible Person in the House/ Leader of Family

Sr. No	Head of Family Member/ responsible person in the House	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondent	Respondent		
1	Father	80	90	170	85 %
2	Mother	15	07	22	11 %
3	Brother	05	03	08	04 %
4	Sister	00	00	00	00 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.10. Total % of Responsible Persons in the House

The above data shows responsible person in the families. In both the regions- Konkan and Marathwada region majority of the families are headed by father. He supposed to shoulder the responsibility of the family in terms of livelihood and daily needs. However, in Marathwada region most of the family members are headed by father as compared to Konkan region where around 15 families are run by female member i.e. mother. In Konkan region almost all the family members contribute in the family income of a house. It indicates urgency of income in a house. Thus, in Marathwada region almost all family depended for its food on father but in Konkan region, the mother and brother contribute in family income.

Land holding of the Respondents

SEZs in Maharashtra required approximately 1, 59,123 acres of land for setting up of industrial units. The government plans to acquire this land using the Land Acquisition Act 1894 (LAA) and the Maharashtra Industrial Development Act 1961 (MIDA). In fact, it is forcibly acquiring large tracts of land and then transferring them to developers for high rates. Thus, the MIDC has failed to represent the interests of the people and instead functions more as an agent between SEZ developers and farmers. Following data shows the landholding capacity of farmers who had to forsook their land to the MIDC in Konkan and Marathwada region.

Table No. 6.11

Landholding capacity of Respondents

Sr. No.	Land holding of the Respondent (Area Ha)	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondent	Respondent		
1	01 Hectare	12	15	27	13.5 %
2	02 to 04 Hectare	16	21	37	18.5 %
3	05 to 10 Hectare	20	24	44	22 %
4	11 to 15 Hectare	22	12	34	17 %
5	16 Hectare to Above	30	28	58	29 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.11. Landholding capacity of Respondents

As has been mentioned above the main source of protest against SEZs in Marathwada and Konkan region is in land acquisition process by MIDC, a government organization. In the above table it is clear that 12 landowners owned minimum 01 hectares of land in Marathwada region and minimum 12 landowners in Konkan region own 05-10 hectares of land. In Konkan region, over 30 land owners had 16 hectares and above land as compared to 28 hectares of land owners in Maharashtra. Thus, maximum land was used by SEZs in Konkan region wherein the SEZ units were established.

Types of Land Structure /Farm Pattern

The Special Economic Zone Act came into force in 2005. Since its implementation around 1046 SEZs are in different stages of approval in the country. This rapid increase in SEZ approvals has meant large scale acquisition of land from private owners through the implementation of the Land Acquisition Act, 1894 or similar state legislations. Prime agrarian land and commons are being acquired for the cause of industry, causing serious concern, agitation and struggle in SEZ areas across the country.

The survey reflected that much of the land to be acquired is cultivable and productive. The Konkan region, including Mumbai, Thane, Raigad and Pune, has the highest rainfall in Maharashtra making the soil excellent for cultivating paddy. In Raigad, most people whose lands have been notified, grow paddy which is a water intensive crop and a variety of vegetables like cucumber and okra. Farmers in Aurangabad, Nanded, and Latur reported growing soybean, wheat, corn, bajra, sugarcane, paddy and groundnut yielding a high income from this land. Apart from growing crops the land (even the barren land) is used for *chara* or fodder for animal husbandry. Farmers derive an income from rearing animals, fishing, working on salt pans and other allied activities. The affected farmers derive an income from dairy, poultry and allied activities. Following data shows type of land acquired from the respondents for setting up of SEZ units.

Table No. 6.12
Types of Land /farm

Sr. No.	Types of Land	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondent	Respondent		
1	Dry Land	20	25	45	22.5 %
2	Fertile Land	35	30	65	32.5 %
3	Irrigated Land	45	45	90	45 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.12. Types of Land

The data in the above table shows use of land for the SEZ projects in Konkan and Marathwada region. 45 respondents reported that their land was dry and barren, 65 respondents claimed it as fertile land and seasonal crops used to be taken in that land and maximum of the respondents complained that their land was fertile and irrigated. In fact they all were depended on agrarian land for livelihood. But, with enactment of SEZ act most of them had to loose their land for SEZ units in exchange of monetary benefits.

Type of Ownership of Land Holders

The traditional way ownership of agricultural land was based on transfer of assets from one generation to the next heirs in the family. The data about the ownership of land in the target area shows that most of the respondents have purchased land, some of them received as heirs in the family, and some of them

received it from government under various schemes for agricultural purpose. This types of ownership of land is explained in detail in the table no.6.13.

Table No 6.13
Type of Ownership of Land Holders

Sr. No.	Type of Ownership of Land Holders /Respondent	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondent	Respondent		
1	Own	50	55	105	52.5 %
2	Parents Gift	43	44	87	43.5 %
3	Govt Land	00	00	00	00 %
4	Sealing Land	05	00	05	2.5 %
5	Other	02	01	03	1.5 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.13. Type of Ownership of Land Holders

The above table shows details of land holding in Konkan and Marathwada region. Maximum people (105) own the land that is in vicinity of SEZ area or is soon to be acquired for the purpose. In konkan about half of the land was owned by farmers, nearly 43 respondents received it as gift from ancestors, and 05 respondents' land came under the sealing land area. Similarly, around 55 respondents had brought up their land by sheer hard work and nearly half of the farmers have been cultivating the land ever since their ancestors left it as the only source of livelihood. Whereas only 02 respondents acquired land and tilled to support income. Thus, it becomes clear that the land to be acquired by the government agency was majorly owned by farmers and

half of the land was been cultivated by them as traditional source of income and livelihood in Konkan and Marathwada regions.

Total No. of Wells in Farm land

The land owned by the farmers in Konkan and Marathwada region was of cultivable land. In Konkan region most of the agricultural activity depended on rain water but in Marathwada region most of the respondents had to rely on well, tube-wells for irrigating the crops. Following data reveals the source of irrigation in Konkan and Marathwada region.

Table No. 6.14
Total No. of Wells in Farm land

Sr. No.	Total No. of Well in Farms	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondent	Respondent		
1	0	21	16	37	18.5 %
2	1	29	34	63	31.5 %
3	2	19	30	49	24.5 %
4	3	14	12	26	13 %
5	4	06	03	09	4.5 %
6	Above 5	11	05	16	08 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.14. Total No. of Wells in Farm land

In the survey, an attempt was made to accumulate data about irrigation resource of farmers whose land lay near to the SEZ projects. It was observed that nearly all the farmers in Marathwada region highly depended on well or

tube for irrigation needs. Highest number of respondent (34) had at least one well and minimum 16 respondents reported to have no such facility in their field. There were 05 respondent who had more than 05 wells for irrigation facility in Marathwada region.

Similarly, in Konkan region too many farmers had wells and tube wells for irrigation. It was worth noting that about 21 farmers completely depended on seasonal rainfall as there was no well in the farm. Maximum 28 respondents had one well and only 11 respondents had more than 05 wells for irrigation. Thus, it becomes clear that most of the farmers were engaged in agricultural activity irrespective of availability of irrigation facility.

Land Acquisition Agencies

Perhaps the most detestable aspect of the new SEZs provisions is that it enabled private companies to grab large area of land from farmers. The speed at which agricultural lands were being lost, led to a series of agitations by small farmers. The tremendous indignation of famers at the bold abuse of the Land Acquisition Act - the disgusting insurrection of the original purpose of “eminent domain” which was proposed to apply to projects of public importance and not to help generate private profits. Following were the agencies who acquired the land from farmers.

**Table No. 6.15
Land Acquisition of Agencies for SEZ Project**

Sr. No.	Who is Acquired your land?	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondent	Respondent		
1	MIDC	24	35	59	29.5 %
2	DIC	28	24	52	26 %
3	SEZs Project	44	40	84	42 %
4	Others	04	01	05	2.5 %
	Total	100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.15. Land Acquisition of Agencies for SEZ Project

Many agencies played vital role in acquiring the land for SEZ units. Amongst are MIDC, DIC, SEZs projects and other who assumed role of mediators between farmers, general public and private companies and government for acquiring large tract of land in Konkan and Marathwada region. When asked about agency that acquired land the respondents reported that maximum land was acquired by MIDC both in Konkan and Marathwada region. More than fifty respondents reported that MIDC took hold of their land. On the other hand 84 respondents reported acquisition of land by SEZs project owned companies, whereas total 52 respondents' land was taken for export oriented production units under SEZ by DIC in Konkan and Marathwada region. As noted earlier not all the landowner were agreed upon the deals between the government agencies and private companies. Some of them were forced to sell their land without taking into consideration of rehabilitation measures in affected area.

Awareness about Land Acquisition Process

Under the SEZs Act, 2005, there was not any special awareness campaign before issuing the intimation or prior notice to peoples for acquisition of land. The land acquisition process was conducted without making any public issue. Most the SEZ stakeholder privately approached private agents to survey and complete sale deeds. In some of the districts in Konkan and Marathwada region, the SEZ developers directly attracted farmers inquiring land for SEZ projects. As a result people were surprised over the un-notified land acquisition process which was, in fact, approved under the SEZ

policy of the government. The following table no 6.16 shows the information about factual awareness land acquisition process undertaken by private developers and indicative of general feeling about SEZ in rural and urban areas.

Table No. 6.16
Awareness about Land Acquisition Process

Sr. No.	Land Acquisition Process	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondent	Respondent		
1	Yes	27	20	47	23.5 %
2	No	73	80	153	76.5 %
	Total	100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.16. Awareness about Land Acquisition Process

Above responses of respondents suggest awareness about SEZ land acquisition procedures regulated under the Land Acquisition process by government agencies. It was found that nearly 153 respondents were completely unaware about the complex procedure of acquiring land. In fact they were just lured by the companies by showing large sum in exchange of their land. Merely 47 respondents had an idea of land acquisition in the study area. Lack of awareness about the land acquiring process resulted in growing complexities in problems in getting compensations for the landowners.

Awareness about SEZs Project

As noted above most of the general public in rural areas of Konkan and Marathwada region had very little knowledge about SEZ and its land acquisition. Hence, in such circumstances, one cannot claim awareness about SEZ projects to be set up in the land acquired. Following table details opinion about SEZ projects in Konkan and Marathwada region.

Table No. 6.17

SEZ Projects and Land Awareness

Sr. No.	Do you know about SEZs Project	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondent	Respondent		
1	Yes	41	37	78	39 %
2	No	59	63	122	61 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.17. SEZ Projects and Land Awareness

The data indicate general nature of SEZ and its policy implemented in rural as well as urban areas in Konkan and Marathwada region. Most of the people gave their land demanded by government but majority of them had rare idea about the nature of SEZ project established in the area. Around 122 (61%) respondents said that they had no idea about the type of SEZ project being established or in process in the vicinity. Only 78 (38%) respondents reported awareness about the awareness of SEZ project to be established in the area.

Discontent after Land acquisition for SEZ Projects

Private developers and the government agencies started acquiring land for SEZ. As result great discontent spread among rural areas. The common people were separated from the land which was their traditional resource of livelihood. It is often not realized and recognized that land ownership in rural was limited to a few families; but many lives families depended upon that land, although they may not own it. The owners of large tracts of land may receive what may appear as large monetary compensation for the land acquired but as experience shows the ability of most to put it to gainful and long term sustenance is doubtful. Thus, while the socially marginalised and economically deprived are the worst affected by this process of land acquisition even those who apparently gain in the immediate context may actually be losers in the longer term. Both, as a result of the morally and legally questionable and insensitive manner in which the land is being bought up by corporate companies, developers and government and the realization that this form of development is but nothing but a chimera as far as the rural population and especially the marginalised are concerned has raised feelings of resentment against the companies and government. This table shows the feeling of discomfort after acquisition of land for SEZ project in Konkan and Marathwada region. Is your family affected by land acquisition for SEZ PROJECT?

Table No 6.18
Land Acquisition and affected under SEZ Project

Sr. No.	Are you affected as land acquisition for SEZ project?	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondent	Respondent		
1	Yes	35	25	60	30 %
2	No	65	75	140	70 %
	Total	100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.18. Land Acquisition and affected under SEZ Project

As has been found in the survey, most of the land in rural and urban areas of Konkan and Marathwada was acquired for SEZ projects. It was used by the inhabitants who were completely dependent on it for livelihood. The survey concluded that not all but majority of the population expressed discontent towards the use of land as their immediate source of income was thrashed. Around 35 respondents in Konkan and 25 in Marathwada region confirmed the benefit of acquisition of land. However, majority of the landowner resented the process. In Konkan (30 %) and Marathwada region (70 %), more than half of the respondents gave negative reply. As a result large massive agitations and agricultural audits have been undertaken in the affected area to ascertain the outcome of SEZ projects.

Selling of land for SEZ units

In Konkan region where the SEZ was to be established, each of individual owned an average of three plots of land. And approximately 2/3 of all land owners actually opposed selling land to the SEZ.

The farmers in affected area, as assumed by the SEZ supporters, selling the land because it is not good even for cattle grazing. But, fact is that it was done deliberately and the farmers were forced to withdraw their objections filed under Section 5A of Land Acquisition Act. These agreements were not explained or read out before the farmers. The farmers were compelled to sell the land because of the compulsory acquisition process, since 2006. However, these farmers who have sold lands to M-SEZ, don't want SEZ to come up, they

have also expressed their opinion through the opinion poll. But the results of the opinion poll have not been taken into consideration.

Table No 6.19
Land to the SEZs Developer/ SEZs Project?

Sr. No.	Did you sold your land to the SEZs Developer/ SEZs Project	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondent	Respondent		
1	Yes	37	38	75	37.5 %
2	No	63	62	125	62.5 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.19.land sold for developers

Above table highlights inferences drawn over the opinion poll conducted to assess the fact file of land acquisition. In Konkan region and Marathwada region most of the landowners reported that their land was acquired forcefully. About 125 farmers expressed their concerns over acquisition procedure and just 75 respondents showed consent over the deal.

Table No. 6.20
Consent over giving land to the SEZs projects

Sr. No.	Do you agree for giving land to the SEZs Project?	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondent	Respondent		
1	Yes	39	25	64	32 %
2	No	61	75	136	68 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.20. Total % of both regions

The responses in above table gives clear insight into agreement and disagreement toward selling of land to SEZ projects. It is clear from the data that around 136 respondents showed reluctance over giving land for SEZ as compared to the 64 respondents who seemed to lured by the private companies in exchange of large monetary compensations. Are you opposed for Land Acquisition Process for SEZs project.

Purchase of land

Giving land for SEZs project was not simple decision for farmers in Konkan region and Marathwada region. In order to sue the farmers and landowners, there are many real-estate touts and agents operating in the area, and most of them are buying land with the hope of selling it back to the Project at higher rates. Private companies have been recruiting some people to work as promoters in convincing people to sell their land. In the survey, it was also found that the private companies are using muscle power and extra constitutional means such as filing of false registry cases to forcibly evict the

people from their land holdings. The large number of sharecroppers and landless peasantry, fisher-folk will naturally exclude a large number of the affected people from any form of compensation or traditional rights to their traditional livelihood. Those above 40 years, especially the women, were vulnerable due to the loss of their traditional occupation. Hence, these people generally carry out traditional occupations and may face problems when sold their land which will cause threat to their occupations in the changed scenario. Following are the responses of general public in Konkan and Marathwada region when asked: Was there any burden for sale of land for SEZs Projects?

Table No.6.21
Land Acquisition Burden and SEZ Projects

Sr. No.	Burden for sale of land for SEZs Projects?	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondent	Respondent		
1	Yes	69	52	121	60.5 %
2	No	31	48	79	39.5 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.21. Burden for sale of land for SEZs Projects?

The responses show the forceful implementation of SEZ Act in order to gain land for setting up SEZ projects in Konkan region and Marathwada region. In konkan region most of the respondents reported that at first they were not agreed upon selling their land but the ensuing efforts by the private companies compelled them to sell the land. As result, around 121 respondents in both the region reported there was certain pressure to sell the land and just 79 of them reported willingness to sell the land for SEZ. In konkan region

around 69 respondents rejected the demand for land but were at last lured to sell it. Similarly, in Marathwada region, most of the farmers were sued to sell the land. It can be concluded that the result of SEZ Act had adverse effect on the farmers. In fact some of them were forced to sell their land which doesn't hold humanitarian aspect at any point of achieving economic development.

Table No. 6.22
Land purchased by the different office/Organisations

Sr. No.	Land Purchased by the different office/Organisations	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondent	Respondent		
1	Central Government	05	00	05	2.5 %
2	State Government	23	30	53	26.5 %
3	MIDC	30	40	70	35 %
4	SEZs Developers	21	15	36	18 %
5	Privet Company	20	12	32	16 %
6	Politician	01	03	04	02 %
7	other	00	00	00	00 %
	Total	100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.22. Land Purchased by the different office/Organisations

As has been noted in earlier discussion, the MIDC, SEZ developers and private companies came forward to take control of the land for prospective SEZs projects in Konkan and Marathwada region. Despite the dispute over the

land acquisition issues in respective regions, the process was in progress amidst mixed agreement among stakeholders. Above data explains the land acquisition by various government and private agencies. Maximum respondents reported that their land was overtaken by MIDC (70) and State government (53) in the region whereas minimum land was acquired by politician (04). SEZ developers (36) showed interest in setting up units in the regions. In Konkan region maximum land was acquired by MIDC, state government and private company as compared to Marathwada region. Therefore, it is concluded that SEZ units were established in mutual agreement between state and central government and private companies.

Land Acquisition and Compensation for the land acquired?

The following table no 6.23 given the answer of the above question and affected farmers /people’s opinion about that, developers and Government not give proper compensations against land acquisition.

Table No. 6.23
Land Acquisition and proper Compensation

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondent	Respondent		
1	Yes	35	26	61	30.5 %
2	No	65	74	139	69.5 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.23. Land Acquisition and proper Compensation

The above response shows disillusionment caused due to lack of compensation after land acquisition. In the survey, out of two hundred respondents 139 of them reported negative response when asked about the

compensation from government agency or private company, whereas only 61 respondents were satisfied with the compensation. In Konkan region majority of the respondents were successful in getting compensation extracted from the private and government agencies as compared to Marathwada region. Thus, in Marathwada region most of the people staged more protest to get compensations.

Compensation as Per Current Market Rate

Private land is being acquired for long in ‘public purpose’ as defined by the Land Acquisition Act (LAA) of 1894. But large-scale acquisitions for SEZs have raised questions on whether the government should intermediate in acquiring land for private developers and whether such acquisition is justified as ‘public purpose’. The questions have extended to a critical query: Is the ‘eminent domain’ of the Indian state discriminating against small and medium landowners? The passion aroused by the debate has been intensified by demands for restoring the right to property as a ‘fundamental’ right – an issue currently being examined by the Supreme Court. The laws suggest fixing compensation for acquired land on the basis of its market price. But India’s opaque land markets prevent the discovery of ‘correct’ prices. Land prices recorded in sale (or purchase) deeds are usually under-quoted to avoid high stamp duties. Compensation also depends upon changes in land value arising from future use. Following data shows about responses given by respondents who somehow were aware about rates put forth by government agencies and private agencies to acquire their land.

Table No. 6.24
Respondents view about Land market rate

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondent	Respondent		
1	Yes	37	45	82	41 %
2	No	63	55	118	59 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.24. Respondents view about Land market rate

In the above table responses from the affected people who responded to the question: Did the SEZs Developers give compensation as per current market rate? As has been shown in the table in Konkan region maximum respondents gave negative response as compared to respondents in Marathwada region. In all 118 respondents said that the compensation given to them was not as per the market rates and hence they reject the SEZ units. Total 82 respondents were aware about the market rates of the land that they received from the government agencies. Thus, above response shows causes behind discontent among people in SEZ areas owing to dis-satisfaction over land rates.

Table No. 6.25
Satisfaction over the Compensation

Sr. No.	Satisfaction over the Compensation	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondent	Respondent		
1	Yes	23	25	48	24 %
2	No	77	75	152	76 %
Total		100	100	200	100%

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.25. Satisfaction over the Compensation

The responses in the above table suggest satisfaction over the compensation after land acquisition by government and private agencies. In Konkan region, about 23 respondents were happy to get the monetary benefits, but as compared to konkan region, just 25 respondents in Marathwada region reported their satisfaction over compensation. On the contrary, in Konkan region total 48 and in Marathwada region 152 respondents registered their discontent over the compensation by government and private agencies.

Use of Compensation money by the landowners

Money compensation and employment have been verbally promised and claimed but there are no written assurances. Compensation is a onetime income and is not comparable to the land that is being acquired considering that land is a perennial resource. This land is the true wealth of the farmers. The onetime money compensation, however, does not stay and will be used immediately and then we will be left with nothing. Following responses indicate the factual situation in the affected area.

Table No 6.26

After selling the land have you purchased another agriculture land?

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Yes	26	45	71	35.5 %
2	No	74	55	129	64.5 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.26. After selling the land have you purchased another agriculture land

The responses data shows utilization of money by the landowners in Konkan and Marathwada region. Most of the people invested money in land. In konkan region less number of respondents (26) invested in real-estate and plotting business as compared to higher number of respondents (45) in Marathwada region. On the other hand total 74 respondents used money for buying luxurious goods and services instead on investing in real-estate. Similarly 55 respondents in Marathwada region utilized money on sundry life pleasures. As total 71 people used money to establish new real-estate business and maximum 129 respondents preferred spending money for luxurious pleasures after getting the compensations.

Table No. 6.27

Are you satisfied with the deal/ acquisition of land by SEZs Projects?

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Yes	25	26	51	25.5 %
2	No	75	74	149	74.5 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.27. Are you satisfied with the deal/ acquisition of land by SEZs Projects?

In above table the response of land owners is recorded in order to know their satisfaction after selling of land or acquisition of land by the government agencies. It clearly shows that, in Konkan and Marathwada region total 71 people expressed satisfaction over the land deal, since they received huge compensation for the barren land. However, around 129 people were dissatisfied with land deals as they were forced to sell the land. The land was only the source of income for such families but due to force and land agents they were made to sell their land against compensations from government and private companies. Hence, majority of the public showed reluctance toward land deals in general.

Table No. 6.28
SEZs Projects satisfaction of Villages

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Strongly Agree	20	15	35	17.5 %
2	Agree	10	25	35	17.5 %
3	Disagree	45	35	80	40 %
4	Strongly Disagree	15	23	38	19 %
5	Not at all	05	02	07	3.5 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.28. Satisfaction of project

The above table shows 35 (17.5%) respondents from Konkan region agree over the SEZ project set up in the village or locality, whereas 80 (40%) showed disagreement over the setting up of SEZ project in their locality. Not more than 07 (3.5%) respondents had not idea about what was going on in their locality while the land acquisition process was in process. In both the regions, just 35 (17.5%) respondents showed strong agreement and on the contrary majority i. e. 38 (19%) expressed strong disagreement over the SEZ projects in their locality.

Thus, the general public showed mixed response over the setting up of various industrial units under SEZs. The responses of the respondents are indicative of the general sense of feeling in disfavour of the SEZ policy of Government.

Do you believe that SEZs is beneficial for providing Employment / Job? :

The able No 9.9 shows that information about response from Konkan and Marathwada regions. The respondents' opinions were collected regarding employment opportunities provided by SEZs projects in the locality.

Table No 6.29
SEZ and employment opportunities

Sr. No.	Opinion of Respondents	Total Respondent of Konkan & Marathwada Regions	Percentage
1	Strongly Agree	35	17.5 %
2	Agree	35	17.5 %
3	Disagree	80	40 %
4	Strongly Disagree	38	19 %
5	Not Response	13	6.5 %
Total		200	100%

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.29. SEZ and Employment opportunities

The above table shows 35 (17.5%) responds from Konkan region strongly agree over the employment opportunities made available in the SEZ project set up in the village or locality, whereas 80 (40%) showed disagreement for the reason that they didn't get any job opportunity after the setting up of SEZ project in their locality. Just 13 (3.5%) respondents registered no response over the employment in SEZ. In both the regions, just 35 (17.5%) respondents showed strong agreement and on the contrary majority i. e. 38 (19%) expressed strong disagreement over the SEZ projects in their locality.

Thus, in general the local people in and around the industrial units under SEZs expected employment opportunities but due lack of expertize and proper

educational qualification most of them were dismayed over the employment opportunity. The responses of the responses are indicative of the general sense of feeling in disfavour of employment opportunities generated by the SEZ policy implemented by the Government.

Source of Employment

After implementation of SEZ Act, 2005 was the main objectives before SEZ Act/policy was creation of employment opportunities. As per section 5 of SEZ Act, one of the objectives of SEZ Act was generation of Employment i.e. both direct employment for skilled and unskilled labour. However, there is no policy for skill development for employment of the project affected people which has led to providing of employment to very few individuals only.

Table No. 6.30
Source of Employment /Job creation before acquisition of land for SEZs Project

Sr. No.	Employment before acquisition of land for SEZs	Konkan Region	Marathwada region	Total	Percentage (%)
1	Own farming	55	42	97	48.5 %
2	Agriculture labourers	23	35	58	29 %
4	Entrepreneurs	02	00	02	01 %
5	Service	05	03	08	04 %
6	Labour	15	20	35	17.5 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.30. Source of employment creation before acquisition of land for SEZs Projects.

The table no 6.30 shows information about source of employment / Job creation before the land acquisition for SEZs Projects. The mostly rural areas peoples working in Own farming, and Agricultural labours are depending in

agro sectors. In Konkan regions total 55 respondents engage own farming, 23 farmers depending labours in agro sector, and fishery, “mithgar” farm in nearest areas, and 15 respondents as working labourer activities and only 2 respondents doing business and entrepreneurial activities, and 5 respondents are in doing service. In Marathwada regions in 42, respondent totally depend upon agricultural and own farming, and 35 respondent given response for they are engage labourers activity in agriculture related activity, and 3 respondents are in service and 20 respondents working as labour in industrial areas in his nearest place.

SEZs Projects and Job Opportunities

Table No.6.13 shows the information about employment for the affected peoples in projected areas after land acquisition.

Table No. 6.31
Employment Opportunities after Land Acquisition

Sr. No.	Employment you are getting after land acquired for SEZs project?	Total Respondent of Marathwada & Konkan	Percentage
1	Farming	38	18 %
2	No Work	64	32 %
3	Labour	50	25 %
4	Worker	30	15 %
5	Helper	20	10 %
Total		200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.31. Employment getting after land acquired for SEZs project

The above table put forth data about employment generation position after land acquisition in the Konkan and Marathwada region. SEZs Project are supposed to generate employment for workers, labourers as well as educational qualified, experts and vocational degree holders in both regions. As the response shows, over 38 (18%) respondents are engaged in farming activities. 64 (32 %) of them said that SEZ has not provided any employment for project affected people. Over 50 (25%) respondents depended on labour and daily wages; whereas 30 (15%) workers strive to get job in SEZ project area. In few cases, 20 (10%) respondents in the nearby areas got jobs in SEZ units but as a Helper. Thus, SEZ projects have generated job opportunities for people in surrounded areas but of sundry nature i.e. Labour, Workers, Helper, in project affected areas. However, the majority of the respondents gave negative response as they were not offered any permanent job in both region.

Employment affected respondents with less land

The MSEZ rehabilitation plan for landless labourers includes a two year steady supply of income and job training for one member in the family but with no guarantee of employment. After two years of minimum wages the agricultural labourers are left to fend for themselves with little government assurance or assurances of jobs from the company. Moreover, women in the families are also involved in agricultural work and they are not included in the rehabilitation programme. The rehabilitation programme includes some vocational training for women and but no employment guarantee. Also, the rehabilitation plan does not consider the loss of livelihood. Loss of land means loss of livelihood for these workers too. When asked about employment opportunity by the SEZs for landless people.

Howsoever, the employment opportunity created required a completely different set of skills that labourers, agricultural workers didn't possess at all. In this regard, employment issue of the SEZ affected people has become burning topic in Konkan and Marathwada region.

Do the SEZs provide Employment (Affected people) opportunity for land less people?

Table No. 6.32
Employment opportunity for land less people

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Yes	20	25	45	22.5 %
2	No	80	75	155	77.5 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.32 Employment (Affected people) opportunity for land less people

To avail employment opportunity for the people was one of the prime concerns of establishing SEZ in Maharashtra. So as to understand the employment status in Marathwada and Konkan region, the respondents were inquired about any job opportunities in the SEZ units. It was observed that majority of the general public which included lower classes, labourers, workers, women and men who strive to earn their livelihood on daily wages, reported that not all but very few would get jobs in SEZ units or project sites. Since, the SEZ unit site is assumed to have new labour laws, its rules and regulations hardly apply to the general public in terms of employment opportunities. In fact, the landless, lower class general public is given sundry works on SEZ sites and the high profile, skilled labour is hired from distant places. Hence, majority of the respondents (155) expressed grave concerns over the employment in SEZ projects, whereas just 45 respondents could get jobs in the SEZ. It can be concluded that SEZ units in Maharashtra are not entitled to generate employment for the local people.

Job Satisfaction at SEZ sites

The survey reflects concern over the compensation as well as employment opportunities for unskilled and skilled labourers in the SEZ units. Farmers and agricultural labourers are skilled in agriculture and allied activities and do not have any other skills. In effect, acquiring the land caused a loss of livelihood and privation among unskilled labourers who are in search of employment now. They didn't get employment and are lead to displacement in search of livelihood making them venerable to worse effects of unemployment than ever before.

The MSEZ rehabilitation plan for landless labourers includes a two year steady supply of income and job training for at least one member in the family. However, it won't give guarantee of employment in the SEZ units. People, who have lost their land were assured two years of minimum wages to the agricultural labourers are left to fend for themselves with little government assurance or assurances of jobs from the company. Moreover, women in the families are not included in the rehabilitation programme. Moreover the rehabilitation programme included some vocational training for men and women but doesn't guarantee employment opportunity in the SEZ premises.

Table No. 6.33
Job Satisfaction under SEZs Project

Sr. No	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Strongly Agree	15	20	35	17.5 %
2	Agree	30	27	57	28.5 %
3	Disagree	25	13	48	24 %
4	Strongly Disagree	25	45	70	35 %
5	Not at all	05	05	10	05 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.33. Satisfied for job provided by the SEZs Project

It is observed during the study that, few respondents could get entry into SEZ project sites, but they were asked about their job satisfaction it was realized that about 35 respondents strongly agree and 57 of the total respondents agree over the job satisfaction they conferred with. However, around 48 and 70 respondents expressed disagreement and strongly opposed the stringent labour laws framed for SEZ territories. Hence, it is imperative that the SEZ policy must look into the labour laws framed for SEZ units and take necessary action, especially, from the point of view of interest of general public.

Place of residence

In process of land acquisition many families lost their mainstay and they are made to wait for rehabilitation packages. In order to ascertain the rehabilitation and resettlement of the persons affected due to compulsory acquisition of land the survey attempted to know about locality of the SEZ area. But SEZs project does not providing any such types of supposed be provided with free house sites, grant for house construction/subsistence allowances, etc.

Table No. 6.34
Accommodation Position and SEZ Projects

Sr. No.	Respondent	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Own house	45	28	73	36.5 %
2	Rental Accommodation	25	40	65	32.5 %
3	Outside of the company premises	40	22	62	31 %
4	In side of the company premises	00	00	00	00 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.34. Accommodation Position of Respondents

The above table show the response about the residential status of people who are, somehow, directly or indirectly depended on SEZ units for livelihood. It can be observed from the above table that, 47 respondents in Konkan and Marathwada region had their own dwelling place, total 65 respondents rented houses in and around the SEZ premises and over 62 respondents stay outside the company premises whereas just 26 of them managed to get place to stay in company premises. It can be concluded that the SEZ premises is not suitable for general public and those who own houses in nearby SEZ territory draw attention towards fundamental facilities in and around the villages.

Awareness about SEZ

Special Economic Zones (SEZ) policy announced by the government of India in April 2000 assumed to be foreign territory for the purpose of trader operations, duties and tariffs. The object is to provide an internationally competitive and difficulty free environment for exports. The units may be setup for manufacture of goods and rendering of services. Special Economic Zones (SEZ) is geographical region that has economic laws that are more liberal than country's typical economic laws. Usually the goal is to increase in foreign investment. Despite such high motives, does the general public has any clear cut information about the SEZ policy. To find out more the respondents were asked following question:

Table No. 6.35
Awareness about the SEZs Policy/ Act, 2005

Sr. No.	Respondent	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Yes	36	20	56	28 %
2	No	64	80	144	72 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.35. Awareness about the SEZs Policy/ Act, 2005

As per the study, most of the respondents residing in the SEZ project area. Marathwada and Konkan had very little information about the SEZ policy of the Government. Out of total 200 respondents only 56 respondents including farmers, businessmen, men and women, workers, tribal landless labours reported that they come to know about SEZ from local leaders, business men,

MIDC workers and government offices. On the contrary about 144 respondents had either no idea or paid heed to the SEZ units being set up under government regulation. Most of them got aware only when there was news about massive agitation in their area. This indicates ignorance about SEZ and government policies among general public in India.

Information about SEZs policy

The SEZ Act is applicable to whole India as Nation. The Act is expected to be applied to different area, region, state according to the dates declared separately. This Act, Central Govt. on the recommendation of the Board of Approval may, by notification established specially delineated area in any state or more than one state, Central Govt. reserves the right to make rules regarding specific requirements. The establishment of SEZ shall be considered as a specific foreign territory for the purpose of trade operations, duties, taxes, etc.,

Particularly the reserve area can be used for setting up of units for production of goods and rendering services. The rights reserve with central .Govt. to prescribe procedure for setting up of unit and their operations. Now to be very specific whether the general public made aware about the nature of business operations is the question. It seems that government and government agencies made any such efforts about SEZ policy as a result there had been constant discontentment among general public about SEZs.

**Table No. 6.36
SEZ Awareness and respondent**

Sr. No.	Respondent	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Yes	25	15	40	20 %
2	No	75	85	160	800 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.36. SEZ Awareness and respondent

Above responses highlight awareness about the general and specific information about SEZ established in the area once the SEZ policy was regularized in India. As per the findings in survey, around 40 respondents had detail idea about the setting of SEZ, its role, its operation, its ownership, its infrastructure, management, land acquisition and issues like foreign territory etc. However, majority of the public in Konkan and Marathwada had no idea about SEZ policy its detail provisions and outcomes. Hence, the government should have had conducted wide campaign about SEZ projects, its provision, beneficiaries, its specific laws, labour laws, technology, administration.

Whether you were aware about the purpose of land acquisition by SEZs?

The following table no 6.37 shows responses regarding awareness about the purpose of land acquisition by SEZs Project.

Table No. 6.37

Whether you were aware about the purpose of land acquisition by SEZs?

Sr. No.	Respondent	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Yes	45	48	93	46.5 %
2	No	55	52	107	53.5 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.37. Awareness about the purpose of land acquisition by SEZ

Above responses by total 200 respondents referred to the awareness among project affected people in the surrounding areas about the purpose of land acquisition by SEZ. Only 93 respondents gave positive response in Konkan and Marathwada region about awareness process of land acquisition. On the contrary, majority of the respondents (107) registered negative response as they were not aware about SEZ land acquisition process. It can be concluded that the government should have conducted a wide awareness campaign in order to get general consent over the Setting Up of SEZ units in the localities.

Which types of jobs are provided by SEZs projects for land lord/ Land owner/ land owner?

The SEZs project are providing job for land owners who have been affected due course of land acquisition in Konkan & Marathwada region. The following table shows jobs offered for the affected people.

Table No. 6.38
Types of Job for Affected People/ Farmers

Sr. No.	Types of Job for Affected People/ Farmers	Total Respondents of Konkan & Marathwada Region	Percentage
1	Worker	40	20 %
2	Labour	60	30 %
3	Trainees	30	15 %
4	Officers	00	00 %
5	Manager	00	00 %
6	other	70	35 %
Total		200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.38. Total percentage of jobs provided by SEZs projects for land lord

Above table shows the information for 200 respondents in Konkan & Marathwada region who have to sell their land for SEZs project. The researcher tried to collect responses from both regions and observed that total 40 (20%) respondents got job as workers; 60 (30%) respondents are working as labours; 30 (15%) respondents are getting Trainees job for projects; and 70 (35 %) respondents are in other categories for and that percentage is 35%. It becomes clear that the SEZs project are not providing god job for farmers who have to loose their traditional living sources. Because, framers are not technically and highly educated they have generated negative feeling for SEZ project.

SEZs Project and Employment Generate

The main objectives of SEZs policy for generating employment opportunities for the peoples and society for rural development and increasing economic activity. But ground level is situation is very different and far away from SEZs project are not providing employment. This information given following table no 6.39.

Table No. 6.39
SEZs Project and Employment Generation for Rural People

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Yes	12	9	21	10.5 %
2	No	88	91	179	89.5 %
Total		100	100	200	100%

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.39. SEZs Project Generate Employment

Above responses by total 200 respondents indicate ground reality of SEZ policy in respect of employment in rural areas and surrounded areas. In all only 21 (10.5 %) respondents gave positive response in Konkan and Marathwada region when asked about employment generation under SEZs policy. On the contrary, majority of the respondents 179 (89.5%) registered negative response as they were constantly facing unemployment factors for due to suffer in land acquisition by SEZ projects in the residential areas.

SEZs Provide Employment Opportunities for Women

As experienced by the East Asian countries, the developing economics SEZs have significantly improved women employment in SEZs in India. But, in Maharashtra especially in Konkan and Marathwada regions this position is revers position for employment opportunities for women. In order to understand the impact on employment opportunity for women who are effected and displaced the researcher collected following data. It was found that the SEZs provided employment opportunities in SEZ units only five percent women.

Table No. 6.40
SEZs Provide Employment Opportunities for Women

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	Percentage
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Yes	15	13	28	14 %
2	No	85	87	172	86 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.40. SEZs Provide Employment Opportunities for Women

Above responses by total 200 respondents male and females are indicate ground reality of SEZ policy in respect of their SEZs provide employment opportunities for women. In all only 28 (14%) respondents gave positive response in Konkan and Marathwada region when asked about employment generation for women under SEZs policy. On the contrary, majority of the respondents 172 (86%) registered negative response as they were constantly facing unemployment factors for due to suffer in land acquisition by SEZ projects in the residential areas.

SEZs Provide Employment for Landowners

The Project Affected Peoples and landowners lost their land for SEZs project in exchange of compensation. But it has been found that after acquiring the land they were totally helpless and jobless. The following table gives opinion of landowners who are awaiting employment in SEZs.

Table No. 6.41
SEZs Provide Employment for Landowners

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	%
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Yes	8	6	14	07 %
2	No	92	94	186	93 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.41. SEZs Provide Employment for Landowners

Above responses indicate reality of SEZ policy in respect of providing employment for landowners' peers in SEZs projects. In all only 14 (07%) respondents gave positive response in Konkan and Marathwada region when asked about employment generation under SEZs policy. On the contrary, majority of the respondents 186 (93%) registered negative response as they were constantly facing unemployment challenges after selling land to by SEZ projects in the residential areas.

Nature of Employment

There has been great debate over the special objectives of employment generation under Special Economic Zone policy as the established SEZ units showed negative response regarding enrolment of employees in the company. Thus, in order to understand the nature of appointment, the survey collected responses from the respondents who were deployed in the factories under SEZ.

Table No. 6.42: Nature of Employment

Sr. No.	Nature of Employment	Konkan Region		Marathwada Region	
		Respondents	%	Respondents	%
1	Permanent Employee	1.2	1.2 %	1	1 %
2	part-time employees	6.2	6.2 %	5.9	5.9 %
3	Contractual employee	2.5	2.5 %	2.8	2.8 %
4	Seasonal employees	35	35 %	42	42 %
5	Trainees	25	25 %	32	32 %
6	No employment	30.1	30.1 %	16.3	16.3 %
Total		100	100 %	100	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.42. Nature of Employment

Employment generation must have been sole aim of the SEZ policy as far as setting up SEZs in the rural and distant urban areas. But, the nature of employment and the scanty availability of employment and the hidden employment policy, due course of time, generated negative feeling among local public which was affected by the SEZ projects. In case of Konkan region, the data about nature of employment is alarming. It shows that just 01% people got permanently recruited in SEZ; 6.2 % got part-time employment; 2.5% are on Contractual basis; 35% get seasonal employment; 25% are Trainees and 30.1% find not job opportunity in SEZ projects. Similarly, in Marathwada region, 01% people got permanently recruited in SEZ; 5.9 % got part-time employment; 2.8% are on Contractual basis; 42% get seasonal employment; 35% are Trainees and 16.3% find not job opportunity in SEZ projects. It becomes clear from the data that despite the job assurance by SEZ policy the people are not satisfied over the nature of employment. Majority,

SEZs Provided Facility

After implementation of SEZ Act, 2005 one of the main objectives of the SEZ Act/policy was development to infrastructure facilities in the SEZ nearby areas.

In Konkan region wherein the SEZs units were to be implemented, many villages were presently connected with pucca road and telephone facilities and electric supply. Most villages have primary and secondary schools. For higher education villagers are dependent on nearby towns. Due to availability of schooling facilities, literacy rate in these villages is higher than the average literacy rate for the state (Maharashtra), and most of the youth are educated up to secondary and higher secondary levels. However, due to lack of technical education facilities, their skill levels are of general nature, which may not be very suitable for jobs in the Project. Most villages in Konkan region have health care sub-centres and almost all the villages have private doctors but they, in general, are quacks with the primary health centre at the Taluka headquarters. Except the villages immediately on the sea shore, all villages are connected with piped water supply.

However, in Marathwada region, where the SEZ units were scheduled to be established most of the area was surrounded by slum dwellers. Since, most of the SEZs were in MIDC area and newly acquired agricultural land, it was expected that basic infrastructure facilities were to be provided by the SEZ projects owners.

In Konkan and Marathwada region the farmers and agricultural workers, fishermen, salt pan workers, rice mill workers, transport workers and other workers allied to the agrarian economy who are rendered unemployed as their source of livelihood is threatened. As a result, many gaonthan or village settlements are made to survive on the heap of problems pertaining to livelihood. Following data shows factual situation prevailing around SEZs units and nearby villages.

Table No. 6.43
SEZs Provided Infrastructure Facility for Villages

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	Percentage
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Yes	42	20	62	31 %
2	No	58	80	138	69 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.43. SEZs Provided Infrastructure Facility for Villages

Above responses by total 200 respondents indicate ground reality of SEZ policy in respect of their responsibility towards welfare facility for villages and surrounded areas. In all 62 respondents gave positive response in Konkan and Marathwada region when asked about infrastructure facilities under SEZs policy. On the contrary, majority of the respondents (138) registered negative response as they were constantly facing road, electricity and water supply problems in the residential areas.

Table No. 6.44
SEZs Provide Health and Sanitations Facilities to rural Peoples

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	Percentage
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Yes	25	12	37	18.5 %
2	No	75	88	163	81.5 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.44. SEZs Provide Health and Sanitations Facilities to rural Peoples

Above responses by total 200 respondents indicate ground reality of SEZ policy in respect of their responsibility towards Health and Sanitation facility for villages and surrounded areas. In all 32 respondents gave positive response in Konkan and Marathwada region when asked about infrastructure facilities under SEZs policy. On the contrary, majority of the respondents (163) registered negative response as they were constantly facing health and sanitation problems in the residential areas.

Table No. 6.45
SEZ s Provide Water for Rural people or village

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	Percentage
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Yes	49	19	68	34 %
2	No	51	81	132	66 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.45. SEZ s Provide Water for Rural people or village

Supply of basic amenities such as water, road and electricity in rural areas needed utmost attention by the government agencies. Since, the SEZs are to be established in the rural area, it is expected that it should attend the rural problems too. Hence, in the survey the researcher found that SEZs are neglecting their responsibilities toward society. Majority of the respondents (132) expressed their concern over supply of water for rural people and villages. However, 68 respondents in Konkan and Marathwada region reported their positive response. Konkan region 49 respondents stated their positive response regarding availability of water due course of establishment of SEZs. In contrast, only 19 respondents expressed satisfaction over the SEZs projects in Marathwada region.

Does the SEZs Provide Road and Transportation facility for development of village

The following table gives the opinion about respondents for SEZs Project provide road and transportation facility for the development of villages

Table No. 6.46
SEZs Provide Road and Transportation facility for development of village

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	Percentage
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Yes	32	20	52	26 %
2	No	68	80	148	74 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.46. SEZs Provide Rode and Transportation facility for development of village

Responses in the above table indicate disillusion experienced by the village people after the establishment of SEZ projects. When enquired about the basic amenities such a road and transport facility provided by SEZ in the vicinity, 148 respondents from Konkan and Marathwada region reported negative response. In all 62 respondents expressed their satisfaction over the

facilities in the nearby villages. It can be concluded that SEZs have been neglecting their responsibilities towards the nearby areas.

Does the SEZs provide Communications and Technology for Villages

The following table gives the opinion about respondents for SEZs Project providing Communicational and Technology facility for the affected villages for development.

Table No. 6.47
SEZs provide Communications and Technology for Villages

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	Percentage
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Yes	36	27	63	31.5 %
2	No	64	73	137	68.5 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.47. SEZs provide Communications and Technology for Villages

The field survey attempted to assess the facilities provided by the SEZs units to the local inhabitants who in exchange of their land and labour forsook their land and assets. Since the inhabitants juxtaposed to techno-savvy area it is also expected that the locals too should get minimum benefits of any such telecommunication facility. When asked to the respondents about any such facility, in Konkan region only 36 respondents confirmed the availability of telecommunication supported by SEZs as compared to 27 least number of

respondents in Marathwada region. In contrast, maximum 64 and 73 respondents, in Konkan and Marathwada region respectively, gave negative reply to the question asking for any telecommunication facility made available by SEZs in the area.

Does the SEZ project provide education facility to affected villagers

The following table gives the opinion of the respondents for SEZs Project providing educational facility for the affected villages.

Table No. 6.48
SEZ project provide education facility to affected villagers

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	Percentage
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Yes	38	15	53	26.5 %
2	No	62	85	147	73.5 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.48. SEZ project provide education facility to affected villagers

Education is the primary requisite in order to generate skilled man power. However, sole responsibility to educate the masses is left with the government instead of industrialists who direly needed skilled workforce to carry out complex processes in factories and offices. In the survey, an attempt was made to assess the responsibility, whether, carried out by SEZ units to nurture talent among local inhabitants to get them involved in production

processes in factories. When asked about about the educational facility, if any, provided by the SEZs units in the locality, in Konkan region, only 38 respondents gave positive reply whereas maximum i.e. 68 of them told absence of any such institution run by the factory owners. Similarly in Marathwada region, around 85 respondents had no idea about any educational unit running in the vicinity that can harness the local talent to meet future man power needs of the SEZs.

It becomes clear that SEZ policy doesn't have any responsibility towards educating the future generation that would meet the demands of work-force in near future.

Does the SEZ Project provide electricity facility in the village

Table No. 6.49
SEZ Project provide electricity facility in the village

Sr. No.	Response	Konkan Region	Marathwada Region	Total	Percentage
		Respondents	Respondents		
1	Yes	52	18	70	35 %
2	No	48	82	130	65 %
Total		100	100	200	100 %

(Source: Compiled from filed survey, 2014-15)

Figure 6.49. SEZ Project provide electricity facility in the village

During the field survey it was observed that in the vicinity of MIDC area was surrounded by slums and residential localities. Most of the households live in scarcity of minimum infrastructure and amenities by the government

agencies. It came to know that the households were in need of urgent electrification facility on street and in houses. In Konkan region, 52 households mentioned that they are provided with electricity facility as compared to lowest 18 households in Marathwada region. Thus, the government should look into the matter in order to justify distribution of electricity facility to the 130 respondents i.e. 48 in Konkan and 82 Marathwada region households around the SEZs locality.

Concluding Remarks

The present chapter has deal with the data analysis and interpretation of responses collected during the field survey based on the scheduled questionnaire. The data acquired primarily focusses on livelihood patterns of affected people who lost their land assets and employment resources. This study uncovers the impact of the SEZ Act in Marathwada and Konkan Region of Maharashtra.

The analysis and interpretation is based on field survey undertaken in SEZs units in study area. For the purpose, over 200 respondents, 100 from each of the regions, including male and female workers, farmers, landowners, were selected who are directly and indirectly affected in SEZ units operational in the regions. It has been observed that majority of the farmers and general public in Navi Mumbai, Raigad, Ratnagiri of **Konkan region and Nanded, Latur, and Aurangabad** in Marathwada region staged protest against SEZ projects in the respective regions. This chapter brings forth factual reasons behind discontent among public who have been alleging irregularities in implementation of Labour Laws, Industrial Acts to promote SEZ policy. Thus, an honest attempt has been undertaken to highlight socio-economic aspects such as displacement issues, rehabilitation and resettlement of project affected people, rural development, industrial and infrastructural development, and urbanization in Konkan and Marathwada regions, in particular, as proposed to be addressed through SEZ policy.

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CHAPTER - VII

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter deals with major conclusions drawn, important suggestion and implications of SEZ policy in the Konkan and Marathwada region of Maharashtra state. In pervious chapters, the study attempted a critical analysis of Special Economic Zones (SEZs) and Rural Development in study area. It focused on SEZ project areas wherein general public and landowners felt its direct and indirect impact affecting their socio-economic development.

The establishment of SEZ units, as the proposed objectives imply, are promoted by government as helping hand in the rural development initiatives in Konkan and Marathwada regions in the state of Maharashtra. However, its positive and negative impact needed more attention by government itself. The SEZs have totally altered the social, cultural, political, economic conditions of general public in the target area. The study highlighted some of the key issues confronted by the general public living in and around the SEZ unit premises. With establishment of SEZ they expected employment generation, development of civil amenities like infrastructure facility, road and transportation, water and electricity facility in their locality. However, almost seventy five percent of the responses collected showed degraded condition of SEZ policy objectives.

As has been mentioned this research covered 13 districts in Konkan and Marathwada region including-Konkan: Mumbai, Thane, Ratnagiri, Raighad, Sindhudurg, and Marathwada region included Latur, Nanded, Parbhani, Osmanabad, Beed, Jalna, and Aurangabad. The responses collected are analyzed and conclusions, suggestion and recommendation were drawn concerning livelihood patterns of affected people who lost their land assets and employment resources.

The conclusions reflected plight of general public in terms of displacement issues, rehabilitation and resettlement of project affected people, rural development, industrial and infrastructural development, and urbanization in the said regions during the period 2006-2013.

Presentation of the Study

The *chapter first* dealt with the introduction of Special Economic Zones (SEZ) and SEZs Policy of government that aimed to address the economic condition of India. The chapter elaborated over the general problems faced by countries, Indian sub-continent especially, concept and establishment and evaluation of Special Economic Zones. And in Indian context issues like Global Debate on SEZs, experience in Chinese, history of SEZs, processing and non-processing areas, Exemption from taxes, duties or Cess and land acquisition, procedure of setting up SEZ units, future of SEZs an advantage, FDI policy on SEZ, benefits in India have been discussed.

An overall presentation of this chapter is detail analysis of data and assesses the significance of the Study, Objectives of the study, Hypothesis tested, Scope and limitations of the study and research methodology use Primary data and secondary data about SEZs of Marathwada and Konkan region state of Maharashtra is sources of factual information. Based on Radom Sample selection method 10% of present SEZs Industrial area and projected of SEZs taken for study. This chapter also discusses the research tools applied such as Tabulation, Recasting data as well as Graphs, Common Statistical tools, presentation of the study.

The *chapter second* focused on the scanned literature on Bibliometric study. The review of literature concerning SEZ and its implementation agencies dealt with SEZ projects and its implications of general public in India and Maharashtra state in particular. Several books and journals are scanned in order to identify the previous similar studies. Search on Internet bibliography of (AIU, 2009) database of theses and dissertation on (Inflibnet and

Vidhyanidhi, 2010) is used to formulate the topic for research and to check whether the research has been completed.

Chapter third highlights on the Policies of the state and central government regarding the SEZ and its implementation. It deals with SEZs Policies, Rules Regulation, and Guidelines for development of SEZs units, Special assistance and overall implementation of the policy.

Chapter fourth deals with the important aspect of Special Economic Zone (SEZs) and Rural Development. The government of India introduced a special economic zone (SEZ) Policy. The aim of the Policy is to promote export oriented industrial and economic development for the proponents of rapid development of India SEZs are engines of high economic growth. India is largest sector (Agriculture & Allied) in Indian economy and employing about 60 percent of the population. Chapter fourth Prepare for the SEZs and Its impact on Rural Development. *i.e.* employment, entrepreneurship, social, economic, and overall industrial and infrastructure development with the help of Special Economic Zones.

Chapter fifth highlights on the SEZs and Socio-Economic development in selected regions for the purpose of critical analysis of Special Economic Zones (SEZ) and Rural Development in Maharashtra State. In Konkan and Marathwada regions the establishment of SEZ units proposed socio-economic development harmonious construction of rural development by removing poverty, unemployment and backwardness of the rural people. Further it is aimed to foster economic growth by development of infrastructure and foreign direct investment (FDI). However, it was found that there are various problems the rural development under SEZ policy. Major issues are land acquisition process, compensation process to improve their performance, but very few people have received the apt compensation and due benefits of SEZ policy in the study area.

Chapter Six dealt with data collection and its analysis. The data in the form of responses forms the central part of this chapter. In order to collect data from Konkan and Marathwada region a questionnaire was designed. After that in the survey the researcher sought after the affected farmers and land owner who lost her land and entrepreneurs views, social activists, and general opinions of the people. The collected facts and figures are analyzed and interpreted. The data acquired primarily focusses on livelihood patterns of affected people who lost their land assets and employment resources. Thus, an honest attempt has been undertaken to highlight socio-economic aspects such as displacement issues, rehabilitation and resettlement of project affected people, rural development, industrial and infrastructural development, and urbanization in Konkan and Marathwada regions, in particular, as proposed to be addressed through SEZ policy.

In general it has been found that majority of the people residing in and around the SEZ units are unsatisfied with development process undertaken in the form of setting up a SEZ unit that almost functions as foreign territory. It has its rules and regulations that contradict with the law of the land. Further, it must be mentioned that there have been agitations in India and Maharashtra in particular to withdraw this SEZ Act. Hence, it is clear that general public demands growth and development, but not at the cost of tradition and livelihood assessments.

Chapter seventh overviewed major challenges before SEZ policy in India. There have been several problems in the implementation of SEZs as it has massive impact socio-economic bearings in selected regions in Maharashtra state. It concluded that the future prospects of the policy will depend on vision, a progressive approach, and strong commitment that reflect intense focus on growth, employment opportunity, infrastructural development, and adequate compensation to the land owner, cognizance of rehabilitation and resettlement problems of farmers.

Major Conclusions

This research study through its field survey, seeks to highlight and critically analyze the socio-economic plight of farmers, land owners, male and female worker, labourers etc. in terms of nature of employment, land acquisition, working population, environmental issues. It was an effort to ascertain the reasons behind discontent among localities that have been asserting their rights and the general failure of government to heed their protests. The following major conclusions are based on the critical analysis of SEZs in Konkan and Marathwada Regions

Major Conclusions

- Up to the year 2012-13 there are total 588 formal approvals, 49 in principle, 386 approvals are notified as SEZs, operational SEZs 158 Units in India. (Table No 4.1)
- Export performance of SEZs declined since 2011-12. It showed steep decline in its growth rate from 15.3 % to 4% in the year 2013-14. (Table No 4.2)
- Total land acquired for SEZs projects in Konkan region is 1543 (hectares) and Marathwada region is 3396 (ha)(Table No 4.4)
- Total land executed for SEZ units in Konkan 192 (ha) and in Marathwada region it is 225 (ha) (Table No 4.6)
- Total investment of SEZ in Konkan is 82,814 (crore) & in Marathwada regions it is 3,655 (crore) in the year of 2013. (Table No 4.7)
- Total SEZs 319 units exported products worth 12608 (Rs in Core) and its growth rate is 8.55 %. (Table No 4.8)
- Proposed employment generation under SEZs in Konkan region is 1.34 (lakh) & Marathwada region is 0.15 (lakh) (Table No 4.12)

- Majority of the respondents (148) from Konkan regions & Marathwada regions reported negative response over the civil amenities created by SEZs in the nearest villages (Table no 4.14)
- Setting up of SEZs in locality affected over 175 (87.5 %) Male and 25 (12.5 %) female respondents in villages and talukas places. (Table No 6.1)
- Majority of the respondents affected by the SEZs were in the age group of 15-35 years (Table No 6.2)
- It was found that majority of SEZ project affected people i.e. 66 in Konkan and 73 in Marathwada regions were married. (Table No 6.3)
- Maximum population affected by the SEZ was literate up to HSC and rests of them were illiterate. As a result majority of the population had no idea about the policy of SEZ which lead to agitation over the land acquisition and compensation issues. (Table No.6.4)
- Majority of the population (135) in both the regions was Hindu who own land and around 35 respondents belong to Buddhist community who have no land assets. (Table No 6.5.)
- Majority of the land acquired for SEZ was irrigated land which was used for various agricultural activities. When this land was acquired for SEZ the dependents families had to undertake sundry jobs in SEZ, industrial areas which alternatively lead to unemployment. (Table No 6.6)
- Majority of the respondents said that their land was fertile and seasonal crops used to be taken in that land and maximum of the respondents complained that their land was fertile and irrigated. In fact they all were depended on agrarian land for livelihood. refer (Table No. 6.12)

- Land holding in Konkan and Marathwada region. Maximum people (105) own the land that is in vicinity of SEZ area or is soon to be acquired for the purpose. refer (Table No 6.13)
- Respondents reported acquisition of land by SEZs project owned companies. (Table No 6.15.)
- It was found that nearly 153 respondents were completely unaware about the complex procedure of acquiring land. Lack of awareness about the land acquiring process resulted in growing complexities in problems in getting compensations for the landowners. refer (Table No.6.16)
- Around 122 respondents said that they had no idea about the type of SEZ project being established or in process in the vicinity. (Table No 6.17)
- Majority of the landowner resented the process. In Konkan (65) and Marathwada region (75), more than half of the respondents gave negative reply. (Table No 6.18)
- In Konkan region and Marathwada region most of the landowners reported that their land was acquired forcefully. (Table No 6.19)
- It is clear from the data that around 136 respondents showed reluctance over giving land for SEZ as compared to the 64 respondents who seemed to lured by the private companies in exchange of large monetary compensations. refer (Table No 6.20)
- Around 121 respondents in both the region reported there was certain pressure to sell the land and just 79 of them reported willingness to sell the land for SEZ. (Table No 6.21)
- The compensation from government agency or private company was not satisfactory. In Marathwada region most of the people staged more protest to get compensations. refer (Table No.6.23)

- In Konkan region total 63 and in Marathwada region 135 respondents registered their discontent over the compensation by government and private agencies. refer (Table No. 6.25)
- As total 71 people used money to establish new real-estate business and maximum 129 respondents preferred spending money for luxurious pleasures after getting the compensations. (Table No 6.26)
- In Konkan and Marathwada region total 71 people expressed satisfaction over the land deal, since they received compensation for the barren land. However, around 129 people were dissatisfied with land deals as they were forced to sell the land. refer (Table No 6.27)
- The source of employment/Job creation before the land acquisition for SEZs Projects. In both regions majority of the respondents depended on their farms for employment whereas others took to labours, daily wages. (Table No 6.30)
- Around 60 % respondents said that the SEZ is not providing employment in both regions. About 20% respondents got job as a Helper, Labour, Workers, Helper, and such types of directly and indirectly employment created in project affected areas. (Table No 6.31.)
- Majority of the respondents (155) expressed grave concerns over the employment in SEZ projects, whereas just 45 respondents could get jobs in the SEZ. It can be concluded that SEZ units in Maharashtra are not entitled to generate employment for the local people. refer (Table No 6.32)
- It is observed during the study that, few respondents could get entry into SEZ project sites, but they were asked about their job satisfaction it was realized that about 35 respondents strongly agree and 57 of the total respondents agree over the job satisfaction they conferred with.

However, around 48 and 70 respondents expressed disagreement and strongly opposed the stringent labour laws framed for SEZ territories. refer (Table No.6.33)

- 56 respondents including farmers, businessmen, men and women, workers, tribal landless labours reported that they come to know about SEZ from local leaders, business men, MIDC workers and government offices. On the contrary about 144 respondents had either no idea or paid heed to the SEZ units being set up under government regulation. Most of them got aware only when there was news about massive agitation in their area. This indicates ignorance about SEZ and government policies among general public in India. refer (Table No 6.35)
- Above responses highlight awareness about the general and specific information about SEZ established in the area once the SEZ policy was regularized in India. As per the findings in survey, around 40 respondents had detail idea about the setting of SEZ, its role, its operation, its ownership, its infrastructure, management, land acquisition and issues like foreign territory etc. However, majority 160 respondents of the public in Konkan and Marathwada had no idea about SEZ policy its detail provisions and outcomes. refer (Table No 6.36)
- 200 respondents asked question for whether you were aware about the purpose of land acquisition by SEZ. Only 93 respondents gave positive response in Konkan and Marathwada region about awareness process of land acquisition. On the contrary, majority of the respondents (107) registered negative response as they was not aware about SEZ land acquisition process. refer (Table No 6.37)
- 200 selected respondents in Konkan & Marathwada regions for how loss her land in SEZs project, what about job of these peoples. The researcher collected respond for both regions and observer by the total

40 respondents getting job for workers in SEZs project and his percentage is 20 %. 60 respondents are getting labourer work in SEZs project and that's total percentage is 30 %. And 30 respondents are getting Trainees job for projects and that is percentage is 15 % and 70 respondents are in other categories for and that percentage is 35%. Here easy understanding towards the SEZs project are not providing god job for farmers. Because, framers are not technically and highly educated and farmers also negative for project. Because, they loss his land for SEZ projects. (Table No 6.38)

- Total 200 respondents indicate ground reality of SEZ policy in respect of their generating employment for rural peoples and surrounded areas. In all only 21 respondents gave positive response in Konkan and Marathwada region when asked about employment generation under SEZs policy. On the contrary, majority of the respondents (179) registered negative response as they were constantly facing unemployment factors for due to suffer in land acquisition by SEZ projects in the residential areas. refer (Table No 6.39)
- Total 200 respondents male and females are indicate ground reality of SEZ policy in respect of their SEZs provide employment opportunities for women's. In all only 28 respondents gave positive response in Konkan and Marathwada region when asked about employment generation for women under SEZs policy. On the contrary, majority of the respondents (172) registered negative response as they were constantly facing unemployment factors for due to suffer in land acquisition by SEZ projects in the residential areas. refer (Table No 6.40)
- 200 respondents indicate ground reality of SEZ policy in respect of their providing employment for landowner in SEZs project. In all only 14 respondents gave positive response in Konkan and Marathwada region when asked about employment generation under SEZs policy. On the

contrary, majority of the respondents (186) registered negative response as they were constantly facing unemployment factors for due to suffer in land acquisition by SEZ projects in the residential areas. refer (Table No 6.41)

- Nature of Employment 3.2 % Respondents are got permanent Employment, and 12.1 % Respondents got Part-time, and 5.3 % Respondents got Cotrautal Employment, and 77 % respondent Getting Seasonal Employment, and 57 % respondents Getting trainees Job, and SEZs not provide employment for 46.4 % respondes said No employment in Konkan and Marathwada regions. refer (Table No. 6.42)
- 200 respondents indicate ground reality of SEZ policy in respect of their responsibility towards welfare facility for villages and surrounded areas. In all 62 respondents gave positive response in Konkan and Marathwada region when asked about infrastructure facilities under SEZs policy. On the contrary, majority of the respondents (138) registered negative response as they were constantly facing road, electricity and water supply problems in the residential areas. refer (Table No 6.43)
- 200 respondents indicate ground reality of SEZ policy in respect of their responsibility towards Health and Sanitation facility for villages and surrounded areas. In all 32 respondents gave positive response in Konkan and Marathwada region when asked about infrastructure facilities under SEZs policy. On the contrary, majority of the respondents (163) registered negative response as they were constantly facing health and sanitation problems in the residential areas. refer (Table No. 6.44)
- Majority of the respondents (132) expressed their concern over supply of water for rural people and villages. However, 68 respondents in Konkan and Marathwada region reported their positive response. Konkan region 49 respondents stated their positive response regarding

availability of water due course of establishment of SEZs. In contrast, only 19 respondents expressed satisfaction over the SEZs projects in Marathwada region. refer (Table No 6.45)

- Regarding the basic amenities such a road and transport facility provided by SEZ in the vicinity, 148 respondents from Konkan and Marathwada region reported negative response. It can be concluded that SEZs have been neglecting their responsibilities towards the nearby areas. (Table No 6.46)
- In Konkan region only 36 respondents confirmed the availability of telecommunication facility supported by SEZs as compared to 27 least number of respondents in Marathwada region. In contrast, maximum 64 and 73 respondents, in Konakan and Marathwada region respectively, gave negative reply to the question asking for any telecommunication facility made available by SEZs in the area. refer (Table No 6.47)
- To harness the local talent to meet future man power needs of the SEZs none of the SEZ is running education unit in Konkan and Marathwada region. (Table No 6.48)
- The government should look into the matter in order to justify distribution of electricity facility as majority of the respondents live in darkness without electricity in locality.

Important Suggestion

The state Government should create a land bank by acquiring infertile land and developing its manufacturing and connectivity to attract investors.

- To create a farmers investment fund. The Government can levy some taxes on the SEZs for a period of 25 years and the money should be spend solely to provide necessary inputs to the farmers in the area.
- The Government should frame a compensation policy on the implement it in right earnest.
- The landowners should be allotted with the share of the SEZs Companies on Preferential basis and at lower rate so that they become stakeholders in the company to which they have contributed by selling their land.
- The residential areas in the villages should not be acquired even if the surrounding land is. If the homesteads are left intact within the projects acquisition will not displace people from the area.
- Set up a Special Agricultural Zone in the interest of farmers than the SEZs.
- The whole policy of tax & tariff exemption needs to be reviewed.
- Government should identify rural areas where the land is non-productive, barren lands which really need to be development. This will serve the purpose of rural development, employment generation, and infrastructural development.
- Adopt Sons of the Soil Policy, to make justice with previous land owners.
- SEZs should be set up only on wasteland and non-agricultural land besides exhorting them not to intervene in land purchases made by private developers from original owners.

- Better infrastructural facilities in SEZ project areas, like cheap power supply, road networks and telecommunication services, investor friendly administration, good governance, especially with respect to labour laws etc. should be provided.
- Along with cash compensations the affected people must receive means of livelihood.
- New policy regarding the relief to common people should be drafted under National Rehabilitation Policy.
- Every industry that becomes part of a SEZ has to be treated at par with other enterprises.
- People's livelihoods must be protected, and socio-economic inequalities reduced rather than increased.
- SEZ policy completely bypassed the 73rd and 74th constitutional amendments, which give primacy to the Gramsabhas and Bastisabhas.
- The Govt. should revise the policy on SEZ as it goes against the interest of farmers and agricultural sector. It should not acquire fertile agricultural land for non-agricultural purposes.
- SEZ should look in to the matter of lack of job advancement opportunities. Women should be represented in supervisory and managerial positions.
- SEZ policy should address the large-scale migration in area and put significant pressure on socio-legal aspects such as weak social infrastructure, particularly regarding the provision of as decent housing, education, and health services.
- The present SEZ policy should check the in bypassing of Labour law in India which is being shaped by the unequivocal acceptance of the neo-liberal model of development not only as a means to promote economic

growth but also to enhance the employment net and thus secure wellbeing of labour.

- Fertile piece of land should not be allocated for SEZ development at any condition.
- Farmers should be taken in to full confidence before enforcing them to vacate their lands. External valuation agencies should be given the task of correctly pricing the land to be taken away from the farmers.
- State Governments should initiate skill programmes required by the SEZs manufacturers as regards the type of labour skills required and accordingly design such programmes.

Recommendations

1. The government employment schemes (Employment Guarantee Schemes) should have the objective of increasing the purchasing power of masses working in SEZs.
2. SEZ should create employment for local population which will generate employment for literate and skilled people.
3. Ban on acquiring the fertile and irrigated agricultural land by the Governments for SEZs.
4. Considerations of equity for farmers, farm workers and allied rural workers in the businesses operations in SEZs.
5. In order that farmers get to benefit from substantial value appreciation of their land minimum of 15 percent of the area in the processing and the residential/ commercial parts in the non-processing zone should go back to the farmers on pro-rata basis.
6. Each SEZ proposed must include a plan for rehabilitation of the people. The Development commissioner of the SEZ should be enjoined to oversee the implementation of the rehabilitation plan.

7. Tax incentives for business units in the processing zone of an SEZ should not be made available in the non-processing zone.
8. There should be special incentives for SEZ that are established closer to small towns.
9. There should be independent regulatory authority to deal with the issues related to the SEZs.
10. The union government should create New Township Development Policy with adequate provisions of housing, affordable means of mass transport, and access to basic social infrastructure amenities for peoples in the low-income category.
11. There should be guidelines to protect workers' rights and promote their welfare and also guidelines for environmental protection.
12. It will be advisable to recognize and acknowledge the 'right to information' of the local population, there are numerous questions, feeling, confusion, fear, anger and anxiety among the people over the project.
13. Common Property Resource (CPR) from a valuable part of socio-economic life of rural peoples. These includes common land, trees, ponds, community hall, community services (temples, masques, 'samadhis', schools, health care center, panchayat office, post office, PDF office, playground etc) community amenities (Water, Electricity, road, and communication facility) and natural resources (water, flora, and fauna). Project affected peoples need to be compensated adequately with all these basis community assets/ infrastructure at new side of rehabilitation. Wherever feasible, the common property resources (CRPs) need to be replicated.
14. In villages traditional skilled labours must be imparter with training for improvement of skills.

Future Scope for the Further Research

Further scope of the further research as based on geographic study of Maharashtra state. It is critical study of social and economic purpose of rural development of Maharashtra state with help of sustainable development of farmer policy as well as industrial policy of landowners. Scope of the further research is limited to Konkan and Marathwada region in selected overall 13 Districts which is Special Economic Zones its impact on rural people and to know the problems and prospects in implementation of SEZ and its impact's on rural people.

The critical analysis of special economic Zones (SEZ) and rural development in Maharashtra state with special reference to Konkan and Marathwada region, for the major scope of study to position of rural people in the state and its impact of farmer, land owner and industrial views and limitation on to region in Maharashtra. This is rapidly growth of industrial scenario to SEZs policy for socio-economic impact of rural people for the further study limitation on 2006-2013.

Concluding Remarks

This study highlights on the impact of SEZ and its impact on the society particularly in Konkan and Marathwada region. The researcher has selected only two regions but in future regions or state of Maharashtra, or India will have to be covered in future, to know the performance of SEZs and its impact. This study will also be cover the impact of SEZ and industrial development and different opportunities generated through SEZ by employment and related regions. The study will be useful to the Govt, industrial policy makers, research scholars, Academicians and other related policy makers. This type of studies will be helpful to the balance for regional imbalance and other related socio-economic developmental studies.

Annexure - I
Board of Approval

1	Secretary, Department of Commerce	Chairman
2	Member, CBEC	Member
3	Member, IT, CBDT	Member
4	Joint Secretary (Banking Division), Department of Economic Affairs, Ministry of Finance	Member
5	Joint Secretary (SEZ), Department of Commerce	Member
6	Joint Secretary, DIPP	Member
7	Joint Secretary, Ministry of Science and Technology	Member
8	Joint Secretary, Ministry of Small Scale Industries and Agro and Rural Industries	Member
9	Joint Secretary, Ministry of Home Affairs	Member
10	Joint Secretary, Ministry of Defence	Member
11	Joint Secretary, Ministry of Environment and Forests	Member
12	Joint Secretary, Ministry of Law and Justice	Member
13	Joint Secretary, Ministry of Overseas Indian Affairs	Member
14	Joint Secretary, Ministry of Urban Development	Member
15	A nominee of the State Government concerned	Member
16	Director General of Foreign Trade or his nominee	Member
17	Development Commissioner concerned	Member
18	A professor in the Indian Institute of Management or the Indian Institute of Foreign Trade	Member
19	Director or Deputy Secretary, Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Department of Commerce	Member

(Source: SEZ in India, Ministry of Comm. & Industry, Dept. of Comm.)

Annexure – II
Special Economic Zones Notified under the SEZ Act, 2005
Marathwada Regions

Sr. No	Name of the Developer	Location	Type	Area (hectares)	Date of Notification
1	Maharashtra Industrial Development Corporation	Shendre Industrial Area, District Aurangabad,	Aluminium and aluminium related industry	118.13	22th Dec 2006
2	Maharashtra Industrial Development Corporation	Village Krushnoor, Taluka Naigaon, District Nanded,	Pharmaceuticals	150	11 th Jan 2007
3	Maharashtra Industrial Development Corporation	Latur Industrial Area, District Latur,	Agro-processing	200 (61 denotified) total 139	15th Jan 2007/ 3rd February, 2010
4	Bajaj Auto Limited	Waluj Industrial Area, Within village limit of Pandhapur, Waladgaon and Kamalapur, of Taluka-Gangapur, District Aruagabad,	Automobiles and automobiles components	100.26	17 th April 2007
5	Wokhardt Infrastructure Development Limited	Shendre Five Star Industrial Ares, Aurangabad District,	Pharmaceuticals	107.06	17 th April 2007
6	Ajanta Projects (India) Ltd.	Plot No. C-22, MIDC, Shendre Five Star Industrial Area, District- Aurangabad,	Biotechnology	10	5 th Aug 2008
7	Ajanta Projects (India) Ltd.	Plot No. C-21, MIDC, Shendre Five Star Industrial Area, Aurangabad District,	pharmaceuticals	100	22 nd Oct 2008

**Annexure – III:
List of Formal Approvals Granted under the SEZ Act, 2005
Marathwada Regions**

Sr. No.	Name of the developer	Location	Type of SEZ	Area Hectares
1	Maharashtra Industrial Development Corporation Ltd.	Krushnoor, Dist. Nanded, Maharashtra	Pharmaceutical s	150
2	Maharashtra Industrial Development Corporation Ltd.	Latur, Maharashtra	Agro	200
3	Maharashtra Industrial Development Corporation Ltd.	Shendre, Dist. Aurangabad, Maharashtra	Alumium and Aluminium related industries	118.13
4	Wockhardt Infrastructure Development Limited	Shendre, Aurangabad Distt, Maharashtra	Pharmaceutical	107
5	Bajaj Auto Limited	Waluj, Aurangabad	Automobile and Automobile components	100
6	Ajanta Pharma Limited	Aurangabad	Pharma	100.43
7	Ajanta Pharma Limited	Aurangabad	Biotechnology Non-conventional Energy including Solar Energy equipment	10
8	Rajiv Gandhi IT Park Cooperative Society Ltd. Aurangabad	Survey No. 27, Girner, Paithan Road, Tal Aurangabad, Maharashtra	IT/ITES	10.21

**Annexure - IV:
In-Principle Approvals Granted under the SEZ Act, 2005
Marathwada Regions**

Sr. No.	Name of the developer	Location	Type of SEZ	Area in hectares
1	Gitanjali Gems Limited	Nanded, Maharashtra	Gems and Jewellery	50
2	Gitanjali Gems Limited	Aurangabad, Maharashtra	Gems and Jewellery	102

Annexure - V
Special Economic Zones Notified under the SEZ Act, 2005
Konkan Regions

Sr. No.	Name of the Developer	Location	Type	Area (hectares)	Date of Notification
1	Royal Palms (India) Pvt. Ltd.	Aarey Milk Colony, Goreganon (East), Mumbai.	IT/ITES	10.1 (additional land of 11.7hec)	11th Jan 2007/ 27 th June 2007
2	Hiranandani Builders	Village Powai, District Mumbai.	IT/ITES	12.5891	13 th April 2007
3	K. Raheja Universal Private Limited	Raheja Infocity –I, Plot No. 2/1/B, Block –D, Trans-Thane Creek Industrial Area, Maharashtra Industrial Development Corporation, Villages Kukshet and Shirvane, Opposite Juinagar Railway Station, Taluka-Thane, Navi Mumbai.	IT/ITES	20.654	13 th June 2007
4	Serene Properties Pvt. Ltd.	Kalwa Trans Thane Creek Industrial Area, MIDC, District Thane.	IT/ITES	19.34	2 nd Nov 2007
5	Navi Mumbai SEZ Pvt. Ltd.	Dronagiri, Navi Mumbai.	multi-product	1223.6767	21 st Nov 2007
6	Zeus Infrastructure Private Limited	Village Mulund, Taluka Kurla, District Mumbai Suburban and Village Kopri, Taluka Thane, District Thane.	IT/ITES	57.0979	23 rd April 2008
7	Navi Mumbai SEZ Pvt. Ltd.	Village Ulwe, Taluka Panvelo, District Raigad.	IT/ITES-B	38.28	8 th May 2008
8	Navi Mumbai SEZ Pvt. Ltd.	Village Ulwe, Taluka Panvelo, District Raigad.	IT/ITES-A	21.13	27 th May 2008
9	Gitanjali Gems Limited	Village Chirvat and Sangurli, Taluka Panvel, District Raigad.	Gems and Jewellery	10.035	9 th June 2008
10	Mahindra and Mahindra Limited	Village Owale, Ghodbunder Road, District Thane.	Bio-technology	22.32.7	2 nd July 2008
11	Sanvo Resorts (P) Limited	Village Kolkhe, Taluka Panvel, District Raigad.	IT/ITES	10-69-20	10 th July 2008
12	Saloni Business Park Private Limited	Villages Kharivali and Bhopivali, Taluka- Wada, District Thane.	Biotechnology	34.46.40	31 st July 2008
13	Navi Mumbai SEZ Pvt. Ltd.	Kalamboli, Navi Mumbai.	IT/ITES	103.0727	11th Aug 2008 /

					19 th May 2009
14	New Found Properties and Leasing Pvt. Ltd.	Trans Thane Creek Industrial Area, MIDC, Thane District.	IT/ITES	21.26	22 nd Aug 2008
15	Navi Mumbai SEZ Pvt. Ltd.	Kalamboli, Navi Mumbai.	multi-services	176.708	28 th Aug 2008
16	Sunny Vista Realtors Pvt. Ltd	Villages Talegaon and Panshil, Talukahalapur and village bhokarpada, TalukaPanwal, District Raigad.	Services Sector	139.83	19 th Feb 2009
17	Lodha Dwellers Pvt. Ltd.	Village Narivali, Taluka Thane, District Thane.	IT/ITES	32.67	12th March 2009
18	Navi Mumbai SEZ Pvt. Ltd.	Village Ulwe, Taluka Panvelo, District Raigad.	IT/ITES	10.77	12th March 2009
19	Uttam Galva Steels Ltd	Village Dahiwali, Taluka Khalapur, District Raigad.	IT/ITES	14.43.20	12th March 2009
20	MIDC	District Ratnagiri.	Pharmaceuticals	141.69.20	23 rd April 2009
21	Arshiya International Limited	Village Sai, Taluka Panvel, District Raigad.	FTWZ	45.76/ 6.985/0.890 / add 3.410 (Total 57.045)	4 th May 2009/ 5 th April, 2010/ 22nd July, 2010/ 27th October, 2011
22	Uttam Galva Steels Limited	Village Devnhave, Taluka Khalapur, District Raigad.	biotechnology	10-71-9	19 th June 2009
23	Karanja Infrastructure Private Limited	Village Chanje, Taluka Uran, District Raigad.	FTWZ	40-02-8	18th August 2009
24	Navi Mumbai SEZ Pvt. Ltd.	Village Ulwe, Navi Mumbai.	multi-services	128.4292	3rd September, 2009
25	Navi Mumbai SEZ Pvt. Ltd.	Village Ulwe Node, Navi Mumbai.	Gems and Jewellery	33.5403	3rd September, 2009
26	M/s. Empire Industries Limited (EIL)	Village Chikhholi, Taluka Ambernath, District Thane.	IT/ITES	14.16	2 nd July, 2010
27	Yashprabha Enterprises	Village Pathardi, Taluka Chiplun, District Ratnagiri.	Biotechnology	10.36	7 th July, 2010
28	Gigaplex Estate Private Limited	Villages Airoli and Dighe, District Thane in the State of Maharashtra	IT/ITES	11.74	11 th June, 2013

Annexure - VI
List of Formal Approvals Granted under the SEZ Act, 2005
Konkan Regions

Sr. No.	Name of the developer	Location	Type of SEZ	Area Hectares
1	Sunstream City Private Limited (Zeus Infrastructure Pvt. Ltd.)	Village Kopri, Taluka Thane, District Thane, Maharashtra	IT/ITES	54.22
2	Sinima Meadows Limited(formely Claridges Hotels Pvt. Ltd.)	Chawk in Khalapur Taluka of Raigad Distt.	Multi-Services	242
3	New Found Properties and Leasing Private Limited	Juinagar, Thane, Maharashtra	IT/ITES	21.41
4	Viraj Profiles Ltd	Village Aam Wada Tehsil, Distt Thane, Maharashtra	Stainless Steel Engineering Products	235
5	Mahindra Gesco Developers Ltd	Village Owale, Ghodbunder Road, Thane, Maharashtra	Bio-technology	28
6	Serene Properties Private Limited	Airoli, District Thane, Maharashtra	IT/ITES	14.07
7	Balaji Infra Projects Limited	Dighi Port, District Raigadh, Maharashtra	Port based SEZ for multi product inclusive of FTWZ	100
8	Gitanjali Gems Limited	Panvel Village, Chiravat, District Raigad, Maharashtra	Gems and Jewellery	10.2
9	Royal Palms India Private Limited	169, Aarey Milk Colony, Goregaon (E), Mumbai	IT/ITES	218
10	Maharashtra Industrial Development Corporation Ltd.	Lote, Parshuram, District Ratnagiri, Maharashtra	Pharma	200
11	Chiplun Infrastructure Private Limited (formerly FTWZ Ltd.)	Mumbai	FTWZ	40
12	Cornell Housing and Infrastructure Private Limited	Khari Village, Thane District, Maharashtra	IT/ITES	41
13	Lodha Developers Pvt. Ltd.	Thane, Maharashtra	IT/ITES	32
14	K. Raheja Universal	Navi Mumbai	IT/ITES	20.64
15	Bombay Industrial Corporation	Mahul, Mumbai	IT/ITES	12

16	Dosti Enterprises	Thane, Maharashtra	IT	45
17	Maharashtra Industrial Development Corporation Ltd.	Airoli Software Park, District Thane, Maharashtra	IT/ITES	60.7
18	Royal Palms India Private Limited	Survey No. 169, Aarey Milk Colony Goregaon (East), Mumbai	Gems and Jewellery	10
19	Sanvo Resorts Private Limited	Near Panvel - Palaspephata Junction, Maharashtra	IT/ITES	10
20	Uttam Galva Steels Limited (UGSL)	Khopoli, Taluka Khalapur, District Raigad, Maharashtra	Biotechnology	10.66
21	Uttam Galva Steels Limited (UGSL)	Khopoli, Taluka Khalapur, District Raigad, Maharashtra	IT/ITES	11.63
22	Navi Mumbai SEZ Private Limited (Kalamboli - Bio-Technology Division)	Kalamboli - Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra	Bio Technology	63.74
23	Navi Mumbai SEZ Private Limited (Kalamboli - Light Engineering Division)	Kalamboli - Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra	Light Engineering	179
24	Navi Mumbai SEZ Private Limited (Kalamboli – Pharmaceutical Division)	Kalamboli - Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra	Pharmaceutical s	103.25
26	Reliance Infocom Infrastructure Private Limited	Dhirubhai Ambani Knowledge City, Koper Khairne, Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra	IT/ITES	18.26
27	RNA Builders	Village Ghodbunder, Mira Road, Taluka and District Thane, Maharashtra	IT/ITES	13.5
28	Ferrani Hotels Private Limited/ Ozone Developers	Mumbai, Maharashtra	IT/ITES	27.73
30	Navi Mumbai SEZ Pvt. Ltd. (NMSEZ)	Dronagiri, Maharashtra	Multi product	1250
31	Sunny Vista Realtors Private Ltd	Village Bhokarpada, Panvel, District Raigarh, Maharashtra	Services	135.12
32	RNA Builders	Village Tivri and Rajawali, Taluka Vasai, District Thane, Maharashtra	IT/ITES	40.85
33	Navi Mumbai SEZ Private Limited	Ulwe, Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra	IT/ITES SEZ - A	21.13
34	Navi Mumbai SEZ Private Limited	Ulwe, Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra	IT/ITES SEZ - B	38.28

35	Navi Mumbai SEZ Private Limited	Ulwe, Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra	IT/ITES SEZ - C	13.53
36	Saloni Business Park Private Limited	Village Khariwli Taluka Wada, District Thane, Maharashtra	Biotechnology Park	27.24
37	Modern India Property Developers Limited	Village Khalapur, Taluka Khopoli District Raigad, Maharashtra	Electronic Hardware Software Incl. IT/ITES	14.77
38	Fama Estate Private Limited	Village Shivkar and Chikale, Taluka Panvel, District Raigarh, Maharashtra	IT/ITES	10.12
39	Rameshwar Vaibhav Development Pvt. Ltd.	Taluka Sudhagad, Raigad	IT/ITES	17.227
40	Essel Infraprojects Ltd. (Formerly Pan India Paryatan Ltd.)	Gorai-Manori-Uttan Region, Mumbai	Multi Services	110
41	JSW Jaigarh Port Limited	Kunbiwadi, Tal and District Ratnagiri, Maharashtra	Port Based SEZ	226.03
42	Arshiya Technologies International Limited	Village Sai, Taluka Panvel Maharashtra	FTWZ	68
43	Navi Mumbai SEZ Pvt. Ltd.	Village Ulwe, Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra	Multi Services	128.4292
44	Navi Mumbai SEZ Pvt. Ltd.	Village Ulwe, Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra	Gems and Jewellery	33.5403
45	Yashprabha Enterprises	A.P.Pathardi, TalukaChiplun, Dist. Ratnagiri, Maharashtra	Biotechnology	10.36
46	Marathon Pachin Infrastructure	Raigad, Maharashtra	Multi product	400
47	Empire Industries Limited (EIL)	Ambarnath, Thane distt., Maharashtra	IT/ITES	14.16
48	Veritas Infrastructure Development Limited	Village Shahbaez, Taluka-Alibaug, Distt. Raigad, Maharashtra	Biotech	11.54
49	Jawaharlal Nehru Port Trust (JNPT)	Navi Mumbai, Mumbai, Maharashtra	Port Based Multi Product	277
50	Gigaplex Estate Private Limited	Gigaplex, Plot No. 5, MIDC Knowledge Park, Airoli, Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra	IT/ITES	13.15

Annexure - VII
In-Principle Approvals Granted under the SEZ Act, 2005
Konkan Regions

Sr. No.	Name of the developer	Location	Type of SEZ	Area in hectares
1	Mumbai SEZ Limited	Gujarat Positra Port Infrastructural Ltd	Multi-product	5000
2	Supreme Petrochem Ltd	Taluk Roha, Raigad, Maharashtra	Plastic processing	100
3	Rewas Ports Limited	Rewas, District Raigarh, Maharashtra	Multi product	2850
4	Uttam Galva Group through Uttam Galva Steels Limited (UGSL) & Uttam Power & Steel Private Ltd. (UPSPL)	Khopoli, Taluka Khalapur, District Raigad, Maharashtra	Integrated Steel SEZ	100
5	ISPAT Industries Limited	Raigad District, Maharashtra	Multi Product	1012
6	Jafza Pvt. Ltd.	Raigad, Maharashtra	FTWZ	85.503
7	M/s. Videocon Industries Limited	Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra	Electronic Hardware and Software	100
8	Redi Port Ltd.	Post Redi, district Sindhudurg, Maharashtra	FTWZ	40
9	Quippo Infrastructure	Raigarh Maharashtra	Engineering	180

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